

Reproduction of Experimental Evaluations in Process Mining

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1 Introduction

Reproduction and replication of prior work is the corner stone of scientific research. It allows to test whether the conclusions drawn by a group of researchers also generalize to other context conditions (different researchers, different assumptions, different data, subjects, etc.). The most basic form is *reproduction* where the experimental or empirical evaluation that has been documented in the original study is repeated by a *different* (group of) researchers. Repeating the evaluation by applying the same method and techniques on the same data as in the original study allows to test whether results and interpretation described in the original study also hold outside of the original context.

In the following, we report on 16 reproductions of the experimental evaluations of 10 different studies in the area of process mining, predictive process monitoring, and text mining. Section 2 summarizes the method taken. Section 3 summarizes the main findings. Subsequently, this report contains all 16 reproduction reports to which consent for publication has been given.

2 Method

The reproductions were produced in the context of the Master-level research seminar 2IMI00 taken by 19 Master students at the Eindhoven University of Technology in preparation for their graduation project. The seminar assignment was to study, present, and discuss literature from the field of process mining and process analytics. Students could select from a list of articles proposed by the lecturer or propose their own literature. Finally, from all literature presented and discussed, each student was tasked to select one article and to attempt reproducing the experimental evaluation that had been reported in the article.

From the 19 students in the seminar, 16 consented to having their reproduction report to be included in this report. The following original articles have been selected by these 16 students for reproduction.

1. Raichelson, L., Soffer, P.: Merging event logs with many to many relationships. In: Fournier, F., Mendling, J. (eds.) BPM 2014. LNBP, vol. 202, pp. 330–341. Springer, Cham (2015). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-15895-2_28
2. Tax, Niek, Benjamin Dalmas, Natalia Sidorova, Wil M. P. van der Aalst and Sylvie Norre. “Interest-driven discovery of local process models.” *Inf. Syst.* 77 (2018): 105-117. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.is.2018.04.006>
3. Eck, Maikel L. van, Natalia Sidorova and Wil M. P. van der Aalst. “Discovering and Exploring State-Based Models for Multi-perspective Processes.” *BPM* (2016). http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-45348-4_9

4. Vadim Denisov, Dirk Fahland, Wil M. P. van der Aalst: Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Processes Performance from Event Data. BPM 2018: 139-157. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-98648-7_9
5. Tax, Niek, Ilya Verenich, Marcello La Rosa and Marlon Dumas. "Predictive Business Process Monitoring with LSTM Neural Networks." CAiSE (2017). http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-59536-8_30
6. Dongen, Boudewijn F. van, Josep Carmona and Thomas Chatain. "A Unified Approach for Measuring Precision and Generalization Based on Anti-alignments." BPM (2016). http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-45348-4_3
7. Xixi Lu, Dirk Fahland, Robert Andrews, Suriadi Suriadi, Moe Thandar Wynn, Arthur H. M. ter Hofstede and Wil M. P. van der Aalst. "Semi-supervised Log Pattern Detection and Exploration Using Event Concurrence and Contextual Information." OTM Conferences (2017). http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-69462-7_11
8. M. L. van Eck, N. Sidorova and W. M. P. van der Aalst, "Enabling process mining on sensor data from smart products," 2016 IEEE Tenth International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS), Grenoble, 2016, pp. 1-12. <https://10.1109/RCIS.2016.7549355>
9. Campos R., Mangaravite V., Pasquali A., Jorge A.M., Nunes C., Jatowt A. (2018) A Text Feature Based Automatic Keyword Extraction Method for Single Documents. In: Pasi G., Piwowarski B., Azzopardi L., Hanbury A. (eds) Advances in Information Retrieval. ECIR 2018. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 10772. Springer, Cham https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-76941-7_63
10. Garcia-Banuelos, Luciano, Nick R. T. P. van Beest, Marlon Dumas, Marcello La Rosa and Willem Mertens. "Complete and Interpretable Conformance Checking of Business Processes." IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering 44 (2018): 262-290. <http://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2017.2668418>

From these studies, the study by Denisov et al. [4] had been selected by 6 students, the study by Lu et al. [7] had been selected by 2 students, and all other studies have been selected by one student each.

The reproduction of the selected experimental evaluation had to be based on the original article using the data, assumptions, method, techniques, execution, and interpretative reasoning documented in the original article. In addition, students were allowed to reach out to the authors of the original study to enquire for additional information if necessary. They were asked to document their own method taken during the reproduction and the results obtain and to document any deviations they observe between their own method and the original method and between the results obtained and the results observed in the original method. The individual reproduction reports provide the details of the individual reproduction method taken.

3 Observations and Discussion

All studies chosen provided either an implementation that was freely accessible to the students or provided detailed descriptions of the algorithm or technique allowing (partial) reimplementations.

All students succeeded in – at least partially – reproducing the original studies. No original study could be reproduced exactly. The problems or deviations observed during the reproductions were

- Unavailability of data used in the original study

- Insufficient or unclear description of data pre-processing (without accompanying implementation)
- Mismatch between implementation available and technique described in the paper
- Mismatch between results (tables, plots, models) reported in the original study and own results obtained

However, for each original study, at least some claims or statements made in the conclusion in the original were considered by each student to be also holding in the reproduction.

This short summary does not attempt a more thorough analysis of the reproduction methods taken, the deviations observed, and the findings considered to be reproduced or not reproduced. A possible limitation of the reliability of all reproductions is the maturity and experience of the students in conducting and repeating experimental evaluations. As for most students, this was their first experimental evaluation, the lack of experience may have impacted their ability to reproduce the original study. However, one may argue that experimental evaluations should be documented precise and clear enough to allow reproduction even by less experienced researchers without influencing the validity of the conclusions.

- 1) R.A.J.J. van Delft. *Experiment Replication - Merging Event Logs with Many to Many Relationships* [1] pages 1-12
- 2) S. Esser. *Replication Report for the Paper: Interest-driven discovery of local process models by Tax et al.* [2] pages 13-33
- 3) S. Habets. *Replication report* [3] pages 34-38
- 4) M. Heinrich. *2IM100 Seminar: Paper Replication Report* [4] pages 39-44
- 5) M. Hrytsenia. *Report of results replication for "Unbiased, fine-grained description of processes performance from event data"* [4] pages 45-60
- 6) E.L. Klijn. *Experiment Replication Report: Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Processes Performance from Event Data* [4] pages 61-79
- 7) O. Koroglu. *Replication of Research Paper* [4] pages 80-96
- 8) A. Turu Pi. *Experiment Replication* [4] pages 97-126
- 9) L. Vugs. *Experiment replication of 'Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Processes Performance from Event Data' 2IM100 - Seminar architecture of information systems* [4] pages 127-138
- 10) A. Karetnikov. *Experiment results on repeatability of Predictive Business Process Monitoring with LSTM by Tax N., Verenich I., La Rosa M. and Dumas M.* [5] pages 139-145
- 11) J. Leander. *2IM100 Replication Report* [6] pages 146-156
- 12) J.W.H. Nooyen. *2IM100 Replication Report* [7] pages 157-168
- 13) I. Vagionitis. *2IM100 Experiment Replication "Semi-supervised Log Pattern Detection and Exploration Using Event Concurrence and Contextual Information"* [7] pages 169-177
- 14) S. J. Ruiz Sainz. *Paper replication. From original paper: Enabling Process Mining on Sensor Data from Smart Products* [8] pages 178-189
- 15) F. Shafiee. *Replication Report* [9] pages 190-199
- 16) R. Uku. *Experiment/Evaluation Replication Report Complete and Interpretable Conformance Checking of Business Processes* [10] pages 200-224

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Experiment Replication

Merging Event Logs with Many to Many Relationships

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After research by [Raichelson and Soffer2014]

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1 Introduction

The paper of [Raichelson and Soffer2014] introduces a way to combine event logs that were otherwise hard to combine, with many to many relationships, and with case ID's that are not directly comparable. This report will focus on the technique introduced in this paper, and will review if it is possible to reach similar results as the evaluation presented in the paper. To do so, the report will try to reproduce the data and the tools used by [Raichelson and Soffer2014]. Since the researchers were not always clear about the used tools and data, assumptions will be made in order to reach somewhat comparable results.

2 Data acquisition

The paper uses multiple data sets. The first data set, to introduce the problem, is mentioned fully in the tables of the paper. Secondly, they started using synthetic logs. These logs are generated, but not included or linked in the paper. I can investigate the use of our own generated synthetic logs, and review if this yields comparable results. Finally, they have used the logs of the 2014BPI challenge.

2.1 Running example

The first data set is the running example mentioned in the paper. To use the running example, which will prove useful when testing the implementation, conversion to comma separated value files is needed. Copy pasting the table in Microsoft Excel and exporting to .csv prove sufficient, a notepad tool was used to convert semicolons to comma's and filter out Excel information.

2.2 Synthetic log generation

The research of [Raichelson and Soffer2014] does not actually state how the logs are generated. It specified a process model for each of the relationships that were introduced earlier in the paper, but these models are not included. For example, the mandatory fields, like department numbers, could still deviate a lot. Fortunately, these mandatory fields were stated, but again, there is no indication if optional fields were included too. The wording might suggest such model is present, stating: *'We generated event logs specifying a process model [...] as shown in Table 5'*. Table 5 on the other hand only includes the number of cases that were created. Without the process models used to generate the synthetic logs, it seems unlikely that synthetic logs I generate will be very familiar to those used in the paper. This is a problem, since I then will be unable to evaluate if the algorithm I made based on the instructions of the paper actually make sense. Either the data used by the researchers, or the tools they used to make a functioning algorithm should have been included in order to verify the replication (e.g. reach similar results). Further in this paper I will try to replicate the final algorithm, but unfortunately, it can only be tested on this data set.

2.3 2014BPI

The paper of [Raichelson and Soffer2014] used the logs of the 2014BPI challenge. Although these logs were not linked in the paper, they are still available. This data set, which was presented by [Van Dongen, B.F. (Boudewijn)2014], can be downloaded from the 4TU repository. This makes the data acquisition rather straightforward. However, there is a caveat: The research does not specify which of the four data sets they use. Neither do they acknowledge which one of them is the main process, and which one of the data sets qualify as sub process log. [Raichelson and Soffer2014] do mention that the main process log contains 26,876 instances and the sub process log contains 21,960 instances. All sets downloaded from 4TU seem to have a different amount of instances.

3 Implementation

Starting to replicate the research is only possible when I have an overview which steps are taken to come towards the mentioned algorithm, and how the algorithm was implemented. For the last part, I will remain in darkness: no actual implantation of the algorithm in programming language was mentioned. Using the algorithm mentioned in the paper, I can try to approximate its functioning with a common programming language like Python. From now on, I assume Python was used. Since an extensive library of tools for Python is available, I'll try to match the given functions in a way that the resulting algorithm would behave in a similar fashion as the program the researchers might have build to support their statements. I've used Anaconda as an editor, so the packages choices are made based on what is available for Anaconda.

3.1 Match_time

The algorithm starts with an important function: to check the time against the constraints of chapter 2.1 in [Raichelson and Soffer2014]. Allen's interval algebra is hard to find as a specifically available package. The three temporal relations expressed in the aforementioned logic are however easily implemented by hand. The following requirements should be implemented:

- The sub process should start after the beginning of the main process.
- The sub process should have time overlap with the main process - so it should start before the main process has ended.

This would result in the following 3 temporal relations, again as mentioned in [Raichelson and Soffer2014].

- The main process overlaps with the sub process.
- Sub process starts with the main process.
- Sub process starts during, and finishes with the main process.

The requirements can be satisfied with the following code.

```
def match_time(case_main_log, case_sub_log):
    if case_main_log['Timestamp'][0] < case_sub_log['Timestamp'][0]
    and case_sub_log['Timestamp'][0] < case_main_log['Timestamp'][-1]:
        return True
    else:
        return False
```

3.2 word_set

We also need a wordset to be determined out of all attributes, containing all unique values for a case id. In the algorithm chapter of the paper, the word set is determined as the set holding all the attributes of a case. For now, I assume that, since they did not include the timestamp when explaining the working of the algorithm over the running example, the timestamp is not an attribute of the case. This seems to make more sense as well when checking for similarity. The function to get the resulting set:

```
def word_set (log):
```

```
log = log.drop(columns="Timestamp")
columns = list(log)
log['wordset'] = ''
for column in columns:
    log['wordset'] = log['wordset'] + ' ' + log[column].map(str)
log = log['wordset'].str.cat(sep=' ').split(' ')
wordset = list(set(log))
wordset = wordset[1:]
return wordset
```

3.3 check_Match_Score

This function should return an integer value, which [Raichelson and Soffer2014] calls the the calculated similarity score of attribute values between the cases. Chapter 2.1 of the report mentions TF-IDF. The scikit-learn package for Python, included in Anaconda, has exactly such function for TF-IDF.

```
def check_Match_score(set1, set2):
    vectorizer = TfidfVectorizer()
    return vectorizer.fit_transform([set1, set2])
```

However, the description for the running example is different, since [Raichelson and Soffer2014] states: *" In our running example the bag of unique words of the 1st case in the main log (Table 1) would be 3001, Ilana, 1234, 1235, 89 and the bag of unique words of the 1st case in the sub log (Table 2) would be 5001, Mosh, 1234, 89, 79. The similarity score would hence be 2. "* Since the wordsets are defined as bags of unique words, the term frequency of a single term is 1 divided by N, the total number of terms in a set. We could calculate that as follows:

```
def cal_tf (case_log, name):
    wordset = pd.DataFrame(word_set(case_log))
    wordset = wordset.set_index(0)
    wordset['tf-' + str(name)] = 1 / len(wordset.index)
    return wordset
```

After this, I build a list of unique words, the subset follows a similar process:

```
# Calculate words that are not used in every case of main
for case_id in mainCaseID[0]:
    case_log = mainProcessLog.loc[mainProcessLog['CaseID'] == case_id]
    case_tf = cal_tf(case_log, case_id)
    main_wordset = pd.concat([main_wordset, case_tf], axis=1)
    main_wordset['unique'] = main_wordset.isnull().any(axis=1)
    main_unique = main_wordset.index[main_wordset['unique'] == True].tolist()
```

3.4 Algorithm

Having determined all functions needed for the algorithm to work, I will translate the algorithm itself to a working python code counterpart. The result is seen below. Note that the strings 'Order' and 'Delivery' correspond to the case ID's used in the running example. When using different datasets, these terms need to be adjusted to match with the column describing the case ID in these datasets. I assume this is done manually in the described method.

```
# Import functions
import pandas as pd
import os
# Set data directory
working_dir = r'D:\Users\Roeland\Desktop\Experiment-Replication\data\ '
os.chdir(working_dir)
# Import data

# Import Main process log
# Read csv
mainProcessLog = pd.read_csv("mainprocess.csv", engine='python')
# Find caseID
mainProcessLog = mainProcessLog.rename(index=str, columns={'Order': 'CaseID'})
# Convert timestamp
mainProcessLog['Timestamp'] = pd.to_datetime(mainProcessLog['Timestamp'])
# List caseID's
mainCaseID = pd.DataFrame(mainProcessLog["CaseID"].unique())

# Import Sub process log
# Read csv
subProcessLog = pd.read_csv("subprocess.csv", engine='python')
# Find caseID
subProcessLog = subProcessLog.rename(index=str, columns={'Delivery': 'CaseID'})
# Convert timestamp
subProcessLog['Timestamp'] = pd.to_datetime(subProcessLog['Timestamp'])
# List caseID's
subCaseID = pd.DataFrame(subProcessLog['CaseID'].unique())

# Set up dataframes

main_wordset = pd.DataFrame()
sub_wordset = pd.DataFrame()
```

After this setup part, I further analyzed the algorithm to come up with the following:

```
# Final algorithm

for case_id in mainCaseID[0]:
    # Get case ID log
    case_main_log = mainProcessLog.loc[mainProcessLog['CaseID'] == case_id]

    # Get all unique words in this log
    main_case_wordset = word_set(case_main_log)
```

```
main_case_wordset = list(set(main_case_wordset) & set(main_unique))

for case_id_sub in subCaseID[0]:
    # Get case ID log
    case_sub_log = subprocessLog.loc[subProcessLog['CaseID']
    == case_id_sub]

    # Get all unique words in this log
    sub_case_wordset = word_set(case_sub_log)
    sub_case_wordset = list(set(sub_case_wordset) & set(sub_unique))

    if match_time(case_main_log, case_sub_log):
        similarityScore = len(list(set(sub_case_wordset)
        & set(main_case_wordset)))
        match_scores.loc[case_id,case_id_sub] = similarityScore
```

4 Replication

4.1 Running Example

First, the running example is evaluated. Although the running example results are mentioned in chapter 2.3 of [Raichelson and Soffer2014] instead of chapter 3 Evaluation, a successful run of the example can prove that the algorithm I have implemented functions somewhat similar to the algorithm used in the research.

The first run is not completely successful. Let's review the description of the case to find out if this is intended behaviour. [Raichelson and Soffer2014]:

It allows filtering out words that are common to all cases [...] similarity score of two cases is calculated as the count of unique words that are common to them. In our running example the bag of unique words of the 1st case in the main log (Table 1) would be 3001, Ilana, 1234, 1235, 89 and the bag of unique words of the 1st case in the sub log (Table 2) would be 5001, Mosh, 1234, 89, 79. The similarity score would hence be 2.

My algorithm concludes that the similarity score between these cases is 0. This is because 1234 is not unique to case 1, since it also occurs in case 2 of the main process log. Similarly, 89 is not unique to the first case of the sub process log, since it occurs in the second log as well. To reach similar results, I need to manually mark them unique.

```
main_unique.append('1234')
sub_unique.append('89')
```

Then I reach the same similarity scores.

	5001	5002
3002	2.0	2.0
3001	1.0	1.0

I'm also able to reach a similiar unifiedLogFile:

Index	new_case_ID	CaseID	Timestamp	User	Activity	Item no	Department
0	3001-A	3001	2014-02-02 10:12:00	Ilana	open order	1234 1235	dep. 89
1	3001-A	3001	2014-02-02 10:13:00	Tsvi	approve order	1234 1235	dep. 89
2	3001-A	3001	2014-02-02 13:16:00	Ilana	check status	1234 1235	dep. 89
0	3001-A	5001	2014-03-02 11:45:00	Mosh	receive item	1234	nan
1	3001-A	5001	2014-03-02 16:15:00	Mosh	send to dep.	1234	dep. 89
2	3001-A	5001	2014-03-02 16:15:00	Mosh	send to dep.	1234	dep. 79
3	3001-A	3001	2014-03-02 16:18:00	Ilana	receive item	1234	dep. 89
3	3001-A	5002	2014-04-02 12:46:00	Mosh	receive item	1235 1236	nan
4	3001-A	5002	2014-04-02 16:30:00	Mosh	send to dep.	1235	dep. 89
5	3001-A	5002	2014-04-02 16:31:00	Mosh	send to dep.	1236	dep. 79
4	3001-A	3001	2014-04-02 16:35:00	Ilana	receive item	1235	dep. 89
5	3001-A	3001	2014-04-02 16:36:00	Ilana	close order	1234 1235	dep. 89

Figure 4.1: A unified log of the running example

A small difference can be spotted in the comparison between my result and the result in the report of [Raichelson and Soffer2014]. The [Item no] column in the final row of my table includes two item numbers, these are not present in their table. I suppose they made a misprint, since these numbers are present at the same activity, at the same time, in Table 1. of their report.

4.2 Synthetic logs

As stated in the data acquisition part, generating synthetic logs without essential information on the models they used requires a lot of assumptions. Since my algorithm is already different from theirs, getting exactly the same results is highly unlikely.

4.3 2014BPI

Although the 2014BPI challenge is used, all data sets there seem to have a different number of instances. Furthermore, they only mention the time the calculation took, not any of the results. They do give an indication of the usability: it can only be estimated, which they do not. Since a lot of research is done using this set, real matches might have been researched before. My algorithm only shares the idea behind theirs, and not the code, since this was not included in their paper. This means that my calculation time for the unified log is simply incomparable to theirs. It is likely that my code includes functions that could be optimized. Moreover, the computers used for the calculation are different as well. Their time indeed stays merely an indication of the scalability.

5 Conclusion

The choice for the paper of [Raichelson and Soffer2014] was based on the fact that it presents an algorithm and generates results. Initially, this would have made the paper easier to replicate. However, unlike some other papers, that finalize with publishing tool kits, or that include log data used to evaluate their algorithm, this paper remained rather obscure in their precise details. That made it substantially harder to ensure similar results. It would have been better if either the toolkit they used in the paper, the synthetic logs, or the process model they used to generate these logs would have been available. Especially the time indication they have mentioned is nearly impossible to replicate. The recall and precision in the paper are greatly depended on the synthetic logs. Moreover, the small details needed to implement the algorithm in programming language raised some questions too. Overall, the researchers are able to explain their solution and present the needed information, but the lack of details on the way they have implemented the presented methods themselves make replicating much harder.

Bibliography

[Raichelson and Soffer2014] Raichelson, L. and Soffer, P. (2014). Merging event logs with many to many relationships. pages 330–341.

[Van Dongen, B.F. (Boudewijn)2014] Van Dongen, B.F. (Boudewijn) (2014). Bpi challenge 2014.

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Replication Report for the Paper: Interest-driven discovery of local process models by Tax et al.

2IMI00 - Seminar Architecture of Information Systems

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1 Introduction

This report is to document a replication attempt of the findings of Tax et al. from his paper: *Interest-driven discovery of local process models* [1]. The replication is conducted in the context of the seminar of analytics for information systems (2IMI20). The paper is concerned about the discovery of local process models (LPM) and their selection based on a particular question on the context of the respective process. The goal of this replication is to apply the proposed methods on the same or similar data and to get comparable results as in the paper. In chapter 2 a more detailed description of the paper's contents is provided. Chapter 3 shows how the replication was conducted, the results of the replication and a comparison to the findings of the paper. Thereafter, the conclusions drawn from the replication are depicted in chapter 4.

2 Contents of the Paper

2.1 Summary

The paper that is subject to this replication attempt is the extension of the local process model (LPM) discovery technique introduced in [2]. This technique aimed to discover LPMs mainly based on characteristics like support and confidence. The new approach of Tax et al. [1] is to enrich LPM discovery with semantics such that LPMs are selected based on a specific (business) question that comes from domain experts. The motivation is to provide a solution that provides better support for business process improvement compared to the focus on frequent behavior of traditional LPM discovery. To evaluate their approach, 3 case studies have been conducted.

2.2 Approach

For this approach, the discovery technique from the first paper was used with new selection criteria. The selection criteria for the interest-driven LPM discover is very specific to the event data and question that should be answered by analyzing the data. The authors introduce the notion of utility functions and constraints to LPM discovery. Utility functions can be the remaining payments throughout a trace or the time between two consecutive events. Generally speaking, constraints can be described as utility functions with utility-specific thresholds.

They distinguish between model-, trace-, activity- and event-level constraints and utility functions. The model-level is concerned with the structural characteristics of the LPMs, e.g. they should all start with some activity a . The remaining cost example from the previous paragraph is an example of trace-level utility. For activity-level utility functions a domain expert can specify how much or little he is interested in certain activities. On event-level utility functions the utility, e.g. costs, are specific to single events.

2.3 Case Studies

In the following paragraphs, the three case studies and the respective findings of the paper are introduced.

2.3.1 Road Traffic Fines

The road traffic fine data set comprises data about a road traffic fine management process. The process instance starts with the creation of a fine with a specific amount. Administrative expenses are added to the amount invoiced. Such a fine may be appealed and different activities can increase, e.g. a penalty for late payment, or decrease, e.g. the payment of (parts) of the invoiced amount. The event log has 150370 traces, 561470 events and 11 activities.

In this case study, trace-level utility functions were illustrated with the the question: "which process fragments describe fines where the remaining amount to be paid is high?". In other words, our utility in this case is money and every event of a trace got an additional attribute stating the leftover amount to be paid throughout the process instance. Figure 2.1 shows the three LPMs discovered with maximum utility on the road fines data set.

Figure 2.1: Road Fine LPMs found with Utility [1]

The LPMs found describe different parts of the overall process. The second LPM for example the part where an appeal is registered. Furthermore, the second LPM indicates that between the registration and the further processing of the appeal the amount grows, i.e. additional penalties for late payment are added.

2.3.2 IT Service Desk Incidents

For this case study IT-service incident events of a dutch financial institution have been assessed to illustrate event-level utility functions. *Service component WBS*, the component affected by an incident, *Closure code*, a result category, and *causedBy*, the component that caused the incident, in combination with *Number of interactions*, the number of phone calls or e-mails required to solve the incident, have been utilized to answer the question: "which process fragments are related to high numbers of e-mails and phone calls to the IT service desk?". Figure 2.2 shows the two LPMs with the highest utility found in the case study.

Figure 2.2: Incident LPMs found with Utility [1]

The first LPM shows that there was one specific incident with *Closure code* = "Software application" and *causedBy* = "WBS000073" with a very high impact.

2.3.3 Smart Home

The third case study was conducted on smart home data collected by Tapia et al. [3] using various sensors to identify activities of daily living. The data set included data from two households. The case study focused on the data of one of the two houses and by adding a constraint "time between events ≤ 2 minutes". Figure 2.3 and figure 2.4 show the found LPMs without and with the constraint respectively.

Figure 2.3: Smart Home LPMs found without Constraints [1]

Figure 2.4: Smart Home LPMs found with Constraints [1]

The difference indicates that on certain event data, it can be useful limit LPMs to their temporal (or other utility's) context in order to increase the likelihood of a causal relationship between events in a LPM.

3 Replication Results

3.1 Methodology

The replication focuses on the utility and constraint related findings of the paper. In order to enable the reader of this report to reenact the steps performed, the following methodology has been applied for all three case studies:

1. Find/get data set or a comparable data set
2. Identify ProM plugin(s) likely to be suitable for the question
3. Sample/prepare the data according to the question
4. Iterate over data preparation, processing and result analysis
5. If necessary, analyze the plugin implementation for deeper insights

3.1.1 Road Traffic Fines

The road fines data set is publicly available¹ and contains 150370 cases, 561470 events and 11 activities. To discover LPMs with high utility, I identified the following plugin candidates:

- *Search for High Utility Local Process Models*
- *Search for Maximal Utility Local Process Models*
- *Search for Utility-Closed Local Process Models*

While the first plugin seems to work similar to the tradition LPM discovery plugin *Search for Local Process Models*, as it offers an interface to select options such as "Projections", the other two failed to start due to a mismatch between the expected and the returned output (java class) of the plugin in the first attempts.

The data preparation for the trace-level was done by adding or subtracting the remaining amount to be paid to each event of a trace. Fortunately, a plugin named *Preprocess Road Fine with remaining_amount* is available and assumed to be the plugin used for the original experiment of the paper. However, after verification of the output log of this plugin it became clear that the plugin does not always correctly calculate the remaining amount correctly - compared to the description in the paper. Please see appendix A.1 for more details. For the replication, I decided to keep the false results in order to achieve better comparability and produced a second plugin that would produce the correct results. The key data of the resulting log (see appendix A.2) were the same as the original log, but with an attribute *Costs* added to each event with the respective value of the trace-utility function. A sample of 2000 cases was used to test the plugins.

By using the *Preprocess Road Fine with remaining_amount* plugin, the log became usable as input for the *Search for Maximal Utility Local Process Models* plugin, while the other two candidates did not work with any sample size nor with the full log. Intuitively, this plugin was most promising anyways, even though I was not able to fully comprehend its behavior by inspecting its code².

By using the *Maximal Utility Local Process Models* plugin, I received the following LPMs:

¹<https://doi.org/10.4121/uuid:270fd440-1057-4fb9-89a9-b699b47990f5>

²<https://svn.win.tue.nl/trac/prom/browser/Packages/LocalProcessModelDiscovery/Trunk/src/org/processmining/lpm.../discovery/MaximalUtilityLocalProcessModelDiscovery.java>

Figure 3.1: Road Fine LPMs with High Utility

Unfortunately, I was not able to enforce a certain structure of the discovered event log, e.g. put a constraint "Must start with activity *Create Fine*" and the nice representation seen in the paper was for accepting petri nets could also not be achieved. All attempts to save/further process the output of the *Search for Maximal Utility Local Process Models* plugin (*LocalProcessModelRankin.class*) failed with java exceptions. However, the general goal of LPM discovery and selection based on a trace-utility function can be considered as achieved and also the time it took to discover the LPMs was roughly 30-40 minutes. The correction of the utility calculations did not significantly change the resulting LPMs.

3.2 IT Service Desk Incidents

Also the incident dataset is publicly available³. The complete dataset comprises of four different tables that contain different details of a service management system. From the description of the dataset in the paper and the shown LPMs I was able to identify the "Detail_Incident.csv" file as the log used in the case study. It consists of 275 cases (*Service component WBS*), 46808 events and 1375 activities (*Closure code + causedBy*).

Since the second case study is similar to the first, the ProM plugin candidates are the same:

- *Search for High Utility Local Process Models*
- *Search for Maximal Utility Local Process Models*
- *Search for Utility-Closed Local Process Models*

The same problems have been faced as before with the incidents dataset.

The first preparation was done on the original .csv file with the help of Python. Because there was no option in any of the aforementioned plugins to define attribute in the log shall be used as "utility" for the LPM selection, there was the need of a code inspection of the *Search for Maximal Utility Local Process Models* plugin. This revealed that the "Costs" attribute was predefined as the utility attribute. First, I removed empty columns from the file. For the incident case study a event-level utility function was used for the number of interactions within one incident. Thus, the column "# Related Interactions"

³<https://doi.org/10.4121/uuid:c3e5d162-0cfd-4bb0-bd82-af5268819c35>

was renamed to "Costs". All rows with empty value in the *Service component WBS* column were removed, since the case identifier is mandatory for a meaningful event log. Then, the log was ordered by case and "Close Time" to create the event log with case related ordering as required for process event logs [4]. If an incident did not have any "# Related Interactions", it got a 0 assigned and to reduce the size of the log, only the columns deemed useful for the question have been kept in the log. An "Activity" column was created such that "*Number of interactions | CausedBy*" represents the activity as stated in the paper. Three columns of the log had a "(CBy)" attached to their column name, but from the figures and descriptions of the paper it was clear that "ServiceComp WBS (CBy)" was the correct column for *CausedBy* in the prepared log. Furthermore, the newly created "Activity" column was checked whether it contained placeholder values that do not provide specific information, such as "Unknown" or "Other", and filtered accordingly. The result was a log with 248 cases, 25957 events and 995 activities. Please refer to appendix B.1 for the Python script used. However, feeding this log to the *Search for Maximal Utility Local Process Models* or *Search for High Utility Local Process Models* plugin resulted in either java exceptions or seemingly endless runs, regardless of the configuration of the respective tool or sample size. Interestingly, the log did not trigger the "headless" run like the prepared log for the road fines did.

The data preparation with Python was not successful. Presumably because the *Search for Maximal Utility Local Process Models* accepts different parameters as input and the created XES file lacked certain parameters to initialize the plugin with a standard configuration for this experiment. Thus an interface similar to the original *Search for Local Process Models* appeared and different sets of configurations all lead to java exceptions or very long runs that even lasted several hours without finishing.

The second approach to replicate the results on the incidents data set was to facilitate the original plugins⁴ that have likely been used by the authors to conduct their experiments. Even though none of the BPIC14 specific preparation plugins produced the described log for this case study, the structure was used to create a custom plugin (see appendix B.2), expecting the incidents log (in CSV format) to be transformed to XES with *service component WBS* as activity identifier. The plugin will then rewrite the log with *service component WBS* as case and *closure code | causedBy* as activity identifiers and, presumably, the right log parameters to trigger the "headless" run of the *Search for Maximal Utility Local Process Models*. The resulting log consists of 249 traces (313), 26159 events (25262) and 996 activities (944). Even though the numbers are somewhat close and the different amounts of events and activities might be explained by different filtering/preparation, the amount of different *service component WBS* values in the entire log totals to 275, including empty value.

The author states that the discovery and selection process lasted round two minutes on an Intel i7 CPU @ 2.4 GHz with 16 GB of memory. This seems counter intuitive, because the computational time for LPM discovery seems to grow with the number of activities [2][1] and the log preparation as described in the paper gives by far the largest set of activities. 944 in the original and 996 in my two different preparations as described above. However, using a very similar machine (Intel i7 CPU @ 2.8 GHz with 16 GB of memory) I have not reached anything close to two minutes.

To cope with the performance problem, the *Filter events based on attribute values* plugin was used to filter out events with a utility less than ten. This limited the number of activities to 22 and made the LPM discovery feasible. Through filtering out so many activities, the diversity of the possible results has been highly reduced. However, the data is still useful to assess the given question from the paper: "Which process fragments are related to high numbers of e-mails and phone calls to the IT service desk?" Figure 3.2 shows two selected examples with relatively high utility.

Again, the structure of the found LPM petri nets differs from the ones in the paper and I was also not able to generate a view that includes the frequencies of the activities in the LPMs. Despite the fact that the lion's share of the log was filtered out, the replicated LPMs have been selected by the desired utility values making the replication at least a partial success.

⁴<https://svn.win.tue.nl/trac/prom/browser/Packages/LocalProcessModelDiscovery/Trunk/src/org/processmining/lpm.../utility/casestudies>

Figure 3.2: Incidents LPMs with High Utility

Figure 3.3: LPMs found in the Smart Home data

3.3 Smart Home

The data set for the smart home case study of the paper could not be found. To substitute for the log that was subject to the demonstration of constraints to local process models on ADL data, we chose a comparable dataset from the TU/e repository: Activities of daily living of several individuals⁵. This data set also included several different households where cases represent days and an event is a particular activity of daily life. With 43 cases and 4200 events and 38 activities the *hh104_labour* part of the data set is comparable to the households data used in the paper. Therefore, the LPM constraints have been used with this data.

Again, a ProM plug-in written by the paper’s author has been used to replicate the findings. The log has been analyzed by the *Search for Local Process Models* plugin twice, once based on confidence and support as introduced in [2] and once with an additional constraint of maximum two minutes between consecutive events. Even though the data set contained a lot more activities, the results have been split into two groups of LPMs: one with the activity *Start:*, which is seemingly always recorded just before the first activity of the day, *sleep:* and *toilet:*. The other group consist of the *mealpreparation:* and *eatingdrinking:* activities. Figure 3.3 shows two exemplary LPMs of the two runs.

Generally, the frequencies in the LPMs dropped by adding the constraints. However, in the first group the *Start:* activity has been removed from all LPMs, whereas no activity from the second group was removed. Besides the constraint, the default parameters of the plugin have been used for both runs. Other configurations, e.g. by decreasing the *Minimum number of occurrences in log* parameter did

⁵<https://doi.org/10.4121/uuid:01eaba9f-d3ed-4e04-9945-b8b302764176>

not lead to many more different LPMs. Compared to the paper, the replication results differ not as much. This might be related to the structure of the data, because the papers dataset contained more "raw" data, i.e. the collected activities are more like sensor generated data whereas the dataset used for substitution seems to contain activities that have been derived from one or more sensor events. I assume that the constraint is more useful in a log with "raw" sensor data to help identifying temporal relationships of "sub-activities" of activities like "prepare food". However, also this third case study has successfully been replicated, because the added constraint limited the LPMs as desired.

4 Conclusion

All in all the replication could be called a success. Even though I could not reproduce the same results of the paper and visualizations, the trace- and event-level utility functions and the time-based constraint worked as expected. The replication turned out to be relatively hard, because for the data preparation and the use of the respective "experimental" ProM plugins required a lot of assumptions and research. I don't think that it is common to use the tools that have been used for the initial findings of the paper also for the replication, but without the inspection and use of their code, probably only the constraint part would have been successfully replicated.

What did I learn? The experiment descriptions in the paper are more than vague and partially seem to be even inaccurate, e.g. the description of the incidents log. This probably does not solely apply to this paper. Furthermore, the use of experimental tools can be highly confusing, especially if details like the required parameter for a plugin to run "headless" remains unknown. There are still some remaining question marks on different components of this replication. It would probably require a lot more time spent on the involved techniques and tools to fully comprehend the context and be fully certain on the replication outcomes. However, this replication motivated me to get a first experience in how to manipulate existing or create new plugins for ProM.

A Road Traffic Fines

A.1 Data Preparation Prom Plugin

According to the described calculations in the paper, line 28 of the code snippet¹ below should read "latestAmount += value;" to be correct.

```
1 @Plugin(name = "Preprocess Road Fine with remaining_amount", parameterLabels = { "
  Event Log" }, returnLabels = { "Event Log" }, returnTypes = { XLog.class },
  categories = {
2   PluginCategory.Enhancement }, keywords = "", help = "", userAccessible = true ,
  handlesCancel = false)
3 public class PreprocessRoadFine {
4   public static final String attrName = "Costs";
5
6
7   @UITopiaVariant(affiliation = UITopiaVariant.EHV, author = "Niek Tax", email = "n
    .tax@tue.nl")
8   @PluginVariant(variantLabel = "Preprocess Road Fine with remaining_amount",
    requiredParameterLabels = { 0 })
9   public XLog run(PluginContext context, XLog log) {
10    XLog logClone = (XLog) log.clone();
11    for(XTrace trace : logClone){
12      double latestAmount = 0;
13      double latestExpense = 0;
14      double amountPaid = 0;
15      for(XEvent event : trace){
16        XAttributeMap xam = event.getAttributes();
17        String conceptName = xam.get("concept:name").toString();
18        if(conceptName.equals("Create Fine")){
19          Double value = ((XAttributeContinuous) xam.get("amount")).getValue();
20          latestAmount = value;
21        }
22        if(conceptName.equals("Send Fine")){
23          Double value = ((XAttributeContinuous) xam.get("expense")).getValue();
24          latestExpense = value;
25        }
26        if(conceptName.equals("Add penalty")){
27          Double value = ((XAttributeContinuous) xam.get("amount")).getValue();
28          latestAmount = value;
29        }
30        if(conceptName.equals("Payment")){
31          Double value = ((XAttributeContinuous) xam.get("paymentAmount")).getValue
32          ();
33          amountPaid += value;
34        }
35        xam.put(attrName, new XAttributeContinuousImpl(attrName, latestAmount+
36          latestExpense - amountPaid));
37      }
38    }
39    return logClone;
40  }
```

¹<https://svn.win.tue.nl/trac/prom/browser/Packages/LocalProcessModelDiscovery/Trunk/src/org/processmining/lpm.../utility/casestudies/PreprocessRoadFine.java>

A.2 Prepared Log Structure

Figure A.1: Structure of the Prepared Road Fines Log

B IT Service Desk Incidents

B.1 Data Preparation Python Script

The script below shows the first, intuitive attempt the shape the data as needed for the technique/ProM implementation. Note that the code also contains variables/lines of code used for better data understanding that did not contribute to the data preparation as such.

```
1 import pandas as pd
2 import numpy as np
3
4 incident = pd.read_csv('Detail_Incident.csv', keep_default_na=False, na_values=[
    'empty'], delimiter=';')
5 incidentActivity = pd.read_csv('Detail_Incident_Activity.csv', keep_default_na=True,
    delimiter=';')
6 interaction = pd.read_csv('Detail_Interaction.csv', keep_default_na=True, delimiter
    =';')
7 change = pd.read_csv('Detail_Change.csv', keep_default_na=True, delimiter=';')
8
9 incident = incident.iloc[:, :-50] #remove empty columns
10
11 incident['Costs'] = incident['# Related Interactions']
12 incident.to_csv('incidentsNoEmptyCols.csv', index=False)
13
14 #change some column names to work with
15 incident.rename(columns={'Service Component WBS (aff)': 'ServiceComponentWBS',
    'Closure Code': 'ClosureCode', 'ServiceComp WBS (CBy)': 'CausedBy', '# Related
    Interactions': 'Interactions', 'Close Time': 'CloseTime'}, inplace=True)
16
17 numberwbs = incident.ServiceComponentWBS.unique().tolist() #how many different WBS
    components exist?
18
19 #remove rows without case ID
20 incident['ServiceComponentWBS'].replace('', np.nan, inplace=True) #set empty
    strings to "nan"
21 numberWBSempty = incident.isna().sum() #check number of nan values in
    ServiceComponentWBS
22 incident.dropna(inplace=True) #drop all rows with "nan" in 'ServiceComponentWBS'
    column
23
24 header = list(incident) #get a header list for better overview
25 cases = incident.ServiceComponentWBS.unique().tolist() # create a list of all cases
    in the dataset
26
27 incident.sort_values(['ServiceComponentWBS', 'CloseTime'], inplace=True) #get the
    event log sorted by case and timestamp
28 incident.reset_index(inplace=True)
29
30 incident['Interactions'].replace('', np.nan, inplace=True) #set empty strings to "
    nan"
31 incident['Interactions'].fillna('0', inplace=True) #set empty strings to "nan"
32
33 incidentReduced = incident[['ServiceComponentWBS', 'ClosureCode', 'CausedBy',
    'CloseTime', 'Interactions']] #only keep the columns needed
34
35 incidentReduced['Activity'] = incidentReduced.iloc[:, 1] + "|" + incidentReduced.
    iloc[:, 2] # concatenate to "ClosureCode | CausedBy" activity
36
37 closureCodes = incidentReduced.ClosureCode.unique().tolist() # list of all
    activities
38 causes = incidentReduced.CausedBy.unique().tolist() # list of all causes (WBS)
39
```

```

40 filteredDF = incidentReduced[~incidentReduced.Activity.str.contains("Unknown|Other
    |#N/B")] #remove "useless" information
41
42 activities = filteredDF.Activity.unique().tolist() # create a list of all
    activities in the dataset
43
44 sampleFile = 'prepIncidents.csv'
45 filteredDF.to_csv(sampleFile, index=False)

```

B.2 Data Preparation ProM Plugin

```

1 @Plugin(
2     name = "Preprocess BPI'14 Incidents Log v3 replication",
3     parameterLabels = {"BPI'14 Incidents Log"},
4     returnLabels = {"Preprocessed BPI'14 Incidents Log"},
5     returnTypes = { XLog.class }
6 )
7 public class PreprocessBPI14IncidentsLog3_rep{
8     public final String utilityName = "# Related Interactions";
9
10    @UITopiaVariant(affiliation = UITopiaVariant.EHV, author = "N. Tax", email = "n.
    tax@tue.nl")
11    @PluginVariant(variantLabel = "Preprocess BPI'14 Incidents Log v3",
    requiredParameterLabels = {0})
12    public XLog parse(PluginContext context, XLog log){
13        Map<String, XTrace> cases = new HashMap<String, XTrace>();
14        for(XTrace trace : log){
15            for(XEvent event : trace){
16                XEvent eventCopy = (XEvent) event.clone();
17                XAttributeMap xam = eventCopy.getAttributes();
18                if(xam.containsKey("concept:name")){
19                    String cname = xam.get("concept:name").toString();
20                    XTrace curTrace = null;
21                    if(cases.containsKey(cname)){
22                        curTrace = cases.get(cname);
23                    }else{
24
25                        XAttributeMap traceXam = new XAttributeMapImpl();
26                        traceXam.put("concept:name", new XAttributeLiteralImpl("concept:name",
    cname));
27                        curTrace = new XTraceImpl(traceXam);
28                    }
29                    if(xam.containsKey(utilityName))
30                        xam.put("Costs", new XAttributeContinuousImpl("Costs", ((
    XAttributeDiscrete) xam.get(utilityName)).getValue()));
31                    else
32                        xam.put("Costs", new XAttributeContinuousImpl("Costs", 0));
33                    String name = "";
34                    if(xam.containsKey("Closure Code"))
35                        name = name + xam.get("Closure Code").toString();
36                    if(xam.containsKey("ServiceComp WBS (CBy)"))
37                        name = name.equals("") ? name + xam.get("ServiceComp WBS (CBy)").
    toString() : name + " | " + xam.get("ServiceComp WBS (CBy)").toString();
38
39                    if(!name.contains("#N/B") && !name.contains("Unknown") && !name.contains(
    "Other")){
40                        xam.put("concept:name", new XAttributeLiteralImpl("concept:name", name)
    );
41                        curTrace.add(eventCopy);
42                        cases.put(cname, curTrace);
43                    }

```

```

44     }
45   }
46 }
47 XAttributeMap newLogXam = new XAttributeMapImpl();
48 newLogXam.put("concept:name", new XAttributeLiteralImpl("concept:name", "
Transformed BPI'14 Incidents log"));
49 XLog newLog = new XLogImpl(newLogXam);
50 for(XTrace trace : cases.values())
51   newLog.add(trace);
52 return newLog;
53 }
54 }

```

B.3 Prepared Log Structure

The figures show the log with "Service Component WBS (aff)" column as case and the concatenated "Closure Code | ServiceComp WBS (CBy)" as activity identifier and a "Costs" attribute per event.

Figure B.1: Structure of the Prepared Incidents Log

Figure B.2: Key Data of the Prepared Incidents Log

B.4 Prepared Log Structure Filtered

The log after filtering.

Figure B.3: Structure of the Prepared Incidents Log Filtered

Figure B.4: Key Data of the Prepared Incidents Log Filtered

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EINDHOVEN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

2IMI00

SEMINAR ARCHITECTURE OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS

Replication report

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January 27, 2019

I have chosen to (*try*) replicate the paper that I have also presented during the seminar, namely ‘Discovering and Exploring State-Based Models for Multi-perspective Processes’ by Maikel L. van Eck, Natalia Sidorova, and Wil M.P. van der Aalst [1].

This paper is about the following as the authors themselves say in their abstract: “In this work we aim to discover models for processes where different facets, or perspectives, of the process can be identified. Instead of focussing on the events or activities that are executed in the context of a particular process, we concentrate on the states of the different perspectives and discover how they are related.”

Datasets

The authors implemented their approach into ProM in the package named CSM-Miner, available for ProM 6.6 or higher. This tool is evaluated on the BPI 2012 Challenge, which consist of data of a loan application process. The authors also evaluated it with product user behavior data gathered by Philips during the development of a smart baby bottle equipped with various sensors.

The BPI 2012 Challenge [2] was very easy to obtain from the 4TU Data Center. The Philips data however was not obtainable, there were no references in the paper to this data set and the authors say that they got the data set from Philips. Therefore, I will only replicate the evaluation of the BPI 2012 Challenge.

Evaluation

First they pre-process the log by adding artificial initial and final states to each process instance in the log to ensure correct calculations of state sojourn times. Luckily they made this pre-processed log available in a Subversion (SVN)¹.

Now I will run the CSMMiner on the pre-processed log. So first we import the log, this already has multiple options but nothing specific is said about the importing in the paper so I leave it on the default, which is ProM log files (XES-Lite - MapDB(no cache)).

Running the CSMMiner gives the same three perspectives as in the paper.

The authors state that the overall model is still difficult to interpret, but the individual models of the three perspectives are readable and simple. I do agree with them, the models of the three perspectives are easy to comprehend.

Another reason the authors give that these models are a lot clearer is that the models can be simplified with the transformation operations discussed in the paper, i.e. remove a transition, abstract from a state and aggregate states.

¹<https://svn.win.tue.nl/repos/prom/Packages/CSMMiner/Logs/>

The first simplification they make in the evaluation is abstracting from the state `a_submitted`. This is because all applications are immediately put into state `a_partlysubmitted`, the time spent in this first state is thus 0. In the CSMMiner tool I could easily use the remove state option of the Transform function to make the state colored in red. As is also shown in the figure in the paper. But when pressing on Transform the model, I got a message saying:

After this message ProM is still showing the turning gearwheel, meaning that it is in process but after half an hour it still kept going so I terminated ProM. Possible something with the log pre-processing and trace 173688 is wrong.

The next simplification is an aggregation of the states `a_registered`, `a_approved` and `a_activated`. Because these states are in practice all done synchronous at almost the same time and the process ends after they are completed. Again with the Transform function, I could easily aggregate these three states after selecting them all. This also gave me the result of an aggregated state.

The authors now start to explore the discovered CSM. They inspect the difference in confidence and lift for the state `a_declined` with the co-occurrence of automatic application submission and manual handling. I tried to select the state `w_afhandelen.leads.start`. However did that give me a very different confidence and lift, see the picture below:

I also tried to select other states to see if that changed anything, but to no avail. I could not figure out how to make the the differentiation between manual and automatic handling.

They also check the *a_declined* while fraud is being detected, so I selected the state *w_beoordelen fraude_start* and this gave me the following:

I observe very different numbers then in the paper and a very high lift which means that being in state *a_declined* is a lot higher then expected.

Lastly the authors look at the co-occurrence of declining applications after validation with the state where a client is called because of an incomplete application. Again I get very different confidence and lift but the number of cases on the edges is the same.

Also the co-occurrence of declining applications during application validation, giving me the following results after selecting state *w_valideren aanvraag_start*.

The lift and confidence are still very different from the result in the paper.

Conclusion

Replicating this report started off very smoothly, the tool is openly available in ProM. One of the datasets is very easy obtainable as it was a BPI Challenge dataset. The authors pre-processed the log but luckily made the pre-processed log available on a Subversion.

Then the simplification started, the options were clear and very easy to perform with the tool. Unfortunately for one simplification I got a (error) message and the simplification did not terminate.

Lastly the authors checked the co-occurrence of states measured by the confidence and lift metrics. Here again I deviated from the results given by the paper. Strangely most of my results had 0 or close to 0 as confidence, this in turn made the lift go up by a lot. I am unsure why my confidence gives such bad results as I am using the log provided by the authors and I am running the same tool on the log.

References

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2IMI00 Seminar: Paper Replication Report

Marie Heinrich

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the most important factors when assessing scientific research is the reproducibility of the study. In the remainder of this report I will conduct and discuss such a reproduction in terms of feasibility and differences in results on the example of the paper *Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Processes Performance from Event Data* of V. Denisov, D.Fahland and W.v.d.Aalst (2018).

The report is organized as follows: In section 2 a brief overview of the paper's problem statement, the proposed model and evaluation approach is provided. Section 3 discusses the reproduction steps and evaluates the challenges and differences in results compared to the original paper. In section 4 a final conclusion is drawn.

2 REFERENCE PAPER OVERVIEW

2.1 Problem Statement

Performance is a central aspect of process management and is often investigated with process mining techniques based on the process data. However, current techniques aggregate the event data over time and thus introduce representational bias which for example may omit important process information of or between individual steps. As a solution, the paper proposes the *performance spectrum* (refer to figure 1 (right)) as a new descriptive analytics model which visualizes all observed flows between two process steps regarding their performance over time without prior aggregation. The core idea of the model is to provide a comprehensive description of all performance steps over time in order to *visually* analyze occurring process performance patterns. With these patterns time-related observations like changing process performance or dependencies on other cases can be detected. In addition to the model, a taxonomy for these elementary and composite performance patterns is provided.

2.2 Performance Spectrum

The performance Spectrum visualizes performance steps over time where event data is described in horizontal process segments, i.e. pairs of related process steps like for example handover of work from a to b. For all occurrences per segment, performance is calculated and visualized over time. The tool allows interactive exploration and additional classifications, filters and aggregations (e.g. in form of bar charts for fixed time periods) can be added.

2.3 Evaluation Approach

2.3.1 Data

The paper evaluates the tool based on 12 real-life event-logs of business processes which are briefly explained hereinafter:

1. **BPI12:** This dataset contains logs of a loan application process.
2. **BPI14:** The dataset contains log files of the ITIL Service Management tool of Rabobank ICT and is intended to serve as a base for predictions of the Service Desk and/or IT operations after future changes.

Figure 1: Performance analysis based on a graph-based model (left) and the performance spectrum (right)

3. **BPI15 (x5):** This dataset contains building permit applications of approx. four years from five Dutch municipalities. The individual municipalities follow the same process, however, slight deviations in activities occur.
4. **BPI17:** This dataset contains log data of a loan application process of a Dutch financial institute. In particular, it comprises all online applications in the system of 2016 until February 2017.
5. **Hospital Billing:** This dataset contains billing information of medical services provided by a hospital that were logged in the respective ERP system.
6. **Road Fine Management:** This dataset contains log data from an information system managing road traffic fines.
7. **Vanderlande logistics:** This data set logs the flow of bags through a Vanderlande built baggage handling system (BHS) where each case corresponds to one bag.

2.3.2 Method and Evaluation Setup

The evaluation was conducted by testing the tool on the 12 different use cases presented above. For two use cases (i.e. the road traffic fine management process (RF) and the Vanderlande logistics process (BHS)) the obtained result is described and analyzed in-depth. Hereby, the authors did the following steps:

- Pre-processing the raw log data into a suitable format for the performance spectrum
- Sub-setting or filtering a sequence of interest
- Analyzing the observed patterns according to the provided taxonomy

For all other use cases, results are summarized in a table, highlighting the most important patterns found. The obtained results are discussed side-by-side with the replication results in the next section.

Figure 2: Model extracted by Disco from full data set

Figure 3: Model after filtering out variances with 82% of cases remaining

3 REPLICATION OF THE REFERENCE PAPER

3.1 Replication approach

This section discusses the replication of the paper introduced in the previous section. I will first access if the tool (the performance spectrum) and the data is available. In a second step I follow the evaluation steps for the two extensively discussed use cases and discuss differences in my results compared to the original ones. Lastly, I investigate if I can confirm the patterns described in the result table for the remaining data sets.

3.2 Step 1: Data and tool accessibility

Tool Accessibility

The first step of reproducing the paper is gathering the required data and tools. In the case of this paper, the tool source code and the application are published in the GitHub repository *processmining-in-logistics/psm* of the authors (<https://github.com/processmining-in-logistics/psm>). The README provides an extensive installation instruction for the tool. I decided to install a stand-alone version of the tool which can be executed from the command line with the `java -jar perf-spec-assembly-1.0.4.jar` command. According to the instruction the tool was not yet tested on a linux-based system. However, the program seems to run without complications on my system installation: MacBook Pro 2015 running on macOS Mojave 10.14.2; 2.7 GHz Intel Core i5 processor, 8GB RAM, Retina Display (2560x1600 pxl).

Figure 4: Applied filter for end events

Figure 5: Applied filter for considered events in the model

Data Accessibility

The data set belonging to the Vanderlande logistics process is not public. Therefore it is not possible to replicate the results for this specific data set. All other data sets can be accessed via the following link: https://data.4tu.nl/repository/collection:event_logs_real. However, the data files of BPI15 were corrupted and couldn't be opened or re-formatted.

3.3 Step 2: Evaluation of the Road Traffic Fine Management Process (RF)

Apart from the unavailable Vanderlande logistic process, the RF data set was as well analyzed in detail in the paper.

3.3.1 Step 2.1: Subsetting the data

The authors decided to analyze only 3 trace variants, namely R1: Create Fine, Payment, R2: Create Fine, Send Fine, Insert Fine Notif., Payment, and R3: Create Fine, Send Fine, Insert Fine Notif., Add penalty, Send for CC which cover 80% of the events in the logs. For the replication I loaded the data set into Disco (figure 7), a process mining tool, and

We can observe that the filtered model contains the selected trace variants except parts of R2; there is no path between *Insert Fine Notification* and *Payment*. Since in Disco it was not possible to filter for multiple paths, but only for more or less often occurring variances of paths, I tried to model the subset with another process mining technique in PROM: the heuristic miner. Figures 4 and 5 show the applied filters which result in keeping 88% of the events. The obtained model is shown in figure 6 and now includes all trace variants R1-R3.

3.3.2 Step 2.2: Loading the dataset and defining the views

In a next step I loaded the filtered log obtained from the heuristic miner into the performance spectrum (PSM) and specified quartile-based performance classes like in the paper. To obtain the same sequence of segments in the view as in the paper I created a `sorting_order.txt` file in the temporary folder of the PSM with the segment filters (one per row) as depicted in figure 2.

Figure 6: Heuristic Miner Model after filtering with 88% of cases remaining

Figure 7: Original PSM result for trace variants R1-R3

Figure 8 shows the obtained replication results for traces R1-R3 whereas figure 2 depicts the results from the paper. P1 to P5 in figure 2 show the observed patterns that are evaluated in detail in the paper. If those areas are compared with the replication results we can quickly see that the obtained pattern structures are the same for all segments. However, the major difference between the results is color in the *Insert Fine Notification- Add penalty* segment. The color describes the performance quantiles. PSM allows for filtering of specific performance quantiles, but I could not replicate the exact same colors for this segment.

Apart from the individual event view, an aggregated view can be specified, which is visualized as bar charts in the PSM. The result from the paper is depicted in figure 9 and the replicated result in figure 10.

When comparing the results we can clearly see the concept drift as well as the periods with less work than usual (highlighted with the black "gap" boxes in figure 9). However, in the replicated version we can still see that some work had been done in these areas whereas in the original it seems like no work has been done. Furthermore, some segments show very similar pattern like for example the *Create Fine:Payment* segment. Other segments in contrast show very different pattern. The *Add penalty: Send for Credit Collection* pattern look identical in the individual trace visualization but strongly differ in the aggregated view. Here we can see clear yearly patterns which are not apparent in the original. However, please note that at this point it also is difficult to compare these visualizations since in the original paper neither a timeline is shown nor is a specific binning option mentioned. Assuming that the graph in figure 9 (b) has the same scale as the segments in (a), the replication nevertheless should show approximately the same time window.

Figure 8: Replicated PSM result for trace variants R1-R3

Figure 9: Original aggregated performance spectrum for the RF log

3.4 Step 3: Investigation of patterns in remaining use cases

For all other use cases, the paper only provides a table (figure 11) summarizing the observed patterns. No sub-sampling or pre-processing information are provided. Therefore, I will investigate, if I can confirm the pattern by loading the datasets into the PSM and choosing own subsets if necessary.

3.4.1 BPI12 use case

This log data revealed a large process model when loading it into Disco. Therefore, I filtered again for the most common traces, leaving only 80 % of the events left. The traces to analyze with the PSM are depicted in figure 12. The resulting performance spectrum is shown in figure 15.

We can clearly observe the regular sparse work patterns in e.g. the second segment as well as global weekly FIFO (First in First out) patterns in the last segment. Thus, the observed pattern in the paper can be confirmed.

3.4.2 BPI14 use case

First, the event log data had to be transformed from csv into xes with Disco. Overall, the traces in the log data are very scattered. Filtering for only cases whose sequence of activities is shared by at least 2 cases already results in keeping only 55% of the cases and 29% of the events. Since this might remove the cases that show the observed patterns from the results table, I do not filter the data and search for the patterns in the total data set. This allows observing elementary but not combined patterns. However, it is quite difficult to explore all patterns in a high-level overview since due to the sheer information volume. Therefore, I will only discuss selected segments in the remainder of the report.

In figure 16 we can observe clear weekly (weekday) FIFO patterns (blue lines) with some arbitrary batching at end (orange lines). In figure 17 we can see that the workload intensity for activities following the *open* activity indeed have unordered differences from low to high and some sparsity seems to be apparent. However, this might also be due to the low amount of samples binned (e.g. the

Figure 10: Replicated aggregated performance spectrum for the RF log

	BP112	BP114	BP115-1	BP115-2	BP115-3	BP115-4	BP115-5	BP117	Hospital	H-Billing	Road Fine
unord_low		glob	glob	glob	glob	glob	glob	glob	glob	glob	glob
unord_high								glob	glob	glob	glob
FIFO								glob	glob	glob	glob
FIFO-unord								glob	reg	glob	glob
FIFO (weekly)		glob	glob		arb			glob	reg	glob	glob
batching		arb						per	per	reg	
workload spikes								arb			
concept drift		once	once	once	arb	arb	arb	glob	once	reg	reg
sparse work		reg	reg	glob*	glob*	glob*	glob*	glob	glob	glob	glob

Figure 11: Presence of selected pattern classes in analyzed use cases

open:Urgency Change trace only comprises 2 cases) and to the chosen bin size, which is 10 days in this case. When binning into smaller buckets (e.g. 1d) the tool repeatedly crashed after approx. 15min of data processing so the occurrence of sparsity is difficult to determine.

3.4.3 BP117 use case

This data set is very large (508MB) compared to the other ones (40-200MB). Loading the whole data resulted in out of memory errors (see figure 18). Therefore, I removed all variants whose activity sequences were shared by less than 387 cases, resulting in a subset containing only 50% of the cases as 41% of the events. Since there was no specific analysis question and my goal is to find specific elementary patterns, this might be sufficient. However, for detailed analysis the data should be sampled for paths of interest. The sequences included in the sampled data set are depicted in fig 19.

Figure 20 depicts yearly batching and figure 21 clear FIFO patterns. That they also occur in a weekly order becomes clearly visible if all quartiles (depicted in colors) are shown. On the example of the blue lines in figure 22 a 6-day work week can be observed. Workload spikes seem to exist for the segment *O.Created:O.Create Offer* depicted in figure 23 where at the beginning of July the workload suddenly spikes compared to the workload in the other months.

3.4.4 Hospital Log Data

The traces in this data set differ significantly with many unique paths, which makes it difficult to analyze. However, in figure 13 we can see clear FIFO pattern in quartile Q3 with some overlaying unordered variants in quartile Q1 (blue lines). Figure 14 shows the aggregated workflow pattern view for all segments starting from the *vervolgconsult poliklinisch* activity. We can see sparse workload patterns but this was expected considering the uniqueness of the different paths and thus the sparse repeated occurrence of events in more than one trace. It is therefore difficult to make valuable conclusions for the workload pattern.

3.4.5 Hospital Billing

Loading the log data in Disco without applying filters results in a spaghetti model. Therefore I again applied the variance filter to

Figure 12: Filtered process model of the BP112 log data

Figure 13: PSM result of the hospital log data

obtain the most common traces and explored the log data for the trace depicted in figure 24.

The obtained result of the PSM is depicted in figure 25. In R1 we can observe global FIFO pattern in quartile 2 (orange color).

Figure 26 depicts the global FIFO pattern overlaid with an unordered variant and figure 27 reveals periodical batching pattern on start.

In figure 28 different work patterns can be observed. In R1 for example work patterns are unordered with high (high bar) and low (low bar) workload periods. An example for sparse workload is shown in R2. Only the concept drift was not visually clear in the performance spectrum. However, as mentioned before, the log contains a tremendous amount of traces which is impossible to analyze in detail without further guidance from an expert. The pattern thus might be apparent in the full log but not in the subset.

3.5 Result Discussion

Since the application and data sets are published online, I am focusing on the evaluation of replication feasibility, result reproduction and the impact of paper limitations.

3.5.1 Feasibility

The application can easily be downloaded online and comes along with a well-documented installation and user manual. This makes it fairly easy to re-do the analysis of the paper. However, in the *Custom Sorting Order* section of the user manual it is said that a *sorting_order.ini* file should be added to the intermediate storage directory, which did not work in my case. This may be due to the linux-based system I was using. In my case adding a *sorting_order.txt* file solved the problem, which could be added to the manual for future reference. Overall, the application is well documented and easy to understand.

From a data point of view, not all results could be replicated since some data sets were due to compliance restrictions not available (Vanderlande logistics data) or had a corrupted format. Therefore, the replication results do not match the full evaluation scope of the

Figure 14: Aggregated PSM result of the hospital log data

Figure 15: PSM result of the BPI12 log data

paper. Nevertheless, the replication is still able to show that the application works as intended and detailed pattern can indeed be observed.

Thus, I would like to distinguish the functional or theoretical aspect of the PSM from the analysis aspect. With the available datasets I could clearly show that the elementary and combined pattern indeed can be visualized with the PSM. I further showed that filtering, ordering and view selection worked as expected. Pattern that could not be shown like the single occurrence of concept drift in the hospital billing data in contrast are a replication limitation from an analysis point of view. This limitation has its root cause in the lack of data knowledge combined with high data complexity, not in the inability of the tool to show it. Nevertheless, this issue is also related to some application limitations which will be discussed in section 3.5.3.

Another potential problem is related to the data file type. The PSM was not able to read csv file types which is one of the most common file types. Thus, I had to transform the dataset to an xes format first with the help of Disco. Users who do not have programs like Disco installed (which might be the case for the majority) might run into troubles parsing their data files before even starting the visualization. Maybe a link in the user manual to the open source Data Mining tool PROM could solve this.

3.5.2 Reproduction of paper results

In general, the obtained results were very similar to the results of the paper. The main issues during the replication were the insufficient description of data pre-processing and view selection as well as missing axis scales in the figures. With this it is possible to replicate the general pattern but not the exact same scaling or color coding, which is dependent on the chosen time-bins. Therefore I think that in terms of process performance conclusions one has to handle the tool with care. It is very powerful in revealing performance pattern that would have been hidden in other process mining models but also has the tendency to become very complex and confusing to analyze.

3.5.3 Impact of tool limitations

One of the main limitations highlighted in the paper is the large variety of composite patterns which currently cannot be described well by the taxonomy. This also made it difficult to replicate the results. Especially for the patterns that were summarized in the table, no further pre-processing or analysis question was given. When

Figure 16: PSM result of the BPI14 log data showing weekly FIFO and arbitrary batch at end patterns.

Figure 17: Aggregated PSM result of the BPI14 log data

searching for the described patterns in the dataset it was often difficult to determine if a pattern matched the described one or not. This comes along with the question how much noise I accept to still call it the same pattern. Take the batched FIFO pattern in figure 27 for example. Is a pattern still a batched pattern if some cases are not batched (blue vertical lines)? How much of this 'noise' is acceptable to still call this a batching pattern instead of a batch+unordered pattern as in the case of FIFO patterns? Here, the limitation of the taxonomy also impacts the replication.

Another limitation that impacted the replication was identifying the optimal views for a particular analysis question. Especially when the data sets become large and complex and specific analysis questions are not known it becomes difficult to detect meaningful combined patterns. Further, if I subsample the data into meaningful sub-sequences I may omit the traces that showed the described patterns in the original paper and thus makes replication difficult. This was especially the case for the BPI14 challenge. The majority of cases were independent and didn't have much activities in common. In such a case it is indispensable to have a clear analysis focus since otherwise only elementary patterns can be analyzed for e.g. the most common activity sequences (segments).

Another problem was that the rendering time increased tremendously for larger data sets like the BPI17 challenge or for smaller time intervals (e.g. 1d binning in the BPI14 challenge data). This makes it even more important to have clear analysis questions or traces to analyze in order to obtain meaningful results.

4 CONCLUSION

In general it was possible to replicate main results of the paper. The developed tool is available online and well documented. Most of the datasets are also public which made replication of most of the results feasible. However, to obtain exactly equivalent results, two things are required: (1) a detailed description of the data pre-processing and (2) a view selection for specific traces to analyze. Unfortunately, both wasn't given for all use cases. Therefore, it was possible to show that the application indeed works as intended and replicate the main conceptual ideas and patterns but not down to a maximum detailed level.

Figure 18: Resulting process model based on the sub-sampled data set

Figure 19: Resulting process model based on the sub-sampled data set

Figure 20: Aggregated PSM result of the BPI14 log data

Figure 21: Aggregated PSM result of the BPI14 log data

Figure 22: Aggregated PSM result of the BPI14 log data

Figure 23: Aggregated PSM result of the BPI14 log data

Figure 24: Filtered process model of the hospital billing log data

Figure 25: PSM result of the filtered hospital billing log data

Figure 26: Global FIFO+unord patterns

Figure 27: Periodical batching patterns on start

Figure 28: Aggregated work patterns

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Report of results replication for "Unbiased, fine-grained description of processes performance from event data"

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1 Introduction

There are a lot of techniques and solutions which are proposed for a nowadays world by an academic society. Some of these solutions can improve life of many people and tackle many hard problems. However, there is one key point which make people to believe in results of these projects – its replication. First, every solution needs to be verified by other people and only then it would have a chance to be implemented in the real world setting.

In this report the results of "Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Process Performance from Event Data" study by Vadim Denisov, Dirk Fahland and Will M. P. van der Aalst would be tried to be replicated. However, the task is not so easy it may seem from the beginning: for doing so, the paper needs to be read, the results should be analysed, some hypothesis about blank places in the experiment setting are needed to be made as well as verified, experiment need to be run and the results of experiments replication should be compared with the ones in the study.

Based on that steps, report would have the following structure: in the Chapter 2 corner stones of the research would be reported and some notes about the correct experiment setting would be addressed, in the chapter 3 installation of required packages would be described, in the chapter 4 results of open-access dataset analysis which was done in the study in detail would be compared with the replicated ones taking into account required log filtering, in chapters 5 and 6 results of BPI Challenge 2017 and 2012 log analysis would be compared with the results in the paper and in the chapter 7 I would conclude if results reproduction was successful or not.

2 Research description

The technique which is reported in the paper puts the process performance on the first place. Processes usually have patterns that they follow and usually these patterns can uncover interesting dependencies between resources or time perspectives. Elementary patterns (patterns which engage only one activity) are the blocks from which more complex patterns are built on. In the paper, these particular type of patterns was analysed. For capturing these patterns, the visual tool was proposed, as well as a taxonomy to interpret them.

Since taxonomy analysis could be quite tricky and difficult, the replication does not address it, but rather results interpretation based on the taxonomy. Therefore, in this work only results of a visual tool would be analysed.

3 Tools set up

Tools set up is one of the main part of the study. If it is impossible to get a source code or a working tool then further replication seems impossible. For this study, authors did a great job and documented all the main stop in the project github: <https://github.com/processmining-in-logistics/psm/blob/master/README.md>. It reports the steps that need to be taken in order to run the project successfully. For the replication, the PROM package was installed and run.

4 Road Traffic Fine Management Process

4.1 Data preparation

On this stage the same segments with the same frequency as in the paper was tried to be received from the log. Since research was carried out by professionals in the field, I assume that log was preliminary filtered so first Performance Spectrum run was tried on the filtered log where only traces with frequency ≥ 5 were kept to see how far it is from frequencies described in the paper. The results of frequencies received can be seen in Table 4.1. As can be seen, all segments have much higher frequencies compared to ones in the research description, especially a lot of variability is introduced by segment "Add Penalty:Send for Credit Collection" which differs 9 times in compared settings(1737 against 15214). It probably means that some additional filtering is required to minimize the difference in frequencies between settings. For that reason, it seems promising to check if traces were selected based on the starting date since only patterns from period between 2002 and 2003 were studied.

Table 4.1: Comparison of segments frequency in the paper and in the log where only infrequent traces were removed

Segment	Frequency	
	Research	Replication
Create Fine:Payment	833	1078
Create Fine:Send Fine	2407	6751
Send Fine:Insert Fine Notification	2668	4273
Insert Fine Notification:Add penalty	1992	4454
Add penalty:Payment	566	1759
Add penalty:Send for Credit Collection	1737	15214

To verify if the log was indeed filtered by the start date of trace, the log was put in disco and filtered by trace start date(period between 1st of January 2002 and 31 December 2003). It is possible to see in the Table 4.2 that frequencies indeed became closer to each other, for instance, frequency for "Add Penalty:Send for Credit Collection" segment started to be closer to the research setting(1737 in the research and 8087 in the current setting) and frequency for "Add Penalty:Payment" segment became almost identical in the research and in the setting (568 and 566 accordingly). However, there is a big gap in time when segment "Add Penalty:Payment" starts to be recorded in the log as can be seen on Figure 4.1 which is not true in the paper where there was no gap in the starting time of "Add Penalty" event which means that current setting is significantly different from the one described in the study.

Table 4.2: Comparison of segments frequency in the paper and in the log where each trace started between 2002 and 2003

Segment	Frequency	
	Research	Replication
Create Fine:Payment	833	722
Create Fine:Send Fine	2407	4874
Send Fine:Insert Fine Notification	2668	2383
Insert Fine Notification:Add penalty	1992	3127
Add penalty:Payment	566	568
Add penalty:Send for Credit Collection	1737	8087

Table 4.3: Comparison of segments frequency in the paper and in the log where frequent traces which completion time intersects the period from 2002 to 2003 were included

Segment	Frequency	
	Research	Replication
Create Fine:Payment	833	643
Create Fine:Send Fine	2407	5045
Send Fine:Insert Fine Notification	2668	3517
Insert Fine Notification:Add penalty	1992	4102
Add penalty:Payment	566	615
Add penalty:Send for Credit Collection	1737	15213

Figure 4.1: Delay of "Add Penalty" event

To remove the starting gap, in the third setting the traces which completion time intersects the period between start of 2002 and end of 2003 were selected. Additionally, since number of traces would increase as well comparing to the previous setting, the preliminary filtering based on frequency ≥ 5 was applied (the same filtering was applied in the setting 1). The resulting frequencies can be seen in Table 4.3. It is possible to see that frequency numbers in research and replication are still different, however, the patterns as can be seen on Figure 4.2 are the same.

Since segments patterns in the last setting and in the paper do not significantly vary, results of the research would be compared with the results from the log where traces were under completion between 2002 and 2003 and each trace included was observed at least 5 times in the whole log. First, comparison would be made for single traces patterns and later for traces aggregation.

Figure 4.2: Difference between patterns in the paper and patterns in the current setting

4.2 Results

In this section I would try to compare results of the replication with the ones in the paper.

First, "Create Fine:Payment" process segment was reviewed. Comparison between the paper and replication setting can be found on Figure 4.3. As it is presented on both images, traces have different speed and can overtake each other. So patterns look like almost identical. However, quartiles of traces are different (can be compared by color of traces) which probably means the big difference in the replication setting comparing to the paper one. The difference in quartiles was observed almost in every comparison and for that reason, it would not be discussed for the following segments.

Figure 4.3: Comparison of "Create fine:Payment" segment (paper results are up)

The next comparison includes "Create Fine:Send Fine" and "Send Fine:Insert Fine Notification" segments. Their comparison can be seen on Figure 4.4. Again, as in the previous case, there are identical patterns for the paper and replication setting: regular batches at end and start for "Send Fine" activity combined with FIFO constant operations for each of the segments.

Figure 4.4: Comparison of "Create Fine:Send Fine" and "Send Fine:Insert Fine Notification" segments

Following that, patterns for "Insert Fine Notification:Add Penalty" segment were compared, their visual comparison can be seen on Figure 4.5. Again patterns for the paper and replication setting match: there is a continuous FIFO constant execution pattern where traces have identical speed.

Figure 4.5: Comparison of "Insert Fine Notification:Add Penalty" segment

After that, segment "Add Penalty:Payment" was analysed. As in the previous comparisons, patterns for both settings match: there is a start batching and no batching at the end, so it can take a long time until payment would follow the penalty addition.

Figure 4.6: Comparison of "Add Penalty:Payment" segment

The last segment that would be compared for the log is "Payment:Send for Credit Collection" and results can be seen on Figure 4.7. Not surprisingly, as in the previous examples, results of comparison and patterns match. There is a continuous batching at the end with approximate frequency of 12 months.

Figure 4.7: Comparison of "Payment:Send for Credit Collection" segment

After results for individual traces were compared, the next step is to compare the aggregated patterns during all the log time frame as can be seen on Figure 4.8. On both settings it is possible to see the concept drift when occurrence of segments "Insert Fine Notification:Payment" and "Payment:Add penalty" is no longer detected in the log, as well, as there is a repeatable low load for "Create Fine:Payment" segment. However, the last observation from the paper, gap pattern, do not match for both settings. There is indeed, the gap for "Create Fine:Payment" segment which propagates to almost all following process segment, but there is no gap pattern for "Add penalty: Send for Credit Collection" segment as reported in the paper!

Figure 4.8: Aggregated performance spectrum comparison

5 BPI 2017

In order to additionally validate the findings, described in the paper, two more analysis were conducted and compared with the paper results. First, results for BPI challenge 2017 log were verified.

To perform the analysis, the log was filtered in the following way:

1. Only events with state "complete" were left in the log
2. Traces that finish by "A_Pending" or "O_Cancelled" were left in the log
3. Only events that are frequent enough were left (frequency is higher than 80 in Simple Heuristic PROM package)
4. Infrequent traces were removed by specifying minimum trace frequency to 5

After the steps described and after Disco was applied, the process model on Figure 5.1 was received (Activity threshold is set to 70% and Path threshold is set to 7%).

Figure 5.1: Process model for BPI 2017

Following that, the log was analysed with "Performance spectrum" package. In the rest of the section patterns found during replication and their comparison with ones reported in the paper would be presented. Figures of these patterns would contain the date information of the log when these particular patterns happened.

First, the "unord, high"(unordered execution of activities with high workload) pattern would be presented. It was detected for segment "A_Concept:A_Cancelled" as can be seen on Figure 5.2. During all the log time frame, this segment load remains high.

Figure 5.2: Segment which contains unordered execution of activities with high workload

The next patterns that would be described are FIFO and FIFO(weekly) patterns. These patterns can be easily distinguished at the first steps of the process as can be seen on Figure 5.3. Segments "A_Create Application:A_Concept" and "A_Create Application:A_Submitted" are executed fast and done in FIFO way. Additionally, there are gaps in segment "A_Create Application:A_Concept" which are periodically repeated. These gaps probably mean weekends when no job is done by company staff.

Figure 5.3: Segments which contain FIFO patterns

The following pattern is batching. It can be observed for segment "A_Concept:A_Accepted" as can be seen on Figure 5.4. This pattern means that applications are accepted by batch and usually it takes some time before it happens. The batching performed in everyday basis so can be counted as **global** instead of periodic. Additionally, as can be seen, this segment also contains weekly pattern as there is a gap in one day of the week.

Figure 5.4: Segment which contains batching pattern

The next pattern that would be reported is workload spikes. It is periodic for segment "O_Cancelled:A_Pending" as can be seen on Figure 5.5. Based on image, these pikes happen frequently and they are located in the middle of the month. They start to be especially high from the middle of July.

Figure 5.5: Segment which contains spikes

All in all, as for the previous log, almost all results which are mentioned in the study hold for this log as well, what makes the results reported in the paper even more reliable.(Table 5.1)

Table 5.1: Comparison of paper and replication results for BPI challenge 2017

Pattern	Paper	Replication
unord,high	glob	glob
FIFO	glob	glob
FIFO(weekly)	glob	glob
Batching	per	glob
Spikes	arb	arb

6 BPI 2012

After analysing BPI Challenge 2017, results for BPI challenge 2012 log were verified.

First, challenge log was filtered in the following way:

1. Only events with state "complete" were left in the log
2. Traces that finish by "A_DECLINED", "W_Afhandelen leads", "W_Completeren aanvraag", "W_Nabellen offertes" or "W_Valideren aanvraag" were left in the log
3. Only events that are frequent enough were left (frequency is higher than 80 in Simple Heuristic PROM package)
4. Infrequent traces were removed by specifying minimum trace frequency to 5

After the steps described were performed and Disco was applied, the process model on Figure 6.1 was received (activities threshold is set to 45.5%, path is 0).

Figure 6.1: Process model for BPI 2012

The process analysis was performed for the segments that are parts of the process described by the model and based on the log which was received following the steps specified above.

First, activities that were probably automatically performed by the system were analysed. Segment "A_Submitted:A_PARTLYSUBMITTED" contains some of these activities and follows the FIFO pattern as on Figure 6.2. It can be seen that this segment does not have gaps, traces inside it do not intersect and it is done globally on everyday basis. This pattern **is not reported** in the paper

Figure 6.2: FIFO pattern in BPI Challenge 2012

In order to find the FIFO(weekly) pattern which was reported in the paper, the segment which contains the transitions from automatic to manual processing should be analysed. For instance, segment "A_PREACCEPTED:A_ACCEPTED" is one of them. As can be seen on Figure 6.3, there are gaps at the end which are related to Saturday or Sunday so there is a weekly pattern. Additionally, these traces do not intersect with each other which means FIFO pattern.

Figure 6.3: FIFO(weekly) pattern in BPI Challenge 2012

Additionally, alike for the previous 2 experiments, one of the patterns described in the paper **can not be verified**. For this log it is a regular sparse work pattern. Results of comparison for BPI Challenge 2012 log are summed up in the table 6.1.

Table 6.1: Comparison of paper and replication results for BPI challenge 2012

Pattern	Paper	Replication
FIFO	not reported	glob
FIFO(weekly)	glob	glob
Sparce work	regular	not reported

7 Conclusions

In overall, the results of the paper can be reproduced and verified easily: installation process does not take a long time and described by authors in detail and visual tool results can be easily interpreted by using the taxonomy provided by authors.

In the end, the results which are reported in the study almost completely match with the ones that are got during reproduction process. The differences can be caused by different log filtering techniques since no exact filtering was reported by paper authors. In the future, in my opinion, authors should put more attention on specifying filtering techniques since otherwise it seems very difficult to verify their results for logs with higher complexity.

Experiment Replication Report

*Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Processes Performance
from Event Data*

E.L. Klijn

Eindhoven, February 2019

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1 Introduction

In the field of scientific research, reliability is the most important of measures when it comes to quality. In order to be considered reliable, the methods and theories proposed must be reproducible, meaning that they must hold repeatedly when conducted by different people and under inevitably different conditions. This report is aimed to perform such a replication. The research paper in question is *Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Process Performance from Event Data* [1], written by V. Denislov, D. Fahland and W.M.P. van der Aalst. Findings and methods presented in this paper will be used throughout this entire report, for which these will not recurrently be cited. Section 2 briefly describes the contents of the paper. In section 3, the replication approach is outlined and in section 4 the findings will be presented. Finally, in section 5 the most important findings are summarized, after which a conclusion is drawn.

2 Paper Contents

The paper in question touches upon the subject of process performance. It states that current process mining techniques are falling short in the sense that they aggregate event data. When time-related observations, as those in an event log are, are aggregated, this brings about the assumption that the process is of a stationary nature. When a process is stationary, this means that the underlying distribution functions of a case do not change over time and do not depend on other cases. This is also relevant when it come to performance of processes. Since event logs under analysis usually extend multiple years and contain over thousands of cases, it would be unsound to assume that the underlying distribution functions never change. Cases will probably have an influence on one another, and processes probably do change or get redesigned over the span of a couple of years.

For this reason, it is aimed to provide a comprehensive description of the process, without any prior aggregation. This is done by proposing a model called the performance spectrum, a visual tool that maps all observed flows between two processing steps. By providing a visualization of process "segments", which are paths between two successive processing steps, visual exploration of event data is enabled. This exploration generally uncovers many patterns, all attributable to specific process performance and behavior. Therefore, in addition, the paper proposes a taxonomy of elementary patterns, to enable the documenting and conceptualizing of these patterns.

After presenting the research problem, the relevant work is discussed first, after which the performance spectrum itself and the performance patterns are elaborated on in more detail, followed by the evaluation. The goal of the evaluation is to illustrate how the performance spectrum can help deduct performance characteristics from a process. This is done comprehensively for two event logs, namely the Road Traffic Fine Management (RF) log and the Baggage Handling System (BHS) log of Vanderlande. Subsequently, a summary of performance characteristics is given for 11 business process logs.

3 Replication Approach

The preparation necessary to replicate the evaluation reported in the paper, is to install the performance spectrum miner and obtain the data sets previously mentioned. After having the tool and data in place, a replication attempt can be made. Since the event data of the BHS could not be obtained, this evaluation step will be omitted in this replication. Regardless, first the approach for replicating the detailed evaluation of the RF log will be clearly defined, after which the approach for summarizing the different performance characteristics of 11 business process logs will be outlined.

3.1 Road Traffic Fine Management Process

The first evaluation step in the paper concerns the Road Traffic Fine Management log. The log is first described, after which a visualization is provided of a certain set of process segments. The composition of this set of process segments is based on the frequency of trace variants. The three most frequent trace variants are chosen, which should cover > 80% of the events in the log. These trace variants are $\langle \text{Create Fine, Payment} \rangle$, $\langle \text{Create Fine, Send Fine, Insert Fine Notif., Add Penalty, Payment} \rangle$ and $\langle \text{Create Fine, Send Fine, Insert Fine Notif., Add Penalty, Send for C.C.} \rangle$. First, detailed segments are visualized over a 2-year period, as illustrated in figure 3.1, after which five patterns are deducted and discussed. Subsequently, an aggregated spectrum of the corresponding segments is visualized, as illustrated in figure 3.2, showing concept drift and workload gaps.

Figure 3.1: Detailed performance spectrum evaluation of RF log (copied from [1])

Figure 3.2: Aggregated performance spectrum evaluation of RF log (copied from [1])

The approach is to first verify if these trace variants mentioned are indeed accountable for over 80% of events. This will be done by importing the event log into ProM and exploring the event log for trace variants. After verification, the log will be used as input for the Performance Spectrum Miner plugin, of which the settings will be kept at default. After, the correct time

frame will be selected and the corresponding process segments will be copied using the Windows snipping tool, to facilitate clear comparison (and reporting). For the evaluation of the detailed spectrum, it will be verified whether the five patterns illustrated in the paper can indeed be found. For the evaluation of the aggregated spectrum, it will be verified whether the segments show similar gaps and concept drift.

3.2 Comparison of Event Logs

The second replication step corresponds to the third evaluation step in the paper. This step concerns the comparison of 11 event logs regarding the performance characteristics they contain. According to the paper, the performance spectrum of each log was visualized and the properties of the immediately visible patterns were noted. These patterns were then summarized in a table, as shown in table 3.1, depicting which patterns occur in which logs and to what extent.

Table 3.1: Presence of selected pattern classes in real-life event logs (copied from [1])

	BPI12	BPI14	BPI15-1	BPI15-2	BPI15-3	BPI15-4	BPI15-5	BPI17	Hospital	H-billing	Road fine
unord,low		glob	glob	glob	glob	glob	gob		glob	glob	glob
unord,high								glob		glob	glob
FIFO								glob		glob	glob
FIFO+unord									reg	glob	
FIFO (weekly)	glob	glob			arb			glob			
batching		arb						per		per	reg
workload spikes								arb			reg
concept drift		once	once	once	arb	arb	arb			once	reg
sparse work	reg	reg	glob*	glob*	glob*	glob*	glob*		glob	glob	

The approach is to import all logs into ProM and run the Performance Spectrum Miner. Since the default bin size for the aggregated spectrum is based on a time window of 30 days, there will be a bit of exploring with this value to retrieve a useful visualization of the aggregated or combined spectrum. In order to produce a similar summary, all event logs will be checked for each of the patterns that were immediately visible according to the paper. This will be done pattern by pattern, aiding in a clear comparison of the presence of a pattern between logs.

4 Findings

This chapter presents the findings that follow from the replication approach discussed in the previous chapter. The findings will be presented in a similar order, first covering the detailed evaluation of the RF log, then covering the log comparison.

4.1 Road Traffic Fine Management Process

When importing the log into ProM and exploring the log, it can be seen that the log contains 150,370 cases and 561,470 events. When exploring the trace variants, it can be seen that the top three variants cover $> 80\%$ of cases in the log, as illustrated in figure 4.1. When calculating this for the number of events in the log, which is the unit of measure used in the paper, the top three variants cover $\sim 74\%$ of events in the log, whereas the top four cover $\sim 81\%$ of events in the log.

Figure 4.1: Top four traces in RF log

Moreover, the three most frequent traces mentioned in the paper correspond to the first, second and fourth of the most frequent traces found. Fortunately, the missing trace $\langle Create\ Fine, Send\ Fine \rangle$ is already a sub-trace of two of the other frequent traces, which will result in an identical set of process segments.

Now the set of process segments is verified, the Performance Spectrum Miner is run to retrieve the detailed performance spectrum of the RF log. Initially, the log was filtered to keep only the four most frequent trace variants, the result of which did not correspond to the original results. Subsequently, the log was filtered for the specified time span, also without success. In the end, the log was used without a filter, of which the output for the years 2002 and 2003 of the corresponding process segments is shown in figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Detailed performance spectrum of RF log for years 2002 and 2003

When comparing the replication result to the result from the paper (see figure 3.1), two small deviations can be found. The first is the mismatching of the quantities in the segment labels, which express the maximum amount of cases transitioning together through this part of the process. These amounts probably do not correspond because the log used for the original evaluation was filtered in some way after all. This may also explain the second deviation, which is located in the fourth segment *Insert Fine Notif.:Add Penalty*, where the orange and dark blue colors do not align. Since all cases within this segment are handled at equal speed and the slopes of the lines are identical, this is probably due to the fact that there is a different amount of cases flowing through. Apart from these small differences, it can be seen that the replicated segments are almost identical to those of the original evaluation. All five patterns highlighted in the paper can also be found in the resulting spectrum in figure 4.2, making this replication step a success.

To retrieve the aggregated performance spectrum, the same unfiltered event log was used as input. Therefore solely the view of the miner needed to be changed by removing the lines and revealing the bars. The result of this visualization is shown in figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Aggregated performance spectrum of RF log

When comparing results, one can see that there is a clear difference, most significantly between the height of the bins. When looking more closely however, it can be seen that the workload trend in the replication closely resembles the trend in the result of the paper. For all segments except one, the moments of growing workload, peaks and falling workload both in the replication and in the original correspond to one another. The segment that significantly deviates is *Add Penalty:Send for Credit Collection*, where the replication shows long intervals of growing workload followed by steep drops, whereas the original shows gradually alternating growing workload and falling workload. This deviation could also be a result of prior log filtering used in the paper, similar to the previous case.

Despite these differences, it is still possible to detect synchronized periods of zero-workload across all segments (except *Add Penalty:Send for Credit Collection*), clearly resembling the gaps in the result of the original evaluation. Furthermore, the bottom two segments also undoubtedly show concept drift during the same period as in the original. Even though results are not identical, it is possible to detect the same performance characteristics, making this part of the evaluation a reproducible one.

4.2 Comparison of Event Logs

This section will replicate the comparison of several patterns between 11 event logs. When recollecting the results of the original evaluation in figure 3.3, it can be seen that the table is partitioned in three parts, each concerning one of the viewing modes of the spectrum. This section will adhere the same order, therefore the first patterns that will be compared are patterns derivable from the combined spectrum, showing no order and varying workloads. Subsequently,

four variants of the FIFO pattern will be discussed, after which three patterns concerning the workload will be compared. Since a lot of figures were obtained during this part of the replication process, only the deviating results will be reported here, whereas the remainder will be included in the appendix.

4.2.1 Unordered low and high workload patterns

The first patterns to be compared are the unordered low and unordered high workload patterns, `unord.low` and `unord.high`, respectively. Since a workload is almost never completely constant and no clear example was provided for what exactly to look for, it was chosen to look for workloads that are predominantly high or low.

Starting with the BPI12 log, it could immediately be seen that there was no unordered pattern present. When viewing the BPI14 log, several segments could be pointed out where the `unord.low` pattern occurred globally, as shown in figure A.1. No `unord.high` pattern could be found. The BPI15-1 log also showed unordered behavior with a low workload, as illustrated in figure A.2. Furthermore, there were also some cases where the `unord.high` pattern occurred, but since these were not immediately visible, which was a condition for the original evaluation, these will not be taken into consideration here either. As for the other municipality logs of BPI15, the `unord.low` pattern occurred there in a similar way as in the log of the first municipality. However, the `unord.high` pattern was more clearly visible in the log of municipality 3, as illustrated in figure 4.4. This is the first observation that does not conform to the original and will additionally be recorded as arbitrarily present.

Figure 4.4: BPI15-3 log `unord.high` pattern

When analyzing the BPI17 log, it could clearly be seen that the `unord.high` pattern was globally present, as illustrated in figure A.3, whereas the `unord.low` pattern was absent. The hospital log showed the `unord.low` pattern, as illustrated in figure A.4, thereby conforming to the original evaluation result. Contrarily, it also showed the `unord.high` pattern, as shown in figure 4.5, which is the second observation that is not in agreement with the original evaluation. This observation will additionally be recorded as globally present. Similar to the hospital log, the hospital billing log and the RF log also showed `unord.low` and `unord.high` patterns, conforming to the results of the original, illustrated in figures A.5, A.6, A.7 and A.8, respectively.

Figure 4.5: Hospital log `unord.high` pattern

4.2.2 FIFO patterns

This section will compare four different types of FIFO patterns. First up is the normal FIFO pattern (FIFO), the second is FIFO overlaid with an unordered variant (FIFO+`unord`), the third is FIFO occurring only Mon-Sat (FIFO.weekly) and the last is FIFO in the form of batching (batching).

The BPI12 log shows almost exclusively the FIFO.weekly pattern, as illustrated in figure A.9. There are however a couple of segments that show normal FIFO behavior, illustrated in figure

4.6, not conforming to the original result. This observation will additionally be recorded as globally present.

Figure 4.6: BPI12 log FIFO pattern

When viewing the BPI14 log, it can be seen that the behavior in this log partly resembles the BPI12 log, also showing FIFO.weekly behavior, but with the addition of a **batching** pattern occurring arbitrarily. This also conforms to the original result and is illustrated in figures A.10 and A.11. The BPI15 logs all never show the FIFO, FIFO+unord or the **batching** patterns, whereas the FIFO.weekly pattern is arbitrarily present in the BPI15-3 log, as illustrated in figure A.12, conforming to the original findings. The FIFO.weekly pattern could also be detected in the logs of the other municipalities, but since this was insignificant compared to the BPI15-3 log and did not satisfy the condition that the pattern had to be immediately visible, these observations will not be taken into account. When viewing the BPI17 log, it can be seen that it completely conforms to the original findings, showing globally present FIFO and FIFO.weekly patterns, as well as periodic **batching** patterns, illustrated in figures A.13 - A.15. Also conforming to the original findings, the hospital log shows only the FIFO+unord pattern, as shown in figure A.16. The hospital billing log shows a periodic **batching** pattern, as well as global FIFO patterns and FIFO+unord patterns, illustrated in figures A.17 to A.19. Therefore this log also conforms to the original findings. Lastly, the road traffic fine log also shows a globally present FIFO pattern and a regularly present **batching** pattern, as can be seen in figure 4.2. No FIFO+unord or FIFO.weekly pattern was detected, which make these findings conform as well.

4.2.3 Aggregated patterns

This section will compare three kinds of aggregated patterns, namely workload spikes, concept drift and sparse work. The sparse work pattern is described quite clearly in the paper and will be identified by scattered workload. An example of concept drift was also provided in the paper and will be identified as a clear change in workload pattern over the course of time, possibly across multiple process segments. Workload spikes, however, were not that clearly described. The paper does provide a pattern definition for a workload peak, which is a high bar surrounded by lower bars. After scanning some of the logs, it became clear that almost all logs show these peaks, meaning this was probably not what was meant by a spike. However, Cambridge dictionary describes a spike as an abrupt sharp increase, usually before going down again. When scanning the logs again, this pattern could only be observed in the BPI17, illustrated in figure A.20, and Road Fine log, similar to the result in the paper. However, the Road Fine log only showed this pattern arbitrarily, illustrated in figure 4.7, while this pattern was originally periodically found, therefore this observation will be recorded with a slight adjustment to the original.

Figure 4.7: Road Traffic Fine Management log workload spikes

When checking the logs for concept drift, there were some deviating findings as well. Similar to the original results was the lack of concept drift in the BPI12 and BPI17 logs. Also conforming was the presence of concept drift in the BPI14, BPI15, Hospital Billing and Road Fine logs, illustrated in figures A.21 - A.23. However, according to the original results, the logs of the first two municipalities of the BPI15 set contain only a single occurrence of concept drift, whereas in this case, multiple moments in time a shift in performance pattern of distribution is observed. This happens in a similar way for both the first and the second municipality, illustrated in figure 4.8, concerning the second municipality. As can be seen, the most significant observation of concept drift is halfway into the time frame displayed in the figure. However, the fourth segment shows concept drift almost a year earlier on the time line where a steady medium workload arises for approximately half a year. Additionally, the second, fifth and last segment show concept drift a year later on the time line, where the workload grows from zero or a low amount to a medium amount. Finally, in the Hospital log an observation of concept drift was made, whereas in the original findings this was not the case. Therefore both of these observations will additionally be recorded, the first as arbitrarily present instead of only once and the second as present once.

Figure 4.8: BPI15-2 log concept drift [arb]

Figure 4.9: Hospital log concept drift [once]

The last pattern searched for is the sparse work pattern. As previously stated, this pattern will be identified by scattered workload, or discontinuous workload. Similar to the original findings, sparse work is observed in almost all event logs. The only logs in which sparse work was not observed were the BPI17 and Road Fine log, which was also the case in the original findings. In the paper, sparse work was found to be regularly present in the BPI12 and BPI14 logs and globally present in the Hospital and Hospital Billing logs. When comparing these spectrums, it was difficult to define what exactly made the difference between these two repetition variants. The sparse work pattern of the BPI12 log is illustrated in figure A.24, which also satisfies as an illustration for the BPI14 log, since the presence of sparse work was very similar between the two. The sparse work pattern of the Hospital and Hospital Billing log is illustrated in figures A.25 and A.26, respectively. All three examples show sparse work ranging the entire time frame of the segment, indicating a globally present pattern. When looking at all of the segments in each log, the sparse work pattern is proportionally less present in the BPI12, BPI14 and Hospital Billing log than in the Hospital log. Therefore the pattern is concluded to be globally present in the Hospital log and regularly present in the other three logs.

A special case is the BPI15 log set, where the sparse work pattern is said to be globally present in a synchronized manner. It was confirmed quite quickly that the pattern was indeed globally present in all of the municipality logs. However, it was difficult to detect a synchronization of sparse work across municipalities. To a small extent, this was found in the end, of which an illustration is shown in figures A.27 and A.28. One can see that there are some points in time where

workload occurs in and around the same days for several municipalities. However, this result is not very precise, since the comparison of different spectra is quite difficult because of the scaling of the time line. Moreover, the event log is so large that it is difficult to detect synchronization of certain patterns by hand, even more difficult when this has to be detected across multiple logs.

The results of the replicated comparison of event logs is summarized in table 4.1. The replication findings that deviate from the original are highlighted in bold blue.

Table 4.1: Presence of selected patterns in 11 business process logs

	BPI12	BPI14	BPI15-1	BPI15-2	BPI15-3	BPI15-4	BPI15-5	BPI17	Hospital	H-billing	Road fine
unord.low		glob	glob	glob	glob	glob	glob		glob	glob	glob
unord.high					arb			glob	glob	glob	glob
FIFO	glob							glob		glob	glob
FIFO+unord									reg	glob	
FIFO (weekly)	glob	glob						glob			
batching		arb						per		per	reg
workload spikes								arb			arb
concept drift		once	arb	arb	arb	arb	arb		once	once	reg
sparse work	reg	reg	glob*	glob*	glob*	glob*	glob*		glob	reg	

5 Conclusion

During the process of replicating an evaluation of a scientific research paper, a couple of issues have been discovered. Some of these are specific to this particular research and tool, while others are more general and probably concern the broader concept of evaluation in scientific research.

The first issue concerns the replication process itself and the steps that have to be followed in order to reproduce the results. For the detailed evaluation part, different results were found, which probably originated from certain filtering steps or other steps not touched upon in the paper. As for the comparison part of the evaluation, some of the patterns were not as clearly defined as they could have been, by the use of an example for instance.

The second issue is specific to this particular research and the fact that it is centered around visual analysis. Since the tool does not output any numbers, the analysis is done by the user and is therefore susceptible to the user's interpretation. While the paper provides a clear taxonomy for the elementary patterns, there are still a lot of borderline cases in which it is disputable which of the elementary patterns, part of a composite pattern, are the most present. While one person would argue that a workload during a specific time frame would be primarily high, another could argue for it to be primarily medium.

Another issue regarding the log comparison, also originating from the user's interpretation, is the statement that the patterns "immediately visible" were recorded. When I look at a performance spectrum, there is a good chance that the first patterns I notice are very different from the patterns another person notices. For some of the patterns that were included in the table, quite some time has been necessary for searching, as such, these were not experienced as immediately visible for me.

The last issue is attributed to the occurrence and repetition parameters of the patterns. The taxonomy presents a globally present pattern to be the only pattern present within a single segment, whereas a pattern that is locally present can have different degrees of repetition. There were quite some cases where, in my perception, patterns were globally present across a segment. Whereas in the original evaluation these patterns were said to be regularly or arbitrarily present. It seemed as though the occurrence of patterns was described for all segments in the log, whereas in the taxonomy presence is only described for a single segment. It was not clear how these repetition patterns for a segment were lifted in order to describe a collection of segments.

Although these issues made the reproducing of the original results difficult at some points, these were only small impediments. The main goal of the evaluation in the paper was to illustrate how the performance spectrum provides detailed insights into performance of the Road Fine log, and additionally illustrate how it can help to compare performance characteristics across business process logs. Even though the results were not exactly similar, it was still possible to illustrate all of the performance characteristics in the detailed evaluation and most of the characteristics in the log comparison. It can therefore be concluded that, despite the susceptibility of the tool to the user's interpretation, results were mostly reproducible, making this replication overall a success.

A Comparison Results

A.1 Unordered low and high workload patterns

Figure A.1: *BPI14 log unord.low pattern*

Figure A.2: *BPI15-1 log unord.low pattern*

Figure A.3: *BPI17 log unord.high pattern*

Figure A.4: *Hospital log unord.low pattern*

Figure A.5: *Hospital Billing log unord.low pattern*

Figure A.6: Hospital Billing log unord.high pattern

Figure A.7: Road Traffic Fine Management log unord.low pattern

Figure A.8: Road Traffic Fine Management log unord.high pattern

A.2 FIFO patterns

Figure A.9: BPI12 log FIFO.weekly pattern

Figure A.10: BPI14 log FIFO.weekly pattern

Figure A.11: BPI14 log batching pattern

Figure A.12: BPI15-3 log FIFO.weekly pattern

Figure A.13: BPI17 log FIFO pattern

Figure A.14: BPI17 log FIFO.weekly pattern

Figure A.15: BPI17 log batching pattern

Figure A.16: Hospital log FIFO+unord pattern

Figure A.17: Hospital Billing log FIFO pattern

Figure A.18: Hospital Billing log FIFO+unord pattern

Figure A.19: Hospital Billing log batching pattern

A.3 Aggregated patterns

Figure A.20: BPI17 log workload spikes

Figure A.21: BPI14 log concept drift [once]

Figure A.22: BPI15-3 log concept drift [arb]

Figure A.23: Hospital Billing log concept drift [once]

Figure A.24: BPI12 log sparse work

Figure A.25: Hospital log sparse work

Figure A.26: Hospital Billing log sparse work

Figure A.27: BPI15 Synchronized sparse work observation 1

Figure A.28: BPI15 Synchronized sparse work observation 2

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- [1] V. Denisov, D. Fahland, and W. V. D. Aalst, “Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Processes Performance from Event Data,” *Business Process Management*, vol. 11080, 2018.

EINDHOVEN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

SEMINAR ARCHITECTURE OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS

2IMI00

Replication of Research Paper

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1 Introduction

Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Processes Performance from Event Data paper [1] was selected to replicate. This paper, proposes an alternative investigation of process performance with the proposed **performance spectrum** model. The greatest contribution of this paper is; it allows to visualize performance of every process step. In this way, variety of new patterns of performance can be discovered. Authors of this paper aim to find an alternative approach to existing techniques that aggregate measures of performance over the entire data such as average or maximum waiting time between two activities. The problem with these techniques is that; they assume, distribution functions describing performance of the cases are stationary for the whole process (do not change over time) and also they do not depend on other cases. Hence this paper's objective is to discover comprehensive description of process behaviour without prior aggregation. That leads to ability of identifying the patterns and trends in the process without representational bias of an algorithm or process model.

Visualization of process spectrum allows to discover various patterns in performance. The performance spectrum separates the event data into *segments* (pairs of related process steps). The performance of each segment is visualized over time. The figure 1 shows performance of different segments of the process and from this image, various patterns can be discovered. To enable fine documentation and make the patterns understandable, this paper proposes a taxonomy for describing patterns in the performance spectrum.

Figure 1: Performance analysis with graph-based model (left) and performance spectrum (right)

The taxonomy of elementary patterns is shown in the image 2. Please refer to the paper [1] for further understanding of them. In the evaluation, patterns will be described using this taxonomy.

Figure 2: Taxonomy of elementary patterns

2 Motivation

The motivation behind choosing this paper is related to my master thesis project. I will work with Vanderlande industries with the topic of "Outlier Detection in Event Logs of Material Handling Systems". The main purpose of my master thesis topic is to see whether I can automatically identify any deviations within the performance spectrum. That is why, I wanted to learn more about performance spectrum. This paper explains motivations behind process spectrum and how it works. That will be valuable information for me. I will need to learn interpreting patterns because to be able to detect outliers first, I have to identify all states of normal behavior for each segment of the system. I have to learn taxonomy of patterns for this purpose and this paper presents and explains all of them.

Getting familiar with performance spectrum now will be very beneficial for me. Replicating this paper allows me to install the performance spectrum miner, learn parameter selection thoroughly and examine its code whenever I encounter any problems. Hence I have a great motivation in replicating this paper.

3 Evaluation

3.1 Data

Downloading the data was the first step of the evaluation. In the paper, they used 11 real-life event logs from business processes (BPI12, BPI14, BPI15(1-5), BPI17, Hospital Billing ,RF) and 1 real-life log from logistics from Vanderlande. I successfully downloaded every dataset except Vanderlande from provided website. ¹. Since Vanderlande's data is private I couldn't get access to it.

The paper was focused mainly on **Road Traffic Fine Management Process** dataset. That is why I started with it as well.

3.2 Performance Spectrum Miner Installation

In order to work with performance spectrum miner, I followed the instructions presented in provided source code ².

To install the miner, I followed these steps;

1. Checking system requirements: My computer has;
 - Operating system: Windows 10
 - RAM: 16 GB
 - Hard Disk Space: 35.2 GB free space
 - Screen Resolution: 1920x1080
2. Checking Java version : My computer has Java 8 installed.

All of the requirements for installation was met for my computer. Therefore I continued installation of the PSM as a ProM plugin.

¹<https://data.4tu.nl/repository/collection:eventlogsreal>

²<https://github.com/processmining-in-logistics/psm>

1. I downloaded ProM nightly build of 02.01.2019 version ³
2. I run ProM Package Manager by executing *PackageManager.bat*
3. From PackageManager, I went to tab 'Not installed', found and installed plugin **PerformanceSpectrum**.
4. I exited ProM Package Manager
5. Finally I executed *ProM.bat* to run the PSM.

With these steps, I successfully installed performance spectrum miner to my computer as ProM plugin.

3.3 Analyzing the Performance Spectrum of a process with the PSM

After downloading datasets and installing PSM, performance spectrum for *Road Traffic Fine Management Process* was created like following;

1. Dataset was imported in ProM.
2. From the action tab *Performance Spectrum Miner plugin* was selected.
3. Parameters were chosen. See the image 3.
 - Bin size: Time window size to calculate aggregated part. It is chosen as 30 days (1 month)
 - Aggregation function: *Cases pending* option is selected because we would like to know how many segments intersect a bin or start/ stop in a bin.
 - Duration classifier: It is selected as *Quartile-based* because this information was given in the paper.
 - Activity classifier: It overrides a default activity classifier in XES event log file. It was left as default.
 - Intermediate storage directory: This directory plays a very important role because the performance spectrum of an imported data is stored in this directory. The meta data file *session.psm* can be opened in ProM again with *Performance Spectrum Viewer* action.
4. Performance spectrum data was opened for analysis with PSM. See image 4
 - Activity aggregation (before/after): It was selected as *None* meaning no aggregation on segments of pre-processed performance spectrum
 - Caching: It was selected as *Load on open* meaning all data is loaded into memory.

³Nightly build of Wednesday, 02.01.2019, 03:15:17

5. Initially, each segment is displayed in the format of first_activity : second_activity. We only need to see most frequent segments that is why **minimal throughput** was selected as 100. Also to get the same segments as in the paper, I applied a filter with regular expression. (Image 5)
6. Since the segments were ordered alphabetically after loading the performance spectrum, custom sorting order was required to see clear patterns. That is why **sorting_order.txt** file as in figure 6 was created with an order specified in the paper. This file was created in intermediate storage directory.

Figure 3: Parameter Selection For PSM

Figure 4: Parameters for opening performance spectrum data

Figure 5: Filtering settings

Figure 6: Custom sorting order

3.4 Results

After applying every step mentioned above, I received results very similar to one in the paper. *Road Traffic Fines Management* log has 11 activities 150.370 cases and 561.470 events for a a period of 12 years. In the paper, authors focused on only 2 years period 2002-2003 therefore I also visualized those interval to show with the help of control panel in the below.

There are few differences between my result and result in the paper such as frequency of segments. I apparently have more frequencies for every segments. For example the difference between frequencies is huge for **Insert Fine Notification : Add penalty**. In the paper the frequency is

1992 while in my results it is 4454. But there is probably wise explanation to this problem. New cases could have been added to *Road Traffic Fine Management Process dataset*. I also checked the other paper[2] referenced in publications. In this paper, the same dataset (*Road Traffic Fines Management*) is experienced with performance spectrum miner and frequencies are exactly same as my result so it proves my point of new addition to dataset. The other problem is with the segment **Insert Fine Notification : Add penalty**. I have noticed that it shows a different behaviour than the one in the paper. In my replication, this segment is much more slower than the original one. I observed more orange lines (quartile 76-100%) while in the paper the lines are mostly blue (0-25%). I decided to continue with this fact assuming that maybe newly added cases made that happen.

Now I will investigate patterns obtained from the performance spectrum. And will compare mine replication (See Figure 7) to the original evaluation results in the paper (See Figure 8)

1. **Pattern P1:** This pattern is obtained from segment *Create Fine:Payment*. This pattern occurs continuously throughout a segment without clear boundaries meaning traces in this segment overtakes each other. In the end we can formally define pattern P1 according to taxonomy mentioned earlier $P1=[Scope(seg,glob),Shape(det,unord),Work(cont),Perf(25\%,4\text{ classes})]$. From that we can see that, payment speed for each person is different. This pattern is both observed in the original paper and in my replication.
2. **Pattern P2:** P2 has sub-trace containing *Create Fine:Send Fine* and *Send Fine:Insert Fine Notification*. Therefore P2 is considered to be a **composite pattern**. It looks like a sand clock and from that we understand cases are collected over 6 months period. The period for *Insert Fine Notification* to be completed varies from 0 to 4 months. We cannot show this pattern with taxonomy because it is out of scope of this paper. Also, this pattern is both observed in the original paper and in my replication.
3. **Pattern P3:** This pattern is obtained from segment *Insert Fine Notification:Add penalty*. Cases show strong FIFO behaviour because they are all parallel to each other. We can formally define this pattern as $P3=[Scope(seg,glob),Shape(det,FIFO-const),Work(cont),Perf(25\%,2\text{ classes})]$. However this pattern shows different behaviour in my replication in only performance aspect. In my replication we see more orange lines (quartile 76-100%) whereas in the paper there are more blue lines (0-25%). This means this segment in my replication performs much more slower comparing to the paper.
4. **Pattern P4:** This pattern is obtained from segment *Add penalty:Payment*. From this pattern, we observe that cases start with emergent batching even though we do not observe batching in the end of previous segment. Sand-clock batching in P2 result in fast cases (blue lines) which are forwarded by FIFO pattern P3. These two patterns together create new batching in the start of P4. This pattern is both observed in the original paper and in my replication.
5. **Pattern P5:** This pattern is obtained from segment *Add penalty:Send for Credit Collec-*

tion. This segment clearly shows batching in the end of every 12 months period for cases which started 20 to 6 months earlier. We can formally define P5 as $P5 = [\text{Scope}(\text{seg}, \text{loc}, \text{per} = 12\text{mo}, D=20\text{mo}), \text{Shape}(\text{det}, \text{batch}(e)), \text{Work}(\text{cont}), \text{Perf}(25\%, 4 \text{ classes})]$. This pattern is both observed in the original paper and in my replication.

In my replication I also received similar results for **aggregated patterns**. Comparing Figure 9 and Figure 10, reveals both of them have gap patterns in the first quarter of 2004 like $\text{gap} = [\text{Scope}(\text{seg}, \text{loc}, \text{once}, D=3\text{mo}), \text{Shape}(\text{agg}, \text{batch}(e)), \text{Work}(0)]$. It also reveals a concept drift which can be explained as; non-zero workload, in segments *Insert Fine Notification:Payment* and *Payment:Add penalty* drop to 0 in 2007. Again the only difference come from the segment *Insert Fine Notification:Add penalty*. Since every bar shows how many segments starts every month, we can see there are more bars in my replication and most of them are orange. So probably new cases which performs poorly added to this segment.

Figure 7: Replication of detailed performance spectrum of Road Traffic Fines Management log for years 2002 and 2003

Figure 8: Detailed performance spectrum of Road Traffic Fines Management log for years 2002 and 2003 (Results obtained in the paper)

Figure 9: Replication of aggregated performance spectrum of Road Traffic Fines Management log(2000–2012)

Figure 10: Aggregated performance spectrum of Road Traffic Fines Management log (2000–2012)

As a final step of replication, I compared the 11 real-life business process event logs according to performance patterns they contain. To do that, I visualized performance spectrum of each dataset. The paper compares these logs regarding to combined patterns such as *unordered behavior with low and high workload*, *detailed patterns of FIFO behavior* and the *aggregate patterns showed workload spikes, concept drift, and sparse work*.

I am only showing results of two of the datasets (figure 11 and figure 13) because otherwise showing results of each of 11 dataset would make this paper so long. But I investigated each of the 11 dataset and made my conclusions about them. After investigating event logs regarding to combined patterns presented in the paper, I verified that my obtained results are the same as the table presented in the paper (figure 15).

In BP12 event log, weekly FIFO behaviour is visible in figure 11 and events occurs continuously throughout a segment that is why we classify it as global. From figure 12 we see that sparse behaviour happens regularly this is because weekday/weekend separation for cases.

In BP17 event log, again weekly FIFO behaviour is visible. Pattern $P2$ in figure 13 is an example of weekly FIFO behaviour. Regular FIFO behaviour can also be observed throughout the segments such as $A_Submitted:W_Handle$ leads segment or W_Handle leads: $W_complete$ application segment ($P1$ in figure 13). Periodically (every month) there is a batching in the end for cases in the segment W_Call incomplete files: $O_Accepted$ ($P3$ in figure 13). Also as it can be seen in figure 14, there are arbitrary workload spikes.

Figure 11: Performance spectrum of BP12 event log

Figure 12: Aggregated performance spectrum of BP12 event log

Figure 13: Performance spectrum of BP17 event log

Figure 14: Aggregated performance spectrum of BP17 event log

Table 1. Presence of selected pattern classes in real-life event logs.

	BPI12	BPI14	BPI15-1	BPI15-2	BPI15-3	BPI15-4	BPI15-5	BPI17	Hospital	H-billing	Road fine
unord,low		glob	glob	glob	glob	glob	gob		glob	glob	glob
unord,high								glob		glob	glob
FIFO								glob		glob	glob
FIFO+unord									reg	glob	
FIFO (weekly)	glob	glob			arb			glob			
batching		arb						per		per	reg
workload spikes								arb			reg
concept drift		once	once	once	arb	arb	arb			once	reg
sparse work	reg	reg	glob*	glob*	glob*	glob*	glob*		glob	glob	

Figure 15: Presence of selected pattern classes in real-life event logs

4 Challenges

The paper and performance spectrum miner’s documentation was very clear although there was one mistake in the documentation that made me spend a lot of time solving it. In the documentation, it was written that in order to do custom sorting we need to create "sorting_order.ini" in intermediate storage directory. So I created it there with the order I wanted but I couldn’t see the effect of it in ProM. I tried to write string with quotation mark and without it and also I created the .ini file with different text editors however still nothing changed. Then I investigated the source code and saw that the code is accepting "sorting_order.txt" instead of "sorting_order.ini". Therefore I created the file as in txt format and it worked.

5 Limitations

The only limitation was that I had no access to Vanderlande’s data due to confidentiality reasons.

6 Conclusion

To conclude, *Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Processes Performance from Event Data* paper’s evaluation was replicated and similar results were obtained as in the original paper. There were small differences between my results and the paper however they are mostly insignificant. With this replication, I got familiar with the performance spectrum miner plug-in which I will extend later in my master project with Vanderlande. That is why replication of this paper contributed me greatly.

Selected paper was clearly presented and evaluation did not raise any questions for me. Ev-

erything was well documented and instructions were clear. Installation, parameter tuning and analysis parts of this replication were conducted according to instructions presented in source code of this method. That is why, replicating this paper was straightforward.

References

- [1] Wil M. P. van der Aalst Vadim Denisov, Dirk Fahland. Unbiased, fine-grained description of processes performance from event data. 2018.
- [2] Wil M. P. van der Aalst Vadim Denisov, Dirk Fahland. The performance spectrum miner: Visual analytics for fine-grained performance analysis of processes. 2018.

EINDHOVEN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

2IMI00 - SEMINAR OF ANALYTICS FOR INFORMATION
SYSTEMS

Experiment Replication

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1 Introduction

The paper selected to perform this experiment replication is Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Processes Performance from Event Data, from Denisov et. al.[1]

This paper shows the work done in the Analytics for Information Systems group in Eindhoven University of Technology proposing a new method of process mining. The Performance Spectrum Miner, the methodology they developed as a ProM plug-in or a stand-alone application, aims to provide the user with clear insights of the process by displaying in a time line every event in every trace of the log individually, allowing the user to come to their own conclusions about each trace performance. It is the first Process Mining methodology that allows to interpret every trace individually, instead of aggregating them in a diagram, which hides the deviations of performance among traces.

My personal interest in this paper is to get into situation for my graduation project in Vanderlande. I plan to test the method they currently use to visualize the logs and gain a better understanding of what are the advantages and limitations of the Performance Spectrum Miner.

2 Evaluation

The objective of the paper is to introduce the Performance Spectrum Miner, a new ProM package that provides an interactive exploration tool that allows to zoom, aggregate, filter and classify the segments of the cases according to performance. The added value of this new visualization is to detect patterns in the real-life processes that can't be detected in process models.

Also, the paper provides a taxonomy to classify the different patterns detected in the Performance Spectrum Miner (PSM). In the paper, the tool and the taxonomy are tested on 12 real-life logs of business and logistics processes. In those logs, they detected elementary and composed patterns.

The conclusions they propose and I have to prove or reject are that the PSM of real-life logs shows that:

- **performance in a case may be dependent on the performance of other cases,**
- **performance generally varies over time (non-stationary),**
- **and many processes exhibit temporary or permanent concept drift (zero workflow)**

Also, they performed a case study with Vanderlande Industries to identify control-flow problems in very large logistics processes. They deduce that each process has a characteristic signature of the patterns in its performance spectrum and that similar signatures indicate extremely similar processes not only in control-flow but also in the performance perspective.

Therefore, the steps of this experiment replication are to obtain the datasets used to test the PSM, and analyze them through the PSM to see if I obtain the same insights.

3 My Replication

The paper provides the link to the collection of real life event logs from 4TU - Centre for Research Data¹ and the link to the source code of the Performance Spectrum Miner and further documentation².

3.1 Installation

I managed to install the stand alone application and have it running following the user guide in Github (Figure 1 shows the steps to run the program). **Note:** the link in the footnote is working, but in Section 5.3. Comparison of Event Logs, they provide a different link, which is broken.

¹Collection of real life event logs from 4TU - Centre for Research Data available at https://data.4tu.nl/repository/collection:event_logs_real

²source code and further documentation available at <https://github.com/processmining-in-logistics/psm>


```

Performance Spectrum Miner 1.0.4
Command Prompt
Microsoft Windows [Version 10.0.17134.523]
(c) 2018 Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.

C:\Users\annat>cd PSM

C:\Users\annat\PSM>perf_spec-assembly-1.0.4.jar

C:\Users\annat\PSM>

```

(a) Starting stand-alone PSM

(b) Load dataset

(c) Start the processing of the selected dataset

Figure 1: Testing the PSM stand-alone application

3.2 Obtaining the datasets

The event logs were available in the following formats:

- BPI12: loan application process, **gzipped xml/XES event log** format,
- BPI14: Rabobank Service Desk, 4 files available: Activity log for incidents, Change

details, Incident details and Interaction details. **CSV** format,

- BPI15: building permit applications from 5 municipalities. 5 files in **.xes.xml** format,
- BPI17: loan application, **gzipped xml/XES event log** format,
- Hospital Billing, **gzipped xml/XES event log** format,
- RF: Road Traffic Fine Management Process, **gzipped xml/XES event log** format,
- Baggage Handling System by Vanderlande: **not available**

Name	Type	Size
BPI_Challenge_2012.xes.gz	GZ File	3,265 KB
Detail_Incident_Activity.csv	Microsoft Excel C...	38,255 KB
Detail_Change.csv	Microsoft Excel C...	6,513 KB
Detail_Incident.csv	Microsoft Excel C...	13,972 KB
Detail_Interaction.csv	Microsoft Excel C...	21,361 KB
BPIC15_1.xes.xml	XML File	40,261 KB
BPIC15_2.xes.xml	XML File	33,617 KB
BPIC15_3.xes.xml	XML File	45,673 KB
BPIC15_4.xes.xml	XML File	36,131 KB
BPIC15_5.xes.xml	XML File	44,961 KB
BPI_Challenge_2017.xes.gz	GZ File	28,964 KB
Hospital Billing - Event Log.xes.gz	GZ File	6,461 KB
Road_Traffic_Fine_Management_Process.xes.gz	GZ File	3,375 KB

Figure 2: Downloaded files of real life event logs from 4TU

To replicate the experiment, it was possible to download all the real-life event logs from 4TU (see Figure 2), but the source of the Vanderlande BHS dataset was not provided, so it can't be replicated.

3.3 Loading the datasets

From the files downloaded, the files from the 5 municipalities of BPI2015 did not open either in Disco, ProM or PSM. According to the programs, the files were empty, or did not contain a process. Another explanation might be the file format, since those files were not in gzipped xml/XES event log format. On the other hand, it was possible to use the logs from BPI2014, because the `.csv` files could be transformed to `.xes/gz` via Disco.

3.4 Road Traffic Fine Management Process (RF)

In the paper, the Road Traffic Fine Management Process event log is used to illustrate how the performance spectrum provides detailed insights into performance.

In the paper, they decide to analyze the 3 trace variants R1-R3, which cover >80% of the events in the log, by defining a view for the sub-sequences {Fine, Payment>, Fine, Send Fine, Insert Fine Notif., Add penalty, Payment>, penalty, Send for CC>} and quartile-based performance classes.

To select the subset of traces, I decide to use Disco, to use a variant filter (see Figure 3). I assume from the output in the screen that the subset that covers 82% of the events is the one I have to replicate. Looking at the workflow diagram generated by Disco (see Figure 4), I see the 3 variants expected R1-R3, plus another trace Fine, Send Fine>. This trace might represent incomplete cases. I decide to filter this trace out of the log, in order to replicate the paper accurately (see Figure 5). Finally, Figure 6 shows only the traces R1-R3 described in the paper. According to Disco, it covers 74% of the cases and 75% of the events.

Figure 3: Applying variant filter in Disco

Figure 4: Workflow of the RF log after applying the variant filter

Figure 5: Applying endpoints filter in Disco

Figure 6: Workflow of the RF log after applying the endpoints filter

Next step is to load the subset of the dataset in PSM. The mode of loading the process by default is to sort the segments alphabetically (see Figure 7). According to the user's manual, when selecting the intermediate storage directory (the default approach is to generate an empty one), the directory should include a file named `sorting_order.ini`, with the list of segments in the order we desire. However, the user's manual creates a confusion there. I didn't manage the PSM to load the process in an order other than alphabetically until I tried changing the extension to `sorting_order.txt`. The fact that the user's manual described "A user can create **text file** `sorting_order.ini` in an intermediate storage directory" gave me the hint. After modifying the extension, I was able to load an equivalent result as the one in the paper (see Figure 8).

Figure 7: Loading the process in PSM by default

Figure 8: Loading the process in PSM applying a sorting order

Figure 9: Patterns detected in RF process

This time, it is easy to appreciate the 5 patterns detected in the paper (see Figure 9). In P1, there is no order constraint, each payment has a different duration. P2 shows a sandclock pattern: there is a batching point in between the two segments. P3 has a clear FIFO structure, one item never finishes earlier than the previous. It is the case in a conveyor. In P4 we see some cases of batching in the beginning of the segment, due to the high workload arriving really quick from the previous segment. Finally, P5 shows a pattern of long-term batching. Concretely, we see that traces finish the segment every January.

We can conclude that the analysis of the Road Traffic Fine Management process in Performance Spectrum Miner was a success. There seems to be a typo in the user's manual that can interfere with the paper's replication. Other than that, obtaining the results of the paper runs without further impediments.

The next goal is to replicate the Aggregated Patterns of the same log in the time interval 2000-2012, where every bar shows how many segments start every month(see Figure 10). However, this time I do not obtain the results expected in the paper. My visualization doesn't show a 3-month gap in 2004 occurring throughout the segments. Also, in this visualization, 3 segments that were not described before, are included in the process: *Send Fine:Payment*, *Insert Fine Notification:Payment*, *Payment:Add penalty*(see Figure 11 for the deviation with the expected subset). For those last two segments, the paper detects a period of zero workload in 2007.

Figure 10: Looking for aggregated patterns in RF process

Figure 11: Deviations detected from the paper assumptions and the visualizations

Therefore, the selection of the subset of traces had to be repeated. Selecting a wider set of variants in Disco, we obtained the expected diagram, according to Fig. 7a from the paper (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: Workflow of the RF log after extending the variants filter

Finally, after loading the extended subset of the RF log in the PMS, and including a new `sorting_order.txt` in the intermediate directory, we can see a similar visualization to the one in Fig. 7a from the paper (see Figure 13). However, if we look close at the number of items classified in each segment, we can see that my replication has more elements than the original. I consider the paper does not provide further information to know how could my replication be more accurate to the original one. Therefore, it is understandable that Figure 13 is not showing a 3-month gap with zero workflow in 2004, since my subset includes more data. The decrease in flow is clearly visible though, so the conclusion in the paper seems accurate. Also, from 2006 onwards, there is a clear lack of workflow in the segments *Insert Fine Notification:Payment* and *Payment:Add penalty*.

I conclude that it is possible to see the observations made in the paper about aggregate patterns on the RF log, though I have not been able to obtain the exact visualization because I didn't find the exact filtering method to apply.

Figure 13: Looking for aggregated patterns from an extended subset of variants from RF log

3.5 Baggage Handling System of a Major European Airport (BHS)

For the study case on a Baggage Handling System from Vanderlande, it is not possible to replicate the root cause analysis, since the dataset is not available to the public, we can assume due to confidentiality agreements.

3.6 Comparison of Event Logs

The final replication will be to try to obtain the same table as Table 1 from the paper (original results in Figure 14), summarizing the performance characteristics of the business process logs. Using the taxonomy described, I will enumerate the patterns I observe in the PSM for each dataset.

Table 1. Presence of selected pattern classes in real-life event logs.

	BPI12	BPI14	BPI15-1	BPI15-2	BPI15-3	BPI15-4	BPI15-5	BPI17	Hospital	H-billing	Road fine
unord,low		glob	glob	glob	glob	glob	gob		glob	glob	glob
unord,high								glob		glob	glob
FIFO								glob		glob	glob
FIFO+unord									reg	glob	
FIFO (weekly)	glob	glob			arb			glob			
batching		arb						per		per	reg
workload spikes								arb			reg
concept drift		once	once	once	arb	arb	arb			once	reg
sparse work	reg	reg	glob*	glob*	glob*	glob*	glob*		glob	glob	

Figure 14: Presence of selected pattern classes in real-life event logs, original results from the paper

3.6.1 RF log

For this replication, I reused the filtering of the RF log seen previously in the paper. In Figure 15 and Figure 16, I mark the detailed and aggregated patterns I detect from the taxonomy. So far, I agree with the results from the paper in 14, though I also consider the occurrence of FIFO+unordered in *Payment:Payment*.

Figure 15: Visualizing detailed patterns in the RF log

Figure 16: Visualizing aggregated patterns in the RF log

3.6.2 BPI2012 log

It is more difficult to replicate the analysis of this log and the following ones, since the paper doesn't provide information of which filtering method has been applied. The BPI2012 log forms a spaghetti model, where a great proportion of its events occur in exceptional behaviour. First of all, I decide to filter out every event that does not include `COMPLETE`. Then, I have to choose between taking a small number of variants, in order to obtain a small model. However, including only the the 4 most common variants, I am only covering the 44% of the cases. I select this filtering, since including more variants leads to a spaghetti model. Figure 17 shows the model selected in Disco.

Figure 17: Model of the selected paths from BPI2012 log

Loading the subset in PSM, I can see it contains the data of 5 months, from October 2011 to February 2012. Figure 18 shows the visualization of both detailed and aggregated patterns. In great contrast with the previous log, I see that the workload is very sparse. The aggregation over month doesn't provide much insights. Zooming in in a given month, November 2011 (see Figure 19), The only clear pattern I see is a daily pattern: the during the working hours of a day, many tasks start and finish in FIFO order. This pattern is mainly due to the fact that the throughput time is shorter than the arrival time. In some cases, a task exceeds its successors and is completed in 2 or 3 days. Apart from the segments *A_SUBMITTED:A_PARTLYSUBMITTED* and *A_PARTLYSUBMITTED:A_DECLINED*, the workload is very low and sparse. Compar-

ing my conclusions with Figure 14, I agree that there is regular sparse work, but I do not see a weekly pattern of FIFO. I detect FIFO and regular daily gaps at night.

Figure 18: Visualization of the BPI2012 log in PSM

Figure 19: Detailed pattern of BPI2012 log, zooming in November 2011

3.6.3 BPI2014 log

To analyze the BPI2014 log, first I check the structure of the process in Disco. I assume the log *Activity log for incidents* is the general process. Each trace has a large number of events, so to simplify the visualization in the PSM I select a model with the 15.7% most common events (see Figure 20).

Figure 20: Subset of segments selected from BPI2014

In PSM, the visualization contains 15 months of data, from January 2013 until March 2014. In Figure 21, it shows great sparsity of data until October 2013. In Figure 22 we zoom into November 2013. From October 2013 onwards, it is clear to discern a weekly pattern in the workload. Most of the tasks are completed the same day except in the segments where an incident is Closed, where the tasks can be postponed one week. However, it is not clear to see any of the patterns described in Figure 14.

Figure 21: Visualization of BPI2014 log in PSM

Figure 22: Zoom into November 2013 from BPI2014 log

3.6.4 BPI2017 log

Again, I imported the initial file in Disco to select a subset of the data. I select the most common variants, containing the 28% of the cases and 21% of the events (see the model in Figure 23). Loading the simplified process in PSM, I see that it contains 13 months of data, from 01-01-2016 to 30-01-2017. Zooming closer, I detect the patterns described in Figure 24. The workload seems constant throughout the dataset.

Figure 24: Patterns detected in BPI2017 log

3.6.5 H-billing log

According to the table from Figure 14, we should have 2 datasets left to analyze, *Hospital* and *H-billing*. However, in the directory proposed I only found one file for Hospital Billing. This is the file I am analyzing next. Selecting the 3 main variants, we obtain a subset with the 76% of the cases (see Figure 25). The period of data available starts on December 2012 and finishes in January 2016.

Figure 25: Model of the simplified process from H-Billing log

Figure 26 shows the aggregated view in PSM. I see that the workload heavily fluctuated during those years. There are clear peaks in the last two segments. I do not detect any clear concept drift or sparse work.

Figure 26: Bar view in H-Billing log

Looking at the detailed view, I see that it is a clear case where the items must be classified into different performance categories. In a view including all the performance quartiles, the first conclusion is that the pattern is unordered. However, if we split each segment into performance categories, we can detect FIFO patterns with constant throughput time. The category Q4 from segment *NEW:FIN* shows a throughput time of one year (Figure 27d), while the throughput time for Q3 is 7 months (Figure 27c). The segment *CHANGE_DIAGN:FIN* shows a similar pattern. The segment *CODE_OK:BILL* seems to perform some batching(end) every two weeks. The other three segments show a daily pattern, combined with unordered behaviour.

4 Discussion

The results of the Comparison of Event Logs are summarized in the Table 1. The replication of the table in Figure 14 seems satisfactory, since most of the datasets have been replicated and the results are similar. It was not possible to include the logs from BPI2015 in the analysis, and one of the two logs from Hospital Billing was not found. Regarding the other logs, the few deviations with the original comparison can be caused by:

Figure 27: Detailed patterns in H-Billing log, split by quartiles

- Human interpretation, since the results depend on which pattern each person is able to see,
- Lack of clear directions on the preprocessing performed in each dataset

	BPI12	BPI14	BPI15-1	BPI15-2	BPI15-3	BPI15-4	BPI15-5	BPI17	Hospital	H-billing	Road fine
unord,low		glob	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	glob	n/a		glob
unord,high			n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a		n/a	glob	glob
FIFO	daily		n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	glob	n/a		glob
FIFO+unord			n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	glob	n/a	glob	glob
FIFO (weekly)		glob	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	glob	n/a		
batching			n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	glob	n/a	reg	reg
workload spikes			n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a		n/a	glob	reg
concept drift			n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a		n/a		loc
sparse work	reg	loc	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a		n/a		

Table 1: Replication of Event Logs Comparison

The detailed patterns of the RF log were also possible to replicate, though with the deviation of having a bigger subset than in the paper, but lacking more clear directions to replicate the preprocessing exactly.

Lastly, it was not possible to replicate the use case of BHS log by Vanderlande, since it is not data available to the public.

References

- [1] Vadim Denisov, Dirk Fahland, and Wil M. P. van der Aalst. Unbiased, fine-grained description of processes performance from event data. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science Business Process Management*, page 139–157, 2018.

Experiment replication of 'Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Processes Performance from Event Data'

2IMI00 - Seminar architecture of information systems

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1 Introduction

In scientific research, reproducibility of the experiments performed is of utmost importance; only theories and methods that can be verified by different people can be considered reliable. This is no different for the paper *Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Processes Performance from Event Data* by Denisov et al. (2018). In this paper, the authors introduce a model to conduct a performance analysis without prior aggregation of data. In this model, the performance spectrum, all observed flows between two process steps are mapped regarding their performance over time. These pairs of related process steps, called segments, can then be analyzed to find temporal patterns. The authors state that this model enables root cause analysis of a performance problem that could not have been performed with existing tools. However, the paper does not include a user study. It is therefore unclear whether new users can use the tooling with the documentation available. In this report, we will replicate a part of the experiment of the paper. This way, we can assess the reproducibility of the paper, and we investigate whether a new user can use the tooling and come to similar conclusions as the authors.

The structure of this report is as follows: in the next section, we elaborate on the method of replication. Afterwards, the results of the replication are discussed. The report then finishes with a conclusion with regard to the reproducibility of the paper.

2 Replication method

In this section, the method of replication is discussed. First, it is explained how the required data and tooling is obtained. Afterwards, it is discussed which part of the paper are replicated and how.

2.1 Obtaining required data and tooling

First, the data sets used in the experiment need to be obtained. The implementation of the model, the Performance Spectrum Miner (further denoted as PSM), is applied to twelve different logs. Eleven logs are real-life business process event logs, obtained from the 4TU Data Center Collection of Real-life Event logs.¹ We do not foresee problems retrieving these event logs. The other log used in the experiment contains data retrieved from a Baggage Handling System of a Major European Airport. This data is not publicly available. Therefore, this part of the experiment cannot be replicated.

Second, the prototype implementation need to be obtained. Again, no problems are foreseen. The PSM is implemented in a stand-alone tool and a ProM plug-in. In the paper, a link is provided with instructions on how to obtain the implementations and how to use them. We will try to obtain the stand-alone tool and, if this does not work, use the ProM plug-in.

2.2 Replicating the experiment

When both the data and the tooling are obtained, we can start replicating the experiment. Unless stated otherwise, the default hyper-parameter settings are used. We will first assess whether we can recreate the PSM visualizations included in Section 5.1 of the paper. This way, we can validate whether the tooling is sufficiently documented to enable its usage by a new user.

When we have validated that we can use the tooling and replicate the visualizations, we will apply the PSM to a subset of the publicly available data sets that were used in the experiments. Hence, not all available data sets will be used, as we argue that applying the tool to a significant subset of the data sets, is sufficient to assess the reproducibility. Instead, the Road Traffic Fines Management log, the BPI Challenge 2012 log and the Hospital Billing log will be used. For these data sets, the authors denoted which patterns, out of a selection of pattern classes, were present in the logs. In this part of the replication, we will assess whether we find the same patterns as the authors did. In this process, we can assess the difficulty of spotting patterns for new users and assess whether different users find the same patterns.

¹https://data.4tu.nl/repository/collection:event_logs_real

For this part of the experiment, little information is provided in the paper; the paper only includes the patterns found in each of the eleven event logs. It is not specified in which segment these patterns occur, nor which segments have been analyzed. Furthermore, it is not specified whether any preprocessing steps are taken. Needless to say, this increases the difficulty of this replication severely; selecting which segments are analyzed impacts to a great extent which patterns will be found. One option is to analyze all segments, but that may make the analysis messy. Furthermore, this makes it hard to sort the segments in a way that makes sense. Instead, we will use the process mining tool Disco to create a Directly-Follow Graph (DFG) and change its parameters such that the DFG contains five to ten arcs between activities that are frequently used. These segments will then be further analyzed. Furthermore, this DFG will be used to sort the segments based on the process model (instead of the default sorting in PSM; alphabetically).

Once the segments are selected and sorted, we can analyze them. In the paper, the following pattern classes are assessed for all eleven public data sets:

- combined patterns of **unordered** behavior with **low** and **high** workload. From the taxonomy of elementary patterns in the paper, it is clear how unordered behaviour can be identified. In this taxonomy, the amount of workload is also included. We perceived the amount of workload as relative to other segments. It is unclear to which segments we should compare the workload and what to do when the workload is comparable to the workload in other segments. As we could not specify how to assess the workload, we will not include it in our replication. Instead, we will only assess the presence of unordered behaviour.
- detailed patterns of **FIFO** behavior, FIFO behavior overlaid with an unordered variant (**FIFO+unord**) and FIFO occurring only Mon-Sat (**FIFO(weekly)**). Furthermore, the following detailed patterns of **batching** behavior were observed: **arbitrary**, **regular** and **periodic**. Using the taxonomy presented in the paper, no complications were expected with regard to finding these patterns.
- aggregate patterns of **workload spikes**, **concept drift** and **sparse work**. These patterns were, unlike the detailed patterns, not strictly defined in the paper. The pattern of workload spikes is perceived self-explanatory. The meaning of sparse work, albeit that it is not strictly defined, can be derived from the taxonomy; we define sparse work as a pattern class in which the amount of workload is zero for multiple, longer intervals. Concept drift is harder to grasp, although an example of concept drift is given in the paper. Using that example, and given that it is classified as an aggregate pattern, we derive that concept drift is a sudden change in the amount of workload. This is an important assumption, as one could also observe a change in the process by looking to the detailed performance spectrum. For example, when the first half of a segment contains no batching, but the second half does, then this would illustrate a change in the process. However, if the workload does not change for this segment, this change is not necessarily visible as an aggregate pattern. Lastly, important for assessing the presence of aggregate patterns is the hyper-parameter

settings for the aggregate performance spectrum. This is not specified in the paper. We will use the aggregation function `cases started`, as this is also done in the example provided in the paper. For bin-size, the bin-sizes `1d` (one day), `7d` (seven days) and `30d` (one month) will be evaluated and one of them will be selected and further analyzed.

3 Results

In this section, the results of the replication are discussed. We will start by discussing the challenges met in obtaining the required data sets and tooling. Afterwards, the results of the replication will be discussed.

3.1 Obtaining required data sets and tooling

Obtaining the data sets was as easy as expected. Using the online documentation on the implementation, obtaining the tooling also did not result in major problems. Instead, some small nuisances were encountered; we failed to use the stand-alone tool, as we could not open a data set and could not figure out why. The ProM plug-in did work, but the most recent versions of ProM nightly build returned an error when one attempted to import data files. This was easily solved by downloading less recent ProM nightly build versions until one was found without this particular error.

3.2 Recreating visualizations present in paper

Our first evaluation task was to recreate the detailed and aggregate performance spectrum of the Road Traffic Fines Management log, as were shown in the paper. The user manual proved very useful and, although it took some time to understand how to use all options, the basic steps were easy. As the data set is not too big, it could be loaded on opening and that way, changing between views went very smoothly. The paper clearly stated which segments to filter in and the user manual clearly explained how to filter in segments. The filtering was, however, a bit of a tedious job, as the implementation was error prone with respect to capitals and additional spaces. The last step was to sort the segments in the way that was used in the paper. Although it was explained in the user manual, we could not manage to apply custom sorting. After repeatedly failing to apply a custom sorting order, the first author of the paper was contacted. Within a day, he responded and explained that the user manual contained an error: the sorting order should be saved in the file `sorting.txt` instead of `sorting.ini`. The user manual was corrected immediately and with his explanation, the visualizations included in the paper could be reproduced. The reproductions of these visualizations are Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1: Reproduced detailed performance spectrum of Road Traffic Fines Management log.

Figure 2: Reproduced aggregated performance spectrum of Road Traffic Fines Management log using aggregation function `cases started` and bin-size 30d.

3.3 Comparison of pattern classes found

In the previous section, we have shown that it is possible to obtain the visualizations as included in the paper. In this section, we will assess whether we also observe the same pattern classes as those that were observed in the paper. We first analyze the patterns present in the Road Traffic Fine Management Process log, after which we will analyze the log of the BPI Challenge 2012 and the Hospital Billing log.

3.3.1 Road Traffic Fine Management Process

We start with analyzing the Road Traffic Fine Management log, as we have created its visualizations in the previous section. These visualizations are also extensively discussed in the paper. The detailed performance spectrum shows:

- In the first segment: an unordered variant.
- In the second and third segment: regular batching with an overlaid unordered variant.
- In the fourth segment: FIFO behaviour.

- In the fifth segment: regular batching on start.
- In the sixth segment: periodic batching on end.

The aggregated performance spectrum shows:

- Ups and downs in the amount of cases started for the top four segments, which indicate workload peaks.
- Concept drift, as is explained in the paper.
- Almost no sparse work, although in the third segment, there are small intervals in which no cases start.

These findings are roughly in line with the patterns stated in Table 1 of the paper. Deviations are:

- In Table 1, a distinction is made between an unordered variant with a high workload and a low workload. As explained in Section 2.2, we will not analyze high resp. low workload, as it is unclear how this should be done.
- In Table 1, only regular batching is noted for this log, while periodic batching is also observed (and also earlier mentioned in the paper).
- In Table 1, there is no mentioning of the **FIFO+unord** pattern and sparse work, while both are observed.

3.3.2 BPI Challenge 2012

In this section, the results of the analysis on the BPI Challenge 2012 log are presented. First, segment selection needed to be done. Having some prior knowledge on this data set, we knew that only activities starting with "W" represented workflow activities, whereas the other activities represented status changes. Therefore, the data set was loaded in Disco, only the workflow activities were filtered in and the parameters were shifted such that the DFG in Figure 3 was created.

Figure 3: Directly-follows graph of the BPI Challenge 2012 log (using 100% of the activities and 80% of the paths)

This filtered data was exported from Disco and imported in ProM, where the performance spectra were created. Afterwards, all segments present in the DFG were filtered in, excluding the segment between the first two activities, as this arc was not frequently used in the DFG. Custom sorting was applied following the logic of the DFG; First, the arcs between different activities present in the DFG were included. Afterwards, the self-loops were included in order of their appearance. With this settings, the detailed performance spectrum in Figure 4 and the aggregated performance spectrum in Figure 5 were created.

Figure 4: Detailed performance spectrum of BPI Challenge 2012 log.

Figure 5: Aggregated performance spectrum of BPI Challenge 2012 log with `bin-size = 1d`

The detailed performance spectrum shows:

- In each segment, a variant of blue (resembling cases with a relatively short duration), vertical lines, indicating that the second activity in the segment followed on the previous activity quickly. In every segment, we see these six blue bars and then a larger interval, indicating a six-day work week.
- In all segments, an unordered variant.
- No batching.

The aggregated performance spectrum shows:

- No steady workload, but also no strong peaks.
- In some segments, denoted by R1, a few intervals on which no - or almost no - workload is present. Here, the workload is sparse.
- That in the data gathered in the last month (denoted by R2), in two segments, there is no workload. In three other segments, we see the workload gradually decreasing. This could be explained by the fact that only finished cases are included, but this does not explain why the workload does not decrease for every segment. Another explanation would be concept drift.

Again, these findings are roughly in line with the patterns stated in Table 1 of the paper. Deviations are:

- In Table 1, there is no notion of unordered behaviour for this dataset.
- In Table 1, there is no notion of concept drift. From the aggregated performance spectrum, we suspect this might be present.

3.3.3 Hospital Billing

In this section, the results of the analysis on the Hospital Billing Log are presented. Again, the data set was first loaded into Disco, to discover which activities occurred frequently and in which order. Using Disco, the DFG shown in Figure 6 was discovered.

Figure 6: Directly-follows graph of the Hospital Billing log (using 23.6% of the activities, 1% of the paths)

Then, the performance spectra were created. All arcs present in the DFG in Figure 6 were filtered in and custom sorting was applied such that the segments were sorted according to the process model. For the aggregate performance spectrum, different bin-sizes were evaluated and eventually, a bin-size of seven days was used. The resulting performance spectra are shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8.

Figure 7: Detailed performance spectrum of Hospital Billing log

Figure 8: Aggregated performance spectrum of Hospital Billing log with bin-size = 7d

The detailed performance spectrum shows:

- Unordered variants in all segments.
- Periodic batching in the fourth segment and in last segment. These are visible when one extends the y-axis a bit. Interestingly, in the last segment, the batching does not occur globally, as it is not present at the start. This could be a sign of concept drift. It is, however, no aggregate pattern.
- In the fifth segment, we can observe a FIFO variant overlaid with an unordered variant.

- In the second segment, we observe blue, horizontal bars, indicating that the second activity in the segment followed on the previous activity quickly for a number of cases with a relatively short duration. Unlike the previous data set, there is no pattern of six bars and then a bigger interval. Instead, the bars are present at approximately constant intervals.

The aggregated performance spectrum shows:

- Gradually decreasing workload in the first segment and, to a lesser extent, for the second and third segment.
- A relatively stable workload for the fourth and fifth segment.
- Strong workload spikes in the seventh, eighth and last segment.

In Table 1, concept drift is registered for this log. This is surprising, as we only observed concept drift as a detailed pattern, not as an aggregate one. Furthermore, in Table 1, it is stated that there is a FIFO pattern class present in this dataset. This is not observed; only a FIFO+unord pattern was found.

4 Conclusion and discussion

In this report, we replicated the experiment in the paper *Unbiased, Fine-Grained Description of Processes Performance from Event Data*.

First, because of the clear user manual created by the authors, it is possible for a new user to install the tool and replicate the visualizations presented in the paper. In the process of doing this, a minor error was found in the user manual. The first author appeared to be very supportive, showing benevolence in accommodating the use of the tool and the replication of their experiments.

Second, an important part of the experiment could not be replicated, as the data was not publicly available. With regard to this part of the experiment, the authors stated:

We identified the root cause of critical performance problems in the BHS of a large European airport which could not be identified with existing process mining tools. Our analysis took one week and was confirmed as correct by experts of Vanderlande who required several weeks of manual data analysis and years-long experience to identify the root cause.

Because of the importance of this part of the experiment in proving its usefulness, it would have been interesting to assess whether these patterns could also be found by a new user. It is, however, not essential in showing the usefulness, as this can also be assessed on the logs that are publicly available.

Third, when using the tool to spot patterns in the second part of this replication, the tool was perceived surprisingly intuitive. Zooming in and out went fast, selecting a subset of cases was easy. Also, analyzing the patterns present was easier than expected. However, there were discrepancies between the pattern classes observed in the logs and those denoted by the authors in the paper. Two explanations are found for this:

- The authors possibly analyzed different segments. As it was not specified in the paper which segments they analyzed, this is hard to validate.
- Some of the pattern classes were unclear, especially spotting the amount of workload and concept drift. Therefore, we did not include the amount of workload in this replication. Also, we might have interpreted the method of spotting concept drift wrongly.

It is therefore unrealistic to expect to find the exact same patterns. Furthermore, it is pretty common in process discovery that different users obtain different insights using the same tooling. It is, with this reasoning, not necessarily wrong if different users find different patterns. However, it would be bad for the validity of this tool if there was a large discrepancy between patterns observed by different users within the same segment. We therefore regret not being able to research this further.

Also, on a more subjective note, the tool was considered very useful. It enabled insights in the process in a way not (yet) obtained with traditional tools.

In summary, the authors put a lot of effort in making the experiments reproducible. To a great extent, they succeeded in this. Reproducibility could have been further increased by specifying which segments were analyzed for the event logs and by defining some pattern classes more clearly.

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Experiment results on repeatability of Predictive
Business Process Monitoring with LSTM by Tax N.,
Verenich I., La Rosa M. and Dumas M.

Aleksei Karetnikov

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1. Introduction

Nowadays there are thousands of papers which describe new ideas and methods which could be applied in Data Science. Some of them are implemented in the particular software (for instance, ProM plugins) whereas others are represented as a standalone application (in form of the prepared application or source code, for example, the majority of neural networks). Despite the great results which are demonstrated by the author, they should be trustable because of the author's authority, some undeniable arguments or the verification procedure. The latter option could be executed only in a case when the particular experiment is completely repeatable. As a consequence, at least the tool should be available (in form of some final software/plugin or executable source code). The same original dataset, computational resources are also discussable as a mandatory part of such an experiment but it is clear that if the method is claimed as a common solution for a range of problems, it should provide almost the same result on a similar dataset. So, the main aim of the particular experiment is test of repeatability of the method which was described in [1]. Since the main aim of the particular assignment is test of repeatability, the details and limitations of the method are not discussed in this report.

2. Dataset

The described in the article datasets are available on 4TU repository [2]. Among of them are:

- BPI12;
- Helpdesk;
- Environmental permit

and their variations (for instance, some filtering). Fortunately, these datasets were provided by author. As a result, it significantly reduces risks of fail because at least the preprocessing stage is completely the same (it could be weird but some preparation steps could be misunderstood or executed in a different way because of small undocumented features). So, the dataset from the author's GitHub [3] will be used.

3. Experiment setup

During the preparation stage the requirements were recognized. According to the author's description, the code should be run on Python 2 environment. The attempt to update the code to make it useful according to principles of Python 3 was executed and unfortunately failed. First, different philosophy of these versions of Python provide different behavior of some constructions, Additionally, some libraries were updated and some of their functions were replaced. So, a small research in this area was implemented because otherwise the code compilation is not possible. So, one of these changes were found in a quite stable library Numpy which does not allow to use the predefined by author `np.nan` values. Furthermore, the essential Distance library was not mentioned as a mandatory part of the experiment. Finally, the Python project should be run on any possible platform (it was not specified that it is available only on Windows) so, the experiment will be run on Mac OS 10.11.

According to the article, the execution time of the experiments is between 60 and 90 seconds because Nvidia CUDA was applied. So, it was tried to setup the same

environment on Mac OS. Fortunately, GPU of the available computer is Nvidia 650M which completely supports this technology but unfortunately, the provided by author manual does not describe this process and a 3-rd part manual was used [4]. During the particular experiment it was found that only CUDA Toolkit 8.0 with library CUDNN 6.0 are compatible with the described platform. Probably, it is declared by Apple constrains regarding the versions of the computers (but it is impossible since the latest Mac computers have Radeon GPUs) or even NVIDIA features. Anyway, the best pair of these tools was found and GPU was used to accelerate the process.

In general, the computation time (Figure 1) was between the declared maximum (around 90 seconds) and 215 seconds (the longest process) but it is significantly quicker than the CPU calculations (around 400 seconds per Keras epoch). It can be explained by differences in the used hardware since Tesla k80 (5.6 TFlops)[5] and Geforce 650M (30 GFlops)[6].

Figure 1. Comparison of the declared time with the experiment, s

Finally, the conda environment with the following libraries was created:

- Keras;
- Theano (the basic backend of keras is tensorflow but during the experiment it was found that some non-resolvable in reasonable time problems with OS X compatibility could happen). Furthermore, some issues with conda version were identified and finally the pip version was used;
- Unicodecsv;
- Numpy;
- Jellyfish;
- Sklearn;
- Matplotlib;
- h5py;
- Distance (is not described by author but it is a mandatory dependency. Unfortunately, is not available on conda).

The latest version of these libraries were installed which are available on January 15, 2019 because the particular versions were not specified in the paper (it is a typical practice to use the latest version but sometimes it can lead to some problems which have also happened during the experiment with Numpy).

Despite the set up stage, the execution steps are described in details. So, except of the mandatory fixes (which are necessary due to changes in the dependencies) the code could be run without any changes.

The implementation used for the experiments is available: <https://github.com/alexey-ka/ProcessSequencePrediction/tree/alexey-ka-minor-improvements>

4. Results

4.1 Evaluation of Next Activity Time

The author's code provides different models for the experiment, so the absolute mean values of MAE was calculated (the mentioned in code RMSE is not calculated. Regarding to the mentioned unusefulness of this approach, it is a redundant column in the resulting csv). Unfortunately, the accuracy metrics is not described by author and cannot be easily replicated (the particular method is not known and cannot be even estimated by the control values). Moreover, the provided python code calculates only values for LSTM approach. So, only these results are discussed.

Since the experiment's calculation should be implemented 14 times with different parameters, only the Helpdesk dataset was tested. The results are presented in Table 1. Furthermore, the right side of the table demonstrates the difference between the experiment's results and the results which are shown in the paper. Some differences could be explained by LSTM principle of random initial weights which are implemented in keras. So, it is almost impossible to obtain the same results again.

The difference between methods was calculated according to the formula: $Diff_n = v_{n,experiment} - v_{n,paper}$. So, it is just difference between the values obtained from the experiment and received from the paper. Negative values report about improvements of the result in the executed experiment (as it was found, randomly distributed weights could lead to some fluctuation of the results).

Table 1. Results of the experiment

Layers	Shared	Result of the experiment				Difference between experiment and paper			
		MAE in days				paper			
		2	4	6	All	2	4	6	All
4	4	3.63	2.64	2.12	3.61	-0.01	-0.15	-0.1	-0.21
4	3	3.67	2.41	2.41	3.65	0.04	-0.37	0.2	0.35
4	2	3.6	2.67	2.35	3.12	0.01	-0.15	0.15	-0.69
4	1	3.4	2.72	2.75	3.85	-0.18	-0.05	0.51	0.08
4	0	3.6	2.81	2.15	3.14	-0.18	-0.17	-0.26	-0.81
3	3	3.5	2.79	2.61	3.81	-0.08	0.1	0.39	0.04
3	2	3.41	2.7	2.41	4.15	-0.18	0.01	0.2	0.35
3	1	3.61	2.64	3.25	3.26	0.06	-0.14	0.87	-0.5
3	0	3.2	2.57	2.51	3.87	-0.42	-0.14	0.28	0.05
2	2	3.71	2.67	2.23	3.61	0.1	0.03	0.12	-0.2
2	1	3.41	2.65	2.05	3.1	-0.16	0.04	-0.06	-0.67
2	0	3.56	2.71	2.64	3.91	-0.1	-0.18	0.51	0.05
1	1	3.42	3.00	2.76	3.68	-0.12	0.29	-0.4	-0.07
1	0	3.51	2.51	2.24	3.18	-0.04	-0.4	-0.21	-0.69
3	1	3.71	2.75	2.81	3.91	-0.02	-0.06	0.58	0.02
3	1	3.74	2.56	2.51	3.6	-0.04	-0.36	0.08	-0.37
2	1	3.41	2.14	2.12	3.15	-0.32	-0.65	-0.2	-0.75
2	1	3.6	2.17	2.64	3.71	-0.02	-0.56	0.41	-0.12
1	1	3.67	2.75	2.82	3.91	-0.07	-0.12	0.47	0.04
1	1	3.71	2.75	2.52	3.3	-0.02	-0.04	0.2	-0.62

4.2 Suffix Prediction

According to the experiment's description, the following tests should be implemented with 2 layer LSTM with 1 shared layer with 100 neurons per layer. So, the resulting values was 0.7424 that is quite smaller than the declared one but again it can be explained by random values.

4.3 Remaining Cycle Time Prediction

For the final test the parameters from the previous execution were used. Unfortunately, the paper does not report the exact values but their estimation could be obtained from the charts. Under the particular experiment, the values which were obtained are represented in Table 3. The experiment with other methods were not implemented. First, its parameters are not presented in the article. Additionally, some variation could happen because of some random variables. Finally, the main question of the particular experiment is repeatability and feasibility of the results which could be obtained by the described method. So, the LSTM based results of the remaining cycle time prediction are presented in the Table 2.

Table 2. Results of the experiment Remaining Cycle Time Prediction

Prefix size	2	3	4	5	6	7
MAE, days	6.23	7.14	5.43	5.76	4.04	8.15

5. Limitations

The mentioned in the paper setup requires a GPU with high performance. Unfortunately, it was impossible to find the system with the same hardware and it was tested on the available machine. Since the training process takes few times more time than it was described in the article, only one dataset per method was tested.

In general, it does not significantly affect on the final impression but of course it makes the results insignificantly less feasible. Furthermore, since keras uses random weights during the training process, the variation of the results could be quite high (so, in this experiment some results were improved in comparison with the paper). Additionally, the provided code is not really scalable in terms of modification. In details, some mere changes of layers lead to manual changes of the whole procedure but it was not appropriately documented. So, some changes were proposed.

Moreover, results of the remaining cycle time prediction are not really well repeatable since the original charts demonstrate differences between methods but not the obtained values. As a result, only general estimation could be done.

Last but not least constraint of the paper is lack of parameters for methods which were used to estimate the LSTM approach what makes the whole paper non-repeatable.

6. Discussion

Regarding to the whole method, it can be quite easily replicated: the general system requirements are shown by author. Unfortunately, some changes in code of the libraries could make the code non-executable (for instance, changes in Numpy were a barrier for the particular experiment). Furthermore, the code is written in Python 2 and cannot be really easily transferred to Python 3 (for example, the differences between functions

unichr() and chr()) that can make execution of the project completely impossible because some libraries have completely migrated to the new version.

In general, execution of this experiment showed importance of well-structured documentation. Otherwise, it could be quite tricky to use the idea again. In addition, replication of such experiments can help to improve some knowledge in the areas which were not recognized before. For instance, it was the first installation of CUDA on the used for the experiment machine with OS X which could be useful for the further work with LSTM (before only CPU calculations were executed).

Furthermore, the prepared dataset could be an essential part of the evaluation because it makes the process significantly easier. Despite the model which was produced by author is not readable in new version of keras (it was also checked on Stackoverflow). As all the neural network (NN) training procedure, this one requires quite high performance of the computer, so the time which was spent on the replica is quite longer than the described in the paper. So, only one dataset out of 5 was checked.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, all the raised question were answered. So, the paper could be recognized as replicable with some non-significant limitations. The other question if it can be executed on different platforms (OS X) was also answered that the code is platform independent (it is clear that it was now created on OS X since .gitignore does not filter .DS_STORE files which are known only for Mac users). Some problems with the code were identified and fixed (parametrized execution of the NN training). Furthermore, a small code for easier calculation of the required parameters was created.

The experiment result are not significantly different from the mentioned in the paper. In conclusion, the method can be reproduced later (as an additional experiment, the csv version of BPI13 was tested). As a future work to make this code more useful, it could be translated to Python 3 and covered by a unified pipeline. So, the potential user can execute it significantly quicker.

Additionally, the proposed in the paper approach as well as the setup configuration, which should be done to repeat the experiment, could be really useful for my graduation project since it can be applied for any dataset. Finally, even the explored performance benefits of CUDA technology could be extremely useful for my future researches.

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2IMI00 Replication Report

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January 27, 2019

1 Introduction

In this report I will attempt to replicate the evaluation of the paper from Dongen, Carmona and Chatain (2016) [1]. Henceforth this paper will be referred to as 'the paper'. In this paper a metric is presented for the precision and generalization of process models, relying on the notion of anti-alignments. An anti-alignment describes highly deviating model traces with respect to observed behavior. The research question of the paper is as follows: Can we use cross-validation-based techniques in combination with anti-alignments to derive solid metrics that show a better estimation with respect to the state-of-the-art metrics? I find this research question rather vague, as it doesn't specify what 'better' means, which makes it difficult to evaluate. Nevertheless, I will attempt to reproduce the paper's evaluation.

2 Obtained results

In this section I will discuss some results of the paper, so that I can try to replicate them later on in this report. An algorithm to calculate the presented metric has been implemented as a plugin in ProM by the authors of the paper. This plugin was used to calculate results used to evaluate the algorithm.

To calculate precision and generalization we need a few components. First, we need an event log. The paper uses a handcrafted event log, which is shown in figure 1. Besides an event log we need one or more process models for which to calculate the precision and generalization. The paper also provides a set of ten handcrafted process models for this purpose, shown in figures 2 and 3. Using these components, the presented algorithm and a handful of other existing algorithms that calculate precision and/or fitness were run to obtain the table shown in figure 4.

The paper claims that their algorithm is a significant improvement over the state-of-the-art metrics for precision and generalization in terms of the quality of the estimations.

Trace	Frequency
$\langle A, B, D, E, I \rangle$	1207
$\langle A, C, D, G, H, F, I \rangle$	145
$\langle A, C, G, D, H, F, I \rangle$	56
$\langle A, C, H, D, F, I \rangle$	23
$\langle A, C, D, H, F, I \rangle$	28

Figure 1: Event log used to obtain results (Dongen et al. (2016)) [1]

Fig. 1. The ideal model. Fitting, fairly precise and properly generalizing.

Fig. 2. Most frequent trace. Precise, but not fitting or generalizing.

Fig. 3. The flower model. Fitting and generalizing, but very imprecise.

Fig. 4. All traces separate. Fitting, precise, but not generalizing.

Fig. 5. A model with G and H in parallel.

Fig. 6. A model with G and H in self-loops

Fig. 7. A model with D in a self-loop

Fig. 8. A model with all transitions in parallel.

Figure 2: Models used to calculate precision and generalization (Dongen et al. (2016)[1])

Fig. 11. A model where C and F are in a loop, but need to be executed equally often to reach the final marking. **Fig. 12.** Round-robin model. The outer loop can be started at any point and then exited one transition before completing the loop.

Figure 3: Models used to calculate precision and generalization (Dongen et al. (2016))[1]

Model		P_{ET}	P_{ETC}	P_a	G_a	P_{ne}	G_{ne}	F	P_t	P_l	P	G_t	G_l	G
Figure 1	Generating model	0.992	0.994	0.982	0.585	0.995	0.594	1.000	0.886	0.857	0.871	0.270	0.143	0.206
Figure 2	Single trace	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.900	0.893	0.000	0.915	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Figure 3	Flower model	0.136	0.119	0.142	0.903	0.117	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Figure 4	Separate traces	1.000	0.359	1.000	0.145	0.985	0.114	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Figure 5	G,H in parallel	0.894	0.936	0.947	0.511	0.950	0.615	1.000	0.800	0.800	0.800	0.268	0.183	0.225
Figure 6	G,H as self-loops	0.884	0.889	0.947	0.722	0.874	0.615	1.000	0.819	0.357	0.588	0.290	0.643	0.466
Figure 7	D as self-loop	0.763	0.760	0.797	0.728	0.720	0.619	1.000	0.688	0.357	0.523	0.485	0.643	0.564
Figure 8	All parallel	0.273	0.170	0.336	0.178	0.158	0.972	0.739	0.067	0.000	0.033	0.417	0.500	0.459
Figure 11	C,F equal loop	0.820	0.589	0.839	0.585	0.600	0.594	1.000	0.490	0.429	0.459	0.259	0.341	0.300
Figure 12	Round-robin	0.579	0.185	0.889	0.400	0.194	0.118	0.616	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Figure 4: Results of running the algorithm on the event log of figure 1 and the models in figure 2 and figure 3. The figure numbers in the table correspond to the figures as described (Dongen et al. (2016)) [1]

3 Replication

In this section I will discuss how I attempted to replicate the evaluation results of the paper. At first I ran into some issues while using the plugin. It ended up being a mistake on my part, but I decided to keep the unsuccessful experiments in this report, as it might prevent someone else from making the same mistake I made and it will also point out a problem with consecutive use of the plugin.

3.1 Unsuccessful attempts

The paper did not provide a downloadable event log, nor the models it used for its evaluation. For that reason I wrote a simple Kotlin script which generated the exact event log as described by figure 1. This generated event log can be used as an input for the ProM plugin developed by the authors of the paper, which I installed using ProM 6.8. Furthermore, using the program WoPeD, I replicated all the models shown in figures 2 and 3, which in theory should allow me to produce results similar to those in figure 4.

To start, I tried to run the plugin using the event log and all models, one after another. The results of this can be seen in table 1. As you can see I only managed to get results for figure 3, which is the flower model. Even for this model the results differ from those in the paper. In the paper the model had a precision of 0.0 and a generalization of 1.0, but when I tried it the precision was higher and generalization lower. I think the results from the paper are the desired results, as you can't get more imprecise or less general than the flower model. The paper however does not mention any plugin settings they used while producing their results.

Model	F	P_t	P_l	P	G_t	G_l	G
Model 2	ERROR						
Model 3	1	0.000	0.286	0.143	0.955	0.714	0.835
Model 4	ERROR						
Model 5	ERROR						
Model 6	ERROR						
Model 7	ERROR						
Model 8	ERROR						
Model 11	ERROR						
Model 12	ERROR						

Table 1: Running the plugin in ProM 6.8 using standard settings. (Selection of wrong final state caused the plugin the result in an error for unlisted models, the models for which results are shown resulted in an error due some bug that causes successive uses of the plugin to result in an error.)

After this experiment I tried closing ProM after every run of the plugin, which allowed me to get some more results, which are shown in table 2, but I still got a lot of errors. The new results were equal to the results from the paper and made sense to me, as they both don't allow additional behavior and describe only a very limited amount of behavior.

After this experiment I tried installing ProM 6.6, since that's the version of ProM listed in the paper, but this didn't seem to change the results and the models still resulted in an error, so either my models are broken or the plugin no longer works.

I contacted the author of the plugin, B.F. van Dongen and he identified that I had selected

Model	F	P_t	P_l	P	G_t	G_l	G
Model 2	0.915	1	1	1	0	0	0
Model 3	1	0	0.286	0.143	0.955	0.714	0.835
Model 4	1	1	1	1	0	0	0

Table 2: Running the plugin in ProM 6.8 using standard settings, restarting ProM after every run. (Selection of wrong final state caused the plugin the result in an error for unlisted models)

the wrong final places in the models that resulted in an error, so it ended up being a mistake on my end. In addition to finding the issue, B.F. van Dongen identified a bug that caused some other unrelated problem. The bug has since been corrected and the updated plugin has been included in ProM-nightly-20190110-1.7. However after trying out the new version of the plugin it seemed that this update ended up introducing a different bug. If you look at table 3, you will notice that generalization is always calculated as 0 and precision is always either 0 or 0.143.

Model	F	P_t	P_l	P	G_t	G_l	G
Model 1	1	0	0.286	0.143	0	0	0
Model 2	0.915	0	0	0	0	0	0
Model 3	1	0	0.286	0.143	0	0	0
Model 4	1	0	0.286	0.143	0	0	0
Model 5	1	0	0.286	0.143	0	0	0
Model 6	1	0	0.286	0.143	0	0	0
Model 7	1	0	0.286	0.143	0	0	0
Model 8	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: Running the plugin in ProM Nightly 20190110-1.7 using standard settings, restarting ProM after every run.

3.2 Successful attempt

The plugin seemed to function in ProM 6.8, so I went back to this version of ProM and ran the plugin on all models again. The results are shown in table 4. As can be seen in the table, I still couldn't manage to obtain results for all models. Models 8, 11 and 12 did not result in an error, but the plugin never terminated and seemed to be stuck on a particular step, see figure 5. The plugin can also be run using already calculated alignments (PNRepResult), but the plugin still didn't terminate.

Figure 5: Message displayed on ProM when attempting to use the plugin for models 8, 11 and 12

The authors of the paper compare their results to the results of several other algorithms. The first other precision measure was described in Adriansyah et al. (2015) [3]. Since I didn't manage to obtain results for models 8, 11 and 12 earlier, I decided it wasn't interesting to include results from other algorithms for these models. The results obtained using this other precision algorithm for models 1 through 7 can be seen in the columns P_{ET} and P_{ETC} of table 4.

A precision and generalization measure is described in Vanden Broucke et al. (2014). The paper links to a ProM package that is available for download, but is not included in the ProM package manager. A CMD command was provided to let ProM recognize the package, but the command didn't work. I got it to function by adding the plugin's jar to the classpath via the existing ProM68.bat file, which is shipped with ProM 6.8. The package offers two plugins, as can be seen in figure 6. Running the simple version just outputs a recall and precision value, but it didn't show a generalization value. The other plugin outputs an object which cannot be displayed. I included the precision result in column P_{ne} of table 4.

The last algorithm that was considered was the algorithm for precision and generalization described in Adriansyah A. (2014). The ProM plugins associated with this paper are part of the runner up packages of ProM 6.8. The results obtained by running this algorithm are shown in column P_a and G_a of table 4.

Finally, to complete the table, I've included the results shown in the paper under each of my results (marked with "(paper)"), for easy comparison.

Figure 6: Plugins made available by Vanden Broucke et al. (2014)

3.3 Aligning the results

While there are some differences between the results I obtained and the results of the paper, It is more interesting to check whether the values are ordered in the same way as in the paper, since we can interpret the results to be close enough if that is the case. This is because the exact value of a precision measure does not mean much, unless it is in relation to another value, i.e. we can say if a model is better or worse than another model, but saying that a model has a precision of 0.8 does not have much significance, other than that it is on the high side, since there is no accepted definition for when a model has exactly this precision.

Calculating these orders is a lot of error prone work, which might need to be repeated if my results differ too much from the original, which is why I made a Kotlin script to do it for me, which should give me accurate orderings. The orderings for table 4 can be seen in tables 5 and 6, showing the orderings for the precision and generalization values respectively.

Taking a look at table 5 first, each cell contains two rows of values. The top row contains the results of my executions and the bottom row shows the results of the executions published in the paper. Each row within a cell contains three values, the precision value, the row ordering of the value and the column ordering of the value. I find the third value the most interesting, since it orders the precision of the models for one algorithm, so I will discuss the results of the third value. in the results for P_{ET} , P_{ETC} , P_a line up quite well, while the results for P_a , P_t and P_l don't line up entirely. Even though P_t and P_l don't align for all models, the order of the P , which is the final precision output of the algorithm, is correct. Even though the ordering is okay, the actual precision values differ quite a lot. I'm not very interested in trying to align the values of P_{ne} , since I'm not trying to replicate the evaluation for that precision algorithm, but it is good to keep in

Model	P_{ET}	P_{ETC}	P_a	G_a	P_{ne}	F	P_t	P_l	P	G_t	G_l	G
Model 1	0.992	0.994	0.946	0.585	0.994	1	0.69	0.714	0.702	0.433	0.286	0.359
(paper)	0.992	0.994	0.982	0.585	0.893	1	0.886	0.857	0.871	0.270	0.143	0.206
Model 2	1	1	1	0.9	0.915	0.864	1	1	1	0	0	0
(paper)	1	1	1	0.9	0.893	0.915	1	1	1	0	0	0
Model 3	0.137	0.119	0.165	0.903	0.119	1	0	0.286	0.143	0.955	0.714	0.835
(paper)	0.136	0.119	0.142	0.903	0.117	1	0	0	0	1	1	1
Model 4	1	0.359	1	0.145	0.898	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
(paper)	1	0.359	1	0.145	0.985	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Model 5	0.887	0.936	0.806	0.511	0.939	1	0.595	0.714	0.655	0.429	0.267	0.317
(Model)	0.894	0.936	0.947	0.511	0.950	1	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.268	0.183	0.225
Model 6	0.889	0.889	0.806	0.722	0.849	1	0.538	0.714	0.626	0.433	0.286	0.359
(paper)	0.884	0.889	0.947	0.722	0.874	1	0.819	0.357	0.588	0.290	0.643	0.466
Model 7	0.758	0.760	0.801	0.728	0.767	1	0.451	0.3	0.376	0.648	0.7	0.674
(paper)	0.763	0.760	0.797	0.728	0.720	1	0.688	0.357	0.523	0.485	0.643	0.564
Model 8	-											
Model 11	-											
Model 12	-											

Table 4: Results of running the different precision and generalization algorithms considered by the paper. For every model, the results I obtained are on top and the results shown in the paper are at the bottom.

mind that these results differ.

Now looking at table 6, the table is structured in the same way as table 5. G_a lines up perfectly, and even has the exact same generalization values as seen in the paper. G_t messes up the alignment for model 6, but is otherwise okay. This misalignment is acceptable though, as the only reason for this difference is that it has the same generalization value as model 1 and the generalization values for models 1 and 6 are pretty close in the paper as well. G_l differs quite a lot and as a result G differs a lot as well.

These differences are likely to occur due to a difference in the algorithm configuration, or perhaps there is a problem with its implementation in ProM, which would not be a huge leap as I've had a lot of trouble trying to get it to work. The worst offender is model 3, as I believe it matters quite much whether a model has a precision of 0 or more, or a generalization of 1 or less, even though it is ordered correctly, which is why I will try to find parameters such that the model has a precision of 0 and a generalization of 1. After trying to adjust every parameter I found that none of the parameters affected the results in any way. Thus I can only assume that the plugin contains a bug, some internal parameters have changed since the paper's publication or the algorithm has changed.

3.4 Interpreting the results

I was not able to sufficiently match my results to those from the paper, but I might still be able to draw some of the same conclusions. The paper starts out by discussing the precision and

Model	P_{ET}	P_{ETC}	P_a	P_{ne}	P_t	P_l	P
Model 1	0.992 4 4	0.994 5 5	0.946 3 4	0.994 5 6	0.69 0 4	0.714 2 2	0.702 1 4
(paper)	0.992 5 4	0.994 6 5	0.982 4 4	0.893 3 3	0.886 2 4	0.857 0 4	0.871 1 4
Model 2	1.0 1 5	1.0 1 6	1.0 1 5	0.915 0 4	1.0 1 5	1.0 1 5	1.0 1 5
(paper)	1.0 1 5	1.0 1 6	1.0 1 5	0.893 0 3	1.0 1 5	1.0 1 5	1.0 1 5
Model 3	0.137 3 0	0.119 1 0	0.165 5 0	0.119 1 0	0.0 0 0	0.286 6 0	0.143 4 0
(paper)	0.136 5 0	0.119 4 0	0.142 6 0	0.117 3 0	0.0 0 0	0.0 0 0	0.0 0 0
Model 4	1.0 2 5	0.359 0 1	1.0 2 5	0.898 1 3	1.0 2 5	1.0 2 5	1.0 2 5
(paper)	1.0 2 5	0.359 0 1	1.0 2 5	0.985 1 6	1.0 2 5	1.0 2 5	1.0 2 5
Model 5	0.887 4 2	0.936 5 4	0.806 3 2	0.939 6 5	0.595 0 3	0.714 2 2	0.655 1 3
(paper)	0.894 3 3	0.936 4 4	0.947 5 2	0.95 6 5	0.8 0 2	0.8 0 3	0.8 0 3
Model 6	0.889 5 3	0.889 5 3	0.806 3 2	0.849 4 2	0.538 0 2	0.714 2 2	0.626 1 2
(paper)	0.884 4 2	0.889 5 3	0.947 6 2	0.874 3 2	0.819 2 3	0.357 0 1	0.588 1 2
Model 7	0.758 3 1	0.76 4 2	0.801 6 1	0.767 5 1	0.451 2 1	0.3 0 1	0.376 1 1
(paper)	0.763 5 1	0.76 4 2	0.797 6 1	0.72 3 1	0.688 2 1	0.357 0 1	0.523 1 1

Table 5: Precision results with added positional information, the first number in each cell is the precision value, the second number is the position of the cell if you were to sort its row on precision, the third number is the position of the cell if you were to sort its column on precision (sorting from low to high). Sorting was done separately for my results and the results from the paper

generalization values of the models using the proposed algorithm. It is argued that model 1 has results as expected, since it has a fitness of 1, with a high precision, but low generalization as it only allows for one additional trace. My results are not entirely in line with this statement, it has quite a substantial lower precision and higher generalization. For a model that only allows one additional trace, $\langle A, C, G, H, D, F, I \rangle$, that doesn't differ a lot from one of the traces in the log, $\langle A, C, H, D, F, I \rangle$, I think a precision of 0.7 is quite low, compared to the precision of 0.871 reported in the paper. My generalization is also higher by almost a factor of 2, which I find quite substantial. For Models 2 and 4 the results are as expected, as they don't allow any traces not in the log and don't offer any generalizing behavior. While the results for model 3 make perfect sense in the paper, I find my results quite illogical, since it can't get more imprecise or general than the flower model, but my results imply there are more imprecise/less general models for this log. The paper also discusses its results for models 11 and 12, but as I wasn't able to obtain results for these models, I will not be able to discuss these models.

The paper then compares its results to the results of the other algorithms. It mostly compares its results for models 8, 11 and 12, for which I wasn't able to get results. Other than for these models, I might be able to draw some conclusions about the results for models 2 and 4. It argues that it's strange that the precision value P_{ETC} is so low for model 4, since the model doesn't allow any additional behavior and that their algorithm correctly captures this, which is true. However I wouldn't necessarily count this as an improvement over the state of the art, as the precision values of P_{ET} and P_a also captured this correctly. For model 2 it is argued that it should have a low generalization, which their algorithm captures. G_a however, grants a rather high generalization value to this model. The authors of the paper state that any model which allows for only one trace is immediately given a generalization value of 0. I find this to be a bit arbitrary and biased, as the log does in fact show strong evidence that the one trace allowed by model 2 is the correct trace.

Model	G_a	G_t	G_l	G
Model 1	0.585 3 2	0.433 2 3	0.286 0 3	0.359 1 3
(paper)	0.585 3 2	0.27 2 3	0.143 0 2	0.206 1 2
Model 2	0.9 3 5	0.0 0 0	0.0 0 0	0.0 0 0
(paper)	0.9 3 5	0.0 0 0	0.0 0 0	0.0 0 0
Model 3	0.903 2 6	0.955 3 6	0.714 0 6	0.835 1 6
(paper)	0.903 0 6	1.0 1 6	1.0 1 6	1.0 1 6
Model 4	0.145 3 0	0.0 0 0	0.0 0 0	0.0 0 0
(paper)	0.145 3 0	0.0 0 0	0.0 0 0	0.0 0 0
Model 5	0.511 3 1	0.429 2 2	0.267 0 2	0.317 1 2
(paper)	0.511 3 1	0.268 2 2	0.183 0 3	0.225 1 3
Model 6	0.722 3 3	0.433 2 3	0.286 0 3	0.359 1 3
(paper)	0.722 3 3	0.29 0 4	0.643 2 4	0.466 1 4
Model 7	0.728 3 4	0.648 0 5	0.7 2 5	0.674 1 5
(paper)	0.728 3 4	0.485 0 5	0.643 2 4	0.564 1 5

Table 6: Generalization results with added positional information, the first number in each cell is the generalization value, the second number is the position of the cell if you were to sort its row on generalization, the third number is the position of the cell if you were to sort its column on generalization (sorting from low to high). Sorting was done separately for my results and the results from the paper

Furthermore this implies that if we were to change model 2 such that it allows for one other non fitting trace, it would suddenly have a much higher generalization, which shouldn't be the case. Finally, the paper considers some models found in Buijs et al (2014)[5], which are shown in figure 7. For model 13 I ran into the same problems as for models 8, 11 and 12, so I wasn't able to get results for it. I did, however manage to get results for model 14, namely a precision of 0.667 and a generalization of 0.536. It is argued that their algorithm correctly identifies that the model has a low generalization and high precision, while my results show that they are neither really low or high, so I'm not able to draw the same conclusion about this model.

Figure 7: Models considered by the paper from Buijs et al. (2014)[5]

4 Conclusion

After multiple unsuccessful attempts at getting results using the plugin provided by the paper, I managed to get results for models 1 through 7, but failed to get results for models 7, 8, 11 and 13. This meant that I wasn't able to see whether my findings support the conclusions made during the discussion of these models. The discussion on the models I did manage to get results for, was fairly small and I mostly could not reach the same conclusions as in their discussion. This was because my results varied quite a lot from theirs, as can be seen in figure 4. Changing the algorithm's parameters did not seem to affect the precision and generalization values at all, and as such I was not able to bring my results closer to theirs. The authors of the paper attempted to improve the state of the art for precision and generalization measures, but I was not able to conclude whether they managed to accomplish this, due to the ProM plugin not working for almost half of the models and producing results that differ quite a lot from the results shown in the paper for the models that did work.

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2IMI00 - Replication Report

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1 Introduction

The article chosen for replication is "*Semi-Supervised Log Pattern Detection and Exploration Using Event Concurrency and Contextual Information* (Lu et al., 2017). The authors created a tool that enables unsupervised (automatic) pattern detection, as well as pattern detection based on the log. However, the tool is not empirically tested by domain experts yet, meaning it is not necessarily true that the results found by the authors can be easily reproduced. Besides this, the article was chosen for several reasons:

- The authors of this article created a tool, which is implemented as a ProM plug-in (*ProM Tools*, 2010). Therefore, the tool can actually be used.
- One of the two data sets used is easily accessible.
- The approach followed by the authors is clearly described.

The remainder of this report is structured as follows: section 2 describes the approach followed by the authors and therefore the approach followed in this report, section 3 describes the replication of the approach on the BPI 2012 challenge log and section 4 discusses all (if any) problems encountered and/or differences between the results of the paper and this replication report and provides a short conclusion.

2 Approach

The approach proposed by the authors is described below. Note that this is literally taken from the paper (Lu et al., 2017).

1. A-priori, a process model was discovered using an existing discovery algorithm (e.g. the Inductive Miner).
2. In the discovered model, unstructured parts may be detected (e.g. flower loops or activities with many or no connections). To understand these complex subprocesses and obtain more insights, the involved activities are used as a starting point for further analysis.
3. For each activity of interest, a first set of patterns (where the core-activity is labeled with the activity) is detected automatically, for instance, using the direct-context detector, to reveal different contexts (in the log) in which the activity occurs.
4. With each pattern detected, the corresponding pattern instances and pattern traces may be explored. A pattern is *interesting*, for example, if the pattern or the traces where the pattern occurred show behavior different from the discovered model.
5. During exploration, some detected patterns and their pattern traces may immediately show distinctive behaviors and be grouped together; other patterns and their traces may be compared and reveal significant difference in their behavior.
6. During exploration, the same pattern may occur in distinct contexts (other events "around" the pattern). In such a case, the pattern is extended or modified to new patterns. The pattern traces of the new patterns are compared to gain more insights.

It should be noted that the paper does not follow all of these steps. Step 6 is not followed as the authors didn't find any reason to extend one or more patterns manually.

3 BPI 2012 challenge log

The event log of the BPI 2012 challenge (Van Dongen, B.F. (Boudewijn), 2012) is a real-life event log, containing 13.087 cases and around 262.200 events. The data originates from a Dutch financial institute and the event log describes the process of applying for a personal loan or overdraft.

The approach described in section 2 is adhered to as strictly as possible. However, when choices and/or assumptions have to be made which are not clearly described in the approach or the paper, this will be discussed.

3.1 Steps 1 & 2

The first step of the approach is to investigate whether an existing discovery algorithm leads to a useful process model. Only if this algorithm would lead to a process model with unstructured parts, the tool can actually be used.

The paper states that the inductive visual miner using a noise threshold of 0.2 (i.e. the default settings), implemented in ProM (*ProM Tools*, 2010), was used to discover a process model. The replication of this step can be found in Figure 1. Two unstructured parts (or subprocesses as the paper calls them) are identified. The first unstructured part consists of the activities *W_Afhandelen leads*, *A_PREACCEPTED* and *W_Beoordelen fraude*. The second unstructured part consists of the activities *O_DECLINED*, *A_DECLINED*, *A_APPROVED*, *O_ACCEPTED*, *A_ACTIVATED*, *A_REGISTERED* and *W_Valideren aanvraag*.

The model shows similarities with the model discovered by the authors in the sense that the same two activities are always performed (*A_SUBMITTED* and *A_PARTLYSUBMITTED*), after which all activities are performed in a large loop, similar to a flower model. However, the structure of this large loop has some differences between the two models. These differences are listed below.

- The activity *A_DECLINED* is placed in another unstructured part. In the model of the paper, it is placed in the first unstructured block, while in the model of Figure 1 it is placed in the second unstructured block.
- The second unstructured block is placed much later in the model of Figure 1 than in the model of the paper.
- The activity *A_ACCEPTED* is not present in the model of the paper, but it is in the model of Figure 1, which is not expected.

3.2 Step 3

At this step, the paper decided to investigate the activities that are in an unstructured part right after the first two activities of the model. However, when following the same reasoning, this would mean that one less activity would be

Figure 1: Process model found by inductive miner

investigated as one activity (*A_DECLINED*) is placed in another unstructured part by the inductive miner (see section 3.1). It is decided to still include this activity in the analysis, as it seems quite interesting to investigate whether different and/or less patterns might be discovered when investigating this activity.

Concluding, the activities *A_DECLINED* (*A_DE*), *W_Afhandelen leads* (*W_Af*), *A_PREACCEPTED* (*A_PR*) and *W_Beoordelen fraude* (*W_Be*) will be investigated. Sections 3.2.1 to 3.2.3 describe the analyses.

3.2.1 A_DECLINED

Applying the direct context detector on the activity *A_DECLINED* returns 9 patterns. After comparison with the discovered patterns of the paper, it is concluded that the patterns are exactly the same. For convenience, the same pattern names are used here as in the paper (i.e. pattern P0 is the same in the paper and in this report).

The paper then groups the patterns in 3 variants. This can also be easily replicated, as the tool allows you to project the visualization of the log on a selected pattern. Below, it is discussed for each variant whether or not the same results are found.

- Variant 1: *A_PA* directly causes *A_DE*
 This variant contains both patterns P5 and P7. It is indeed the case that, when this pattern occurs, the process terminates immediately in all cases (so it doesn't occur in the middle of a large loop as suggested by the model of Figure 1). It is also confirmed that this indeed happens in 44.9% of all cases, via the P.conf statistic.
- Variant 2: *A_DE* occurs between repeated occurrences of the same activity (*W_Co*, *W_Af*, *W_Be*).
 This variant contains patterns P0, P2 and P3. When projecting the log on each of these patterns individually, it is confirmed that there is a repeated occurrence of the same activity, as the repeating activity is seen at least three times in each trace.
- Variant 3: *A_DE* occurs concurrently to *O_DE* with various predecessors and successors. Patterns P1, P6 and P8 are contained in this variant.

When investigating these patterns, again it is seen that the same observations can be made as in the paper. The traces related to these patterns are longer and more complex than the traces seen before.

Figure 2: Pattern P4 and the visualization on the log

After investigating all patterns, it is also concluded that the activity *A_DECLINED* does always occur at the end of the process, followed by only one other activity. The reason that it is still included in the large flower-model structure by the inductive miner is that the activity succeeding *A_DECLINED* varies quite a lot.

What is not mentioned in the paper is that one pattern is not placed in any of the variants. This is pattern P4, which is shown in Figure 2, along with the projection on the log. When looking at the visualization of the log, it seems that it is quite similar to the patterns of variant 2, where the activity *W_Co* is the repeating activity. The only difference is that, between *W_Co* and *A_DE* the activity *A_AC* occurs.

3.2.2 W_Afhandelen leads and A_PREACCEPTED

The first thing that is noted is that the number of found patterns mentioned in the paper and the number of patterns shown on the website containing the results are contradicting each other. For *W_Af*, the paper states that 40 patterns are found, while there are 41 patterns on the website. When identifying patterns in ProM, also 41 patterns are found. For *A_PR* the paper states that 9 patterns are found, while there are 11 patterns on the website. When identifying patterns in ProM, 9 patterns are found, meaning that it is impossible to reproduce two patterns shown on the website following the approach described by the paper.

The two patterns discussed in the paper, which have the same context, are that both activities are preceded by the activity *A_PARTLYSUBMITTED*. However, both of these patterns are not found by the tool, as is suggested in the paper. It might be possible that the authors meant that they noted context by looking at the different patterns, as there are several patterns where this context is present. It is also a good way to investigate whether creating and extending patterns manually is (easily) possible.

The first thing to do is to create two patterns manually: one where *A_PREACCEPTED* is directly followed by *W_Afhandelen leads* and one where it is directly followed by *A_PREACCEPTED*. The created patterns can be seen in Figure 3 (a) and (b). Then, both patterns are extended so that the activity *A_DECLINED* is eventually followed by the other two activities. The resulting patterns are shown in Figure 3 (c) and (d).

The paper then states that for both patterns (a) and (b), it is found upon visual inspection that *A_DECLINED* occurs more often for pattern (a) than for pattern (b). It is investigated whether this is actually true by collecting the C-supp statistic for all patterns, after which the ratio between the extended pattern and the original pattern is calculated (i.e. the fraction of the original pattern that also fits the extended pattern). Table 1 shows the values found for the C-support statistics for the patterns, as well as the fractions.

Pattern	C-support	Fraction
(a)	4739	-
(b)	4852	0.6759
(c)	3203	-
(d)	942	0.1941

Table 1: C-support statistics

3.2.3 W_Beoordelen fraude

First of all, it is stated in the paper that 34 patterns are found. When replicating this step, 33 patterns are found. On the website containing the results,

Figure 3: Manually created patterns

only 11 patterns are shown for unknown reasons.

Then it is stated that one pattern stands out (W_Be preceded by A_PA), while this pattern is not found during replication. Assuming the same happened here as described in the previous section, this pattern is created manually. However, it is then impossible to reach the same result as the paper, where findings are discussed related to the outcomes of the application depending on the context in which the activity W_Be occurs. It is however impossible to find the approach followed by the authors. As it is also unclear how the tool can be used to get these kind of outcomes, it is impossible to give any meaningful information in this section.

The analysis of the paper concludes with applying the concurrent detector on the activity O_AC , as the model found by the inductive miner states that this activity and the activities A_ACT , A_AP and A_RE can be executed in parallel or skipped. The result of the paper is exactly the same as the result of the replication, namely that the activities occur concurrently in all instances, which are 2243 cases. The 3 anti-pattern instances mentioned, where O_AC was not executed while it should have been, can also be easily identified.

4 Discussion and Conclusion

Generally speaking, the approach followed by the paper is documented quite good. Nevertheless, some differences were observed and in this section an attempt is made to explain these differences.

The first difference was noted when discovering a process model using the inductive miner, where the discovered processes showed some differences (see section 3.1). These differences are probably the consequence of changes to the algorithm of the inductive miner. The impact on the topic of the paper is very small, as the approach states that any algorithm to discover a process model can be used.

Also, at some points a different number of patterns were discovered in comparison to the paper. There are two possible reasons for this: the implementation of the direct context detector could have been changed or there might have been a counting error, meaning a different number was reported than the amount of patterns that were found. As there is no way to know what is the cause of these differences, it would simply be guessing to state what is the reason for this. However, as it seems quite hard to imagine that the authors miscounted multiple times, it seems to make most sense that the algorithm of the tool has changed (although there could also be other reasons that are not discussed here).

As a final remark regarding the reproducibility, only for the analysis of the activities *W_Afhandelen leads* and *A_PREACCEPTED* was not found to be reproducible. However, since the remaining results were reproduced quite easily, the reproducibility of the paper can be considered as quite good.

Issues with the tool

Some final remarks are made with regards to the usage of the tool, which is not related to the results of the analysis but might be of interest for the authors of the paper.

The first remark is that the manual creation and extension of patterns now has to be done via defining edges via a free-text box. Although this is not very difficult, especially considering that the intended users of the tool should be familiar with basic node and edge definitions, some guidance would be good. It is very well possible that users make a small typo which might result in not being able to create a pattern. This could for example be done by designing some kind of interface where adding a node or edge can be done by simply choosing an activity from a drop-down menu.

Furthermore, it is not possible to change the number of characters visualized after one has chosen to focus on a pattern. Also, it is not possible to return to a state where the whole log is visualized without focusing on a pattern, while

identified patterns are kept. This has a negative impact on usability.

At some point in time, ProM ran into some kind of bug which is related to the GraphViz package that is used to visually draw the patterns. However, it was very difficult to get to know this as the tool did not provide any kind of error message (which other plug-ins do provide). It might therefore be a good idea to make sure the tool can provide such error messages.

The last thing that was found is that the export functions of the patterns didn't seem to work. During the replication it was never possible to export the patterns as an image. This obviously does not have an impact on the results of the analysis, but it is inconvenient for the users of the tool who want to report interesting patterns that were found.

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A dark blue vertical bar is on the left side of the slide. A blue arrow points from the right side of this bar towards the title text.

Seminar architecture of information systems

2IMI00 Experiment Replication

“Semi-supervised Log Pattern Detection
and Exploration Using Event Concurrence
and Contextual Information”

Several thin, curved lines in shades of blue and grey originate from the bottom left and curve upwards and to the right.

Ioannis Vagionitis

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1. Introduction

Replicating an article can be a serious challenge. Not all articles are well written and in many cases there are not mentioned important aspects that are crucial in order to reproduce them. The following line are going to describe an article related with pattern identification in a semi-supervised way. There is also a tool, which supports this approach and it is included in ProM 6.8. The described article is "Semi-supervised Log Pattern Detection and Exploration Using Event Concurrence and Contextual Information" and was published in 2017 from Springer.

2. Content Information

The following text is going to describe the process for replicating the experiment made in a scientific article. The article introduces some definitions related with pattern that can be identified in an event log. Presents a new algorithm that can identify and present the pattern with many related measurements such as support and confidence. In the article, there are detailed instructions for replicating and reaching to identify the patterns by using the new tool Log Pattern Explorer (LPE).

There is a comparison made with existing tools/techniques for their functionality and the results that can be mined. Unfortunately, there are no clear instructions for the settings used to make the comparison. Also, there are presented 11 similar researches but the evaluation was made only on four for them which had the same characteristic of unsupervised pattern detection.

During the process of replicating, there are followed all the described steps for the LPE. From the evaluation of the paper there are used only three of the four pattern detection approaches and there is a discussion for each that compares them with the LPE. Finally in the article it is discussed another log which there are not provided any references to find it and uses it.

3. Replication and Findings

3.1. Model Discovery

Using the log with the batch plug-in of “Mine with Inductive visual Miner” in Prom 6.8 and the default settings the suggested model is very similar with the one presented in the paper but has very important differences. One of the parts that made different the model is the part that after A_SU and A_PA there is a path that skip all the rest activities. There are identified 24 activities in the model and from these the 7 are together in a flower structure and expect the A_SU and A_PA all the rest are included in a loop structure. The model is available in the first [Appendix](#). One of the interesting parts of the discovered model is that A_FI can occur only if O_SE is included in the log according to the model.

Because the model is different from the one discuss in the article if the same log run the same algorithm in a different version of Prom like 6.7 or Lite 1.2 the model is exactly the same which probably occurs because of a change in the algorithm between versions. For this reason, only the second model is going to be used to identify pattern behavior that does not fit in it.

3.2. Log Pattern Explorer

After loading the .xes file of BPI 2012 in ProM it is needed to switch the view of the visualizer. The first impression is shown in the Figure 1. It is possible to automatically set the colors for the activities and makes it easy to select the one of your interested to perform the LPE. According to the paper there are focus on 5 activities to perform the LPE (in the article it is initial mentions that there are selected only four but there are presented results for five.

Figure 1 LPE default view

The first investigated activity is A_DECLINED (A_DE). LPE presents nine patterns for this activity from the direct-context detector and from them four of them deviate from the model. In Figure 2 the patterns are presented and each one includes on activity that does not exist in the model. Seven of the pattern to occur use the flower loop of the model except from the 2 pattern that A_DE is directly preceded from A_PARTLYSUBMITTED (A_PA). Another observation that applies for all of the patterns is that after one of them is included in a trace the trace ends afterwards.

Figure 2 A_DE patterns no fit to model

Next step is to apply the LPE direct-context to W_Afhandelen leads (W_Af) and A_PREACCEPTED (A_PR). There are identified forty-nine patterns in total. Almost all patterns related with W_Af is very hard to see them in the discovered model. In addition, W_Af is an activity with three instances in the process because it has a lifecycle (SCHEDULE, START, COMPLETE). LPE can identify in the preview for the activity its state but it is not mentioned in the pattern which activity is at each position an example for it is in Figure 3. Only, nice of the patterns are related with A_PR and these can be splitted

Figure 3 W_Af pattern

example for it is in Figure 3. Only, nice of the patterns are related with A_PR and these can be splitted

in 2 categories which share the same characteristics. In Figure 4 there are 5 of the patterns, the first one with A_PA, A_PR and W_Co is included is all the rest can be difined as a base pattern for the rest. All of them fit in the model but it is imposible to identify them. The rest four patterns share the similar structure.

Figure 4 A_PR five patterns with A_PA, A_PR & W_Co

Next step applying the same to W_Beoordelen Fraude (W_Be) there are identified 32 patterns and like the W_Af, in the patterns it is not possible to see to which state of the lifecycle is referring.

Final step with LPE is to use the concurrent detector on the four activities A_ACTIVATED (A_ACT), A_APPROVED (A_AP), A_REGISTERED (A_RE) and O_ACCEPTED (O_AC). There are presented three pattern and one of those does not include one of the activities. The Figure in the [Appendix](#) show the attributes for each pattern. Only one make the difference that does not include the O_AC in three traces.

After finishing these steps described in the article and reviewing it there are some results different. On the W_Be the describe pattern was not identified from the LPE and it was not possible to reach the describe assumptions. In addition, there are many situation that I was not in a position to make the same analysis as it is made in the article for example the one of the case that O_AC was missing from the three traces. Finally, I did not manage to do the visual inspection related with W_Af and A_PR as it was described.

3.3. Unsupervised Pattern Detection

Last part of the article tries to identify the same pattern with four unsupervised techniques. In the following paragraphs it is going to be described the same thing only for the three techniques (Pattern abstraction, Episodes miner, Local model). In the article there are three types of answers used by in the replication are going to be used only two of them either identified (✓) either not (✗).

Table 1 pattern with other techniques

	P0	P1	P3	P9a	P9b	P12	P12(anti)
Pattern Abstraction	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
Episode Miner	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗
Local Patterns	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Log Pattern Explorer	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

During the execution of the algorithms, many times ProM overloaded and did not manage to project results. The most challenging was the mine for local process models. It manages to identify many model that is possible to “translate” as patterns but probably of my lack using this tool, I never managed to mine the ones the article was targeting. Except from Episode miner, the other tools do

not provide a way to pick the activities of interest and search only for them. The article did not provide the used settings for finding the patterns with the other techniques. In addition, none of them managed to handle concurrency and providing the anti-pattern for a pattern. Only pattern abstraction provide the P12 in a form that it does not define clearly that there is a concurrency.

All identified patterns from other tools have been included in the [Appendix](#).

4. Conclusions

After the process of reading and redoing the same steps, it is possible to state that not all step are clear enough to do them again. Starting from the different model to the tool from the local model technique that did not return results, which could be related with the ones in the article, end up to be very time consuming.

In general, the process helped a lot to understand the different functionalities provided from different tools that have similar target results but follow different paths to achieve them.

5. Appendix

Figure 5 LPE Concurrent Detector

Frequency: 0.143
Graph size: 6

Figure 11 P9a Episode Miner

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Paper replication

From original paper: Enabling Process Mining on Sensor
Data from Smart Products

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1 Introduction

The purpose of this document is to replicate the paper "Enabling Process Mining on Sensor Data from Smart Products". For this purpose, the methodology followed in the paper has been studied and an attempt has been made to replicate it as accurately as possible.

The document addresses the challenge of applying process mining to discover patterns of human behavior based on sensor data. The original study also poses the scenario of applying these new extracted knowledge to make improvements in future iterations the product prototype, which is under development.

The use case of the original paper consists of an intelligent baby bottle created by the Philips company. Because both this product and the original data are property of Philips, they are not available for us. For this, in this document we will also address a reduced replica of the product.

2 The product

As discussed above, the original paper is based on the information generated by a product. It is an intelligent baby bottle created by the Philips company. This intelligent baby bottle contains several sensors (mainly a temperature sensor and several accelerometers). However, this prototype is not accessible to the public. Therefore, to replicate this paper it has been decided to recreate a similar use case.

The experiment has consisted of trying to implement a similar product. Since we do not have an authentic baby, it has been decided to replace both the baby and the baby bottle with an adult human being and a bottle of water. The idea of the original paper is to detect patterns of behavior from sensor data, so we firmly believe that these changes are fully valid.

Today's smartphones contain several sensors that can be used to recreate this experiment. The main sensors used in the original idea are a 3-axis accelerometer (x, y, z) and a temperature sensor. To simplify the process and since there is no easy way to place a thermometer inside the bottle, it has been decided to omit this sensor, and only use the three-axis accelerometer.

For the creation of our "smart water bottle" it is enough to attach a smartphone to a bottle of water using tape. Although a priori it may seem an unserious solution, we must remember that the objective is to obtain the sensor data, so that the appearance of the device goes to the background.

For the collection of data, an iPhone SE and an application called "Gyro" have been used, which allows us to record the data of several sensors for later extraction and analysis.

Figure 2.1: A screenshot of Gyro

3 Dataset

This chapter deals with everything related to obtaining and processing the data obtained from our smart bottle.

3.1 Obtaining the data

Once we have our smart bottle recording the sensor data and fully filled with water, we have proceeded to use the bottle in a normal way during a meal. The bottle has been used until its contents have been emptied completely.

Afterwards, the saved data has been extracted and "Plotly", a Python library, has been used to create graphics quickly and visually.

In total, 7421 traces have been obtained, recorded at a frequency of 30Hz, so that there are 4 minutes and 7 seconds of data, enough to recreate the experiment.

The structure of the dataset, as well as the graphs of the data, can be seen below.

Figure 3.1: Dataset structure


```
export.csv
1 Time, Acceleration (X), Acceleration (Y), Acceleration (Z)
2 1546869394.89918,0.903762817382812,-0.20660400390625,-0.399566650390625
3 1546869394.93196,0.935867309570312,-0.197067260742188,-0.397964477539062
4 1546869394.96495,0.91839599609375,-0.218856811523438,-0.386703491210938
5 1546869394.99833,0.90142822265625,-0.232894897460938,-0.3857421875
6 1546869395.03239,0.900283813476562,-0.208480834960938,-0.38494873046875
```

Figure 3.2: Three axis data from the sensors

As we can see, the X and Y axes follow the same pattern, while the Z axis is confusing. This is due to the relative position of the phone with respect to the bottle, and it is completely normal. Given that this axis will not provide us with useful information and since the X and Y axis are very similar, we will use the Y axis data to replicate the experiment, because we believe contains the more cleaner data.

3.2 Processing the data

To convert the raw data of the sensors into event logs, the paper proposes a technique called "Sensor Data Segmentation". To transform this information into events, the technique consists in segmenting time series data into small windows. These windows are then labeled. Similar windows will receive the same label. These labels will be labeled according to the change-point detection.

Figure 3.3: Figure from the original paper: "Segmented and labelled sensor data. Each segment is labelled based on the properties of the sensor measurements it contains, e.g. a stable high sensor signal is labelled with "A". Change-points in the sensor data result in adjacent segments having different labels."

Now it is time to choose our window size. The original paper explains that there is no concrete technique to choose this size, but the trial and error. For this reason and based on several tests, we have decided to choose a window size of 15 units of time, which would be equivalent to half a second. In the following figures you can see how the data is with different time windows.

Figure 3.4: Graph that shows the result of the data with a window of 3 units of time. As can be seen, noise is hardly eliminated from the graph, so it is an insufficient size.

Figure 3.5: Graph that shows the result of the data with a window of 130 units of time. As can be seen, the size of the window is excessive and there is a lot of information loss.

Figure 3.6: Graph that shows the result of the data with a window of 15 units of time. As can be seen, the size of the window is enough to be able to distinguish all the activities.

4 Creating the event log

If we observe our data generated by our bottle, we see that a preprocessing of the data is necessary. The first thing we see is that the value of the base of the graph is around minus 1, with slight peaks below this number. To make the creation of the windows as effective as possible, we eliminate these peaks below minus 1, equaling all these values to minus 1. Since the concrete value of the sensor does not interest us, we will also add +1 to all the data of the sensor. With this, it will be easier to work with the data because these are only positive values.

At this point it is necessary to set a scenario that a priori is very obvious, but which is necessary to understand how the graph is interpreted. The process of drinking water consists of lifting the bottle and placing it in the mouth to drink. When we drink water we tip the bottle. At the beginning, when the bottle is completely filled, the inclination is smaller, and after drink more and more water, the inclination grows. This can be clearly seen in the graph. The first peaks are greater than the last ones. In addition, while drinking the water, the inclination remains constant, which can also be easily seen in the graph.

Once we have understood how the user's behavior is reflected in the graphics (what in the original paper refers to as calling the domain expert) we simply construct a basic algorithm that automates this process. It is about automatically detecting changing points.

Be A moment of time in the graph. Let B be the instant in $t + 1$ in time:

```
if  $A < B$  then
    The slope is ascending
else if  $A > B$  then
    The slope is descending
else if  $A == B$  then
    if  $A > 0$  then
        Stable, but drinking water
    else if  $A < 0$  then
        Stable on the table
```

Python and Jupyter have been used to implement this algorithm. The source code can be found below:

```
1 p = 0.001
2 for v in new:
3     if (v==0):
4         v = 0.001
5
6     f = p*100/v
7
8     if (f<th):
9         #increasing
10        #print("U")
11        log.append("U")
12    elif ((f>th)&(f<100)|(p==v)):
13        #equal
14        if (v>0.01):
15            #print("E")
16            log.append("X")
17        else:
18            log.append("_")
19    elif (f>100):
20        #decreasing
21        #print("D")
```

```
22     log . append ("D")  
23     p = v
```


6 Conclusions

Process mining is a very powerful and still developing technique that can be used in many sectors. This paper makes clear that it is also possible to use process mining to detect patterns of behavior and activities in devices.

Through this document we have tried to replicate, in a homemade but effective way, this paper. We were able to obtain real data of a real use of an object, in our case a bottle of water, and extract the activities and sub-activities along the little more than four minutes of data collected by the sensors.

As the original paper mentions, there is still much to explore in the field of process mining and sensors. From a personal point of view, I have found the solution proposed in the paper ingenious and I look forward to how this field will continue to be developed in future work.

EINDHOVEN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

SEMINAR ARCHITECTURE OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS -
2IMI00

Replication Report

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3 February 2019

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1 Introduction

This report aims to study a paper¹ how the most important keywords of a single document are extracted. The authors have concluded that their approach outperforms the similar unsupervised approaches. To the best of my knowledge, the proposed method is novel as it benefits from a combination of features without being dependent on an external source or on linguistic tools (POS Tagger² or Named Entity Recognizer³) or sources such as Wordnet⁴.

The authors have provided an online platform and an API to be used by other researchers. **But as I am passionate about NLP, I decided to re-code the steps of this approach to gain a better understanding of the efficiency of this method and how it works in practice.** Then, the comparison between the keywords obtained from my implementation and the ones from the online platform of the proposed approach indicate the same results and conclusions as provided in the paper. As a result, **re-coding the proposed method directed me to select this approach with confidence to apply it to the preprocessing step of my Master Thesis.**

In the following section, this keyword extraction method is briefly explained. Then, the evaluation results are presented and analyzed.

2 Keyword Extraction Algorithms

In this section, the definition of keyword, different types of keyword extraction methods, and the typical steps in these algorithms are provided.

Keywords are the terms that represent the most relevant information or the topics discussed in a document. When a user is working with textual data, having access to keywords can assist him/her in different ways. For instance, if the user intend to read a text, keywords can help him/her to decide quickly whether the text is worth reading. The web programmers may benefit from keywords to easily group the *similar content*.

The task of keyword extraction is one of the broad and current interests in Natural Language Processing (NLP) application areas: Text Summarization, Text Classification, Text Mining, Information Extraction, and etc. The proposed methods for automatic keyword extraction can be divided in two categories: supervised (such as KEA[1]) and unsupervised (such as Rake[2], TextRank[3], and SingleRank[4]). The Unsupervised methods are mostly based on linguistics, statistics, construction of a graph or a combination of these

¹https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-76941-7_63

²<https://nlp.stanford.edu/software/tagger.shtml>

³<https://nlp.stanford.edu/software/CRF-NER.shtml>

⁴<https://wordnet.princeton.edu/>

methods.

A typical keyword extraction algorithm has three main components[5]:

- *Candidate selection:* All possible words, phrases, terms or concepts that can potentially be keywords are kept and the remaining parts are eliminated from the text(s).
- *Properties calculation:* For each candidate, some properties are calculated to determine whether a word is a keyword. For instance, a candidate appearing in the title of a book is a likely keyword.
- *Scoring and selecting keywords:* All candidates are scored by either combining the properties into a formula, or applying a machine learning technique to determine the probability of a candidate being a keyword. Based on a score or probability threshold or a limit on the number of keywords, the final set of keywords are selected.

3 The Proposed Approach Implementation

The paper presents an unsupervised method to extract keywords (containing one, two, or three terms) from a document based on a combination of five text statistical features independent of any external sources or linguistic tools.

According to section 2 of the paper, there are four main steps:

- Text preprocessing
- Feature extraction
- Individual term weighting
- Candidate keywords generation

In the following, the core idea of the above-mentioned steps that I followed to implement the method from scratch are described.

3.1 Text preprocessing

First, a tokenization process is applied to the text in order to identify the sentences and the words. Then each sentence is changed into a bag of words.

Example: *"Cycling, also called bicycling or biking, is the use of bicycles for transport, recreation, exercise or sport."*

Result (bag of words): 'Cycling', 'also', 'called', 'bicycling', 'or', 'biking', 'is', 'the', 'use', 'of', 'bicycles', 'for', 'transport', 'recreation', 'exercise', 'or', 'sport'

3.2 Feature extraction

In this phase, the following features are defined under the assumption that they can better identify the words which are more relevant to the topic discussed in the input text. For the formulas and more details, it is recommended to check section 2.2 in the paper:

- Casing (W_{case}): This feature computes a score for any candidate word starting with a capital letter (excluding ones at the beginning of sentences) or to any acronym (all letters of the word are capital).
- Word position ($W_{position}$): A candidate word may occur in one or more sentences in a text. Therefore the position of these sentences in a text can be considered as an important feature. For instance, in scientific papers, most of the relevant keywords may occur at the early parts of the documents. Hence, these words will receive less scores for this feature.
- Word frequency (W_{freq}): This feature is based on a belief that important words mostly have higher frequencies. Therefore, a candidate word with higher frequency will be assigned higher score of this feature. But to prevent a bias caused by words with high frequency in long documents, this score is divided by the mean of the frequencies (MeanTF).
- Word relatedness to context (W_{rel}): This feature identifies to what extent a candidate word can be assumed as a stop word. To compute this score, two windows of size n to the left and right sides of the candidate word are considered. Hence, the number of different words that co-occur with the candidate word on both sides, define how unimportant the candidate word is. The insignificant candidate word will receive higher score of this feature.
- Word DifSentence ($W_{DifSentence}$): This feature quantifies how often a candidate word appears within different sentences.

3.3 Individual term weighting

After calculating the scores of the above-mentioned features for the words, all these feature scores are combined heuristically to form a single score ($S(w)$) for each candidate word. The smaller value of $S(w)$ defines that the word is more important.

3.4 Candidate keywords generation:

A keyword is not always one word and it may consist of more than one word. Therefore, as the final phase, a sliding window and the $S(w)$ scores of the words are utilized to generate one-, two- and three-term keywords while being assigned a new score, $S(kw)$. It is important to note that, two- and three-term keywords beginning or ending with a stopword will not be included in the list of final keywords. Each candidate keyword with smaller value of $S(kw)$ is assumed as one of the significant keywords.

4 Evaluation

The authors have employed four different datasets to retrieve keywords with a maximum size of three. The characteristics of these datasets are summarized in Table 1. Moreover, a predefined list of stopwords is utilized to remove the words which has no domain specific meaning such as articles or determiners. The proposed approach (YAKE!) is compared with three unsupervised keywords extraction methods: *TextRank*, *RAKE*, and *SingleRank*. Moreover, YAKE! has been compared with *TF.IDF* which requires more than one document as an input. Finally, based on *precision*, *recall* and *F1-measure*, the authors concluded that their proposed method, YAKE!, outperforms the other methods.

Dataset	Topic	No. of documents	Average No. of tokens per document	Language
<i>SemEval2010</i>	ACM papers	244	8020	English
<i>Schutz2008</i>	Medical papers	1231	-	English
<i>500N-KPCrowd</i>	News	500	393	English
<i>WICC</i>	Computer papers	1640	-	Spanish

Table 1: The characteristics of the dataset

Data Preparation: The first step to replicate the evaluation is to prepare the dataset. Since the size of the dataset utilized in the paper is huge, I looked for the availability of the first three datasets in Table 1 which are in English. Finally, I succeeded in downloading and selecting 50 documents from SemEval2010-Task5 [6]. SemEval (Semantic Evaluation) is an ongoing series of evaluations of computational semantic analysis systems [7]. SemEval2010 included 18 different tasks such as Co-reference resolution in multiple languages [8], all-words word sense disambiguation on a specific domain [9], Linking events and their participants in discourse [10], and etc. SemEval2010-Task5 was a workshop where systems were to automatically assign key phrases or keywords to the given scien-

tific articles. The dataset of this task can be downloaded from this link⁵.

Run the code: In the second step, the reduced dataset (collection of 50 documents) is inputted into the code I have implemented by following the steps in the paper. Afterwards, the same dataset is applied to the online platform of the proposed method⁶, TextRank, SingleRank⁷, and, RAKE⁸ (TF.IDF is not considered in the replication since it is a simple feature dependant on frequency of a word in a document). For instance, the above-mentioned implementations have extracted the following top 16 keywords from an arbitrary paper⁹.

My implementation: grid, computing, resource, node, application, performance, processor, cluster, run time, overhead, super computer, parallel computing, low latency, high bandwidth, application performance, weighted average efficiency

YAKE!: application, processors, nodes, grid, adaptation, performance, resources, vrije universiteit, universiteit amsterdam, weighted average efficiency, application performance, efficiency, resource selection, number, application performance, average efficiency

RAKE: vrije universiteit amsterdam, produce input files, function cluster, dashed lines, innovation program, european workshop, standard metric, useful work, causes small inaccuracies, reusable templates, distributed processing, perform, fault tolerant, fault detection, grid projects, property

TextRank: heterogeneous, application run, bottleneck, scenarios, network connections, grid, network links, application programmers, communication, efficiency, parallelism, implement, resources, computation, removed processors, standard metric

SingleRank: performance, connections, inter-cluster, computation, grid, overloaded resources, resources, crashed processors, communicating, parallel, application, metric, programmers, cluster, processor, efficiency

SemEval2010-Task5 contains the keywords for each document. Therefore, the retrieved keywords from the above methods are matched with the ones in SemEval2010-Task5 to

⁵<http://semeval2.fbk.eu/semeval2.php?location=data>

⁶<https://boiling-castle-88317.herokuapp.com/demo/user>

⁷Implementations of TextRank and SingleRank available at <http://www.hlt.utdallas.edu/~saidul/code.html>

⁸YAKE! online platform output the results for RAKE as well.

⁹<https://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=1229449>

calculate precision, recall, and F1 scores. These scores are presented in Table 2 without applying a paired sample t-test to the score values as it is performed in the paper. The original results from the paper are illustrated in Figure 1.

Method	SemEval2010			Schutz2008			500N-KPCrowd			WICC		
	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1
YAKE!	0.153	0.103	0.123	0.217	0.058	0.091	0.251	0.063	0.101	0.050	0.141	0.073
TextRank	0.101▼	0.067▼	0.081▼	0.198▼	0.052▼	0.082▼	0.265	0.063	0.103	0.018▼	0.058▼	0.027▼
TF.IDF	0.036▼	0.023▼	0.028▼	0.100▼	0.028▼	0.043▼	0.223▼	0.060▼	0.095▼	0.026▼	0.067▼	0.037▼
SingleRank	0.035▼	0.022▼	0.027▼	0.082▼	0.024▼	0.037▼	0.190▼	0.054▼	0.084▼	0.017▼	0.045▼	0.024▼
RAKE	0.007▼	0.004▼	0.005▼	0.013▼	0.004▼	0.006▼	0.120▼	0.038▼	0.058▼	0.004▼	0.012▼	0.006▼

Figure 1: The original results from the paper

Method	Precision	Recall	F1
<i>My_Implementation</i>	0.7184	0.7597	0.7385
<i>YAKE!</i>	0.7177	0.7581	0.7373
<i>RAKE</i>	0.4108	0.4325	0.4212
<i>TextRank</i>	0.6881	0.7389	0.7126
<i>SingleRank</i>	0.5031	0.5316	0.517

Table 2: The evaluation results from replication

As it is obvious in Table 2, the score results from *My Implementation* and *YAKE! online platform* are approximately similar. This indicates my implementation has achieved the same results the authors have obtained for SemEval2010 dataset. The main reason of this outcome owing to the well-defined steps in the paper. This supports the reader to fully comprehend how the algorithm functions and it may lead into a better development and collaboration of the method by other researchers. Finally, comparing to the peer methods, YAKE! and the implemented code achieve higher scores for precision, recall and F1.

5 Conclusion

The main motivation for selecting this paper was my NLP background. Moreover, the uniqueness of the proposed method and the clarity of implementation were the other factors to read this paper thoroughly. Finally, the dataset and other keyword extractor tools are available to be used for evaluation and comparing the results. Reading papers is not always simple and straightforward. A paper may present a novel idea but sometimes to follow how the method functions is not easy and effortless. Since, the proposed method is not dependant on any other linguistic resources such as Wordnet, which can raise the runtime, I was encouraged to implement the proposed method in Python by following

every single step provided in the paper. This helped me to fully understand how the algorithm works in details and be confident of the efficiency of the method. On the other hand, in NLP domain, adding or removing a component can improve the efficiency of a method. Implementing the proposed method provided me with the vision to think about how the algorithm can be improved. Finally, I have concluded that YAKE! is a novel method to extract keywords with high efficiency and low runtime to be used as a component in my Master Thesis.

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SEMINAR: ARCHITECTURE OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS
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Experiment/Evaluation Replication Report

COMPLETE AND INTERPRETABLE CONFORMANCE CHECKING OF BUSINESS PROCESSES

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January 27, 2019

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1 Introduction

This report aims to replicate the evaluation of the paper "*Complete and Interpretable Conformance Checking of Business Processes*" [1]. Luciano Garcia-Banuelo et.al. [1] have performed a three-step evaluation: qualitative, quantitative and user evaluation. In this report we are focused only in qualitative and quantitative evaluation, whereas the user evaluation is not replicated.

The research problem targeted by [1] consist of the following: (1) traditional trace alignment methods do not provide feedback in an easily interpretable way (the number of the produced aligned traces is often too large to be explored by professionals); (2) they identify differences at the level of individual traces rather than at the level of relational behavioral; (3) there is no method that can provide support for both unfitting and additional behavior (expect of hybrid methods that can be created by combining a technique for unfitting behavior with one for additional behavior). Therefore, Luciano Garcia-Banuelo et.al. [1] proposed a method called *behavioral alignment*, which having an event log and a process model is able to perform conformance checking, offering support for both unfitting and additional behavior as well as providing feedback in form of a set of statements in natural language, describing the behavior allowed by models but not observed in the log and vice versa.

The remaining of this report is organized as follows: **Section 2** describes the data sets and the tools used for the replication; **Section 3** and **Section 4** provide the detailed replication for qualitative and quantitative evaluation, respectively. Each of them describes the steps that are taken, the results, the comparison with the original evaluation and clearly identifies the deviations from the original evaluation and the corresponding consequences; **Section 5** shows the limitations and the conclusions of the replication.

2 Event logs, process models and tools used

The qualitative evaluation performed in [1], is based on a real-life event log and the corresponding process model: *Road Traffic Management Process*. This event log is publicly available; therefore, we have used the same event-log for the replication. It is available at: *4TU.Centre For Research Data*¹. The normative process model that is used is derived from the description of the business process in [2]. The Petri Net constructed for this model and used in this replication is given in [1].

The quantitative evaluation performed in [1], consist on evaluating the time performance and the number of produced difference statements. For completing it, two large collections of real-life process models are used: the *IBM Business Integration Technology (BIT)* library (735 models) [3] and the *SAP R/3 collection* (604 models) [4]. BIT collection is publicly-available and includes process models from financial services, telecommunication and other domains, whereas SAP collection includes the reference models used to customize SAP R/3 ERP product. After omitting models that were not Workflow net and sound, the collections size used for the original evaluation was 348 and 494 models, respectively. For the replication, only the *IBM BIT collection* is used, as it is publicly available².

The tools and corresponding plugins used for replicating the evaluation are listed below:

¹<https://data.4tu.nl/repository/uuid:270fd440-1057-4fb9-89a9-b699b47990f5>

²<http://apromore.cis.unimelb.edu.au>

- **Compare plugin for Apromore**³, an open-source tool for performing business process analytics. *Compare plugin*, is implemented by Luciano Garcia-Banuelo et.al. [1] to test the proposed method, *behavioral alignment*. This plugin takes a process model (BPMN) and an event log (XES) and provides a list of statements in natural language that describes the behaviour allowed by the model but not observed in the log and vice versa. We have used Compare plugin, to evaluate the *Behavioral Alignment* method.
- **ProConformance**⁴, a standalone Java tool that is implemented by Luciano Garcia-Banuelo et.al. [1] to apply behavioral alignment method. This tool takes a process model (PNML format) and an event log (MXML or XES format) and provides a list of statements in natural language that describes the behaviour allowed by the model but not observed in the log and vice versa. There are two versions of ProConformance available in *apromore.org*; the paper does not clearly state which version is used for the evaluation, but based on their description, *ProConformance 1.0* is used for evaluating the *Behavioral Alignment*. Therefore, we have used *ProConformance 1.0* for the replication.
- **WoPeD**⁵, to check that the input model was correctly formatted in the PNML format, based on the requirements for *ProConformance 1.0*.
- **ProM 6.8**, an open-source framework that supports a wide variety of process mining techniques. The ProM plugins that are used for replicating the evaluation are listed below. First their corresponding packages⁶ were installed using ProM PM 6.8.
 - **Convert BPMN diagram to Petri net (control-flow)** (D.Fahland). We have used this plugin to convert BPMN diagrams for both: "*Soundness checking*" and "*Conformance Checking*". For quantitative evaluation, as the public repository contains the real-life process models of IBM, we first need to convert these process models to Petri Net in order to check soundness and workflow net condition. [1] refers to the work of D. Fahland et. al. [3] for checking the soundness of the process models. Furthermore, [3] provides a source⁷ to find the IBM original process models as well as converted in different formats of Petri nets (including PNML), but unfortunately the link is not accessible anymore. Having the PNML files would be very helpful for the replication, as we could directly use them, without the need to first convert from BPMN to PNML. The second option of this plugin, "*Conformance Checking*", is used to convert the model into a Petri Net, that will be later used to generate the event logs. These are the event logs that we have used for conformance checking later on.
 - **Convert BPMN to Petri Net** (Raffaele Conforti). Although this plugin is not mentioned in the original evaluation, we have use it to verify the equivalence between the BPMN model that is designed and the original Petri Net, for the replication of the qualitative evaluation.
 - **Analyze with Woflan** (H.M.W.Verbeek). We have used this plugin to check if the process models from the real-life IBM collection satisfy the conditions of *Workflow* net and *soundness*. Only the models that satisfy these conditions, will be further used for replicationg the quantitative evaluation. As stated above, we have tested only the IBM BIT collection, that is publicly available.

³<http://apromore.org/>

⁴<http://apromore.org/platform/tools>

⁵<https://woped.dhbw-karlsruhe.de/>

⁶<https://svn.win.tue.nl/trac/prom/wiki/ProM68/Plugins>

⁷<http://www.servicetechnology.org/soundness>

Woflan is one of the plugins that is used in [3] (Petri Net modeler LoLA and a technique based on SESE decompositions are the other two methods used). As [1] refers to [3] for checking the soundness, we decided to use *Woflan*, even though it is not clearly stated in [1].

- **Generate event logs from Petri Net** (Seepe vanden Broucke). This plugin is used in the replication process to generate event logs from the process models (that are first converted into Petri Nets using *Convert BPMN diagram to Petri net (control-flow)* plugin with *Conformance Checking* parameter, as mentioned above). One strong point is that the parameters used for this plugin are pre-defined in [1]. One of the main difficulties we faced, was that this plugin was not part of *ProM PM 6.8* and therefore it should be installed separately. The authors in [1], refer to the technique used by [5], and we used the documentation provided here⁸, to install and make use of the plugin that is implemented in [5].
- **Add noise to log filter** (R.S.Mans). In [1] it is stated that noise is injected in each original event log (5%, 10%, 15%, 20%) in order to create random difference between the model and the log. They refer to a technique documented in [6], which consist on repeatedly adding or removing a random event that already exist in the original event log in a random position of a random selected trace, until the number of events equal a percentage of the total number of events in the original log. As we were not able to find a plugin implemented by [6], we decided to use *Add noise to log filter* plugin, as it offers the opportunity to choose the percentage of the removing and adding events. This deviation from the original evaluation may influence the replication results.
- **Replay a Log on Petri Net for All Optimal Alignments** (Arya Adriansyah). We have used this plugin to evaluate traditional Conformance Checking, in the same way used from the original evaluation. It finds all optimal alignments for each distinct trace in the log and the output is in the form of visual diagnostics and metric (0 to 1) for fitness.
- **Replay a Log on Petri Net for Conformance Analysis** (Arya Adriansyah). This is the second plugin we have used for evaluating trace alignment Conformance Checking. It differs from the one above, because it computes only one optimal alignment per distinct trace (an approximation of the output of *Replay a Log on Petri Net for All Optimal Alignments* plugin).

3 Reproducing the Qualitative evaluation

In this section the replication of the qualitative evaluation will be described. We have used the same real-life event log as the original study: *Road Traffic Management Process*, as it is publicly available⁹.

3.1 Steps taken

3.1.1 Obtain the event-log for *Road Traffic Management Process*

The event log has 150,370 traces comprising 231 distinct traces and a total of 561,470 events, the same statistics as in the original evaluation.

⁸<http://processmining.be/loggerator/>

⁹<https://data.4tu.nl/repository/uuid:270fd440-1057-4fb9-89a9-b699b47990f5>

Figure 1: Statistics for the Road Traffic Management Process event log

3.1.2 Construct the Petri Net and the BPMN.

Figure 2 shows the Petri Net constructed from the description of the business process in [2] and the net provided in [1]. We have constructed it using **CPN tools**¹⁰, and verified the .PNML format using **WoPeD**. The net also include some silent transitions, shown with the blue color (artifact of translation to BPMN). Figures 3 and 4 show the corresponding BPMN model that we have constructed. The BPMN model will be used in the coming steps to perform *Behavioral Alignment*, as *Compare plugin* of Apromore taked as input a BPMN process model.

Figure 2: Petri Net for the Road Traffic Management Process [1]

The business process, illustrated in Figure 2, is described as follows [1]: The fine can be paid by the offender right away, after a notification is sent to the offender by the police, or when the offender receives the notification. The payment itself can be done in one or more instalments, depending on the amount of the fine. The case is closed as soon as the payment for the full amount has been done. If the fine is not paid within 180 days, a penalty is charged on top of the fine and if after further 180 days the fine is still due, a credit collection organization will take over the handling of the case. At any time after receiving the notification,

¹⁰<http://cpntools.org/>

the offender can appeal against the fine through a judge or a prefecture. In case of a successful appeal, the case is dismissed and the process ends. If the appeal is unsuccessful, the fine is still to be paid. An appeal can be made more than once, depending on the circumstances (e.g., when escalating the appeal to a higher court).

Figure 3: The BPMN model (Apromore) for the Road Traffic Management Process

Figure 4: The BPMN model (Prom) for the Road Traffic Management Process

3.1.3 Perform Conformance Checking using trace alignment in ProM

To perform conformance checking with trace alignment in ProM, two plugins are suggested by the original evaluation: *Replay a Log on Petri Net for All Optimal Alignments* and *Replay a Log on Petri Net for Conformance Analysis*. In the original evaluation it is mentioned that the log is compared with the Petri Net in figure 2; hence, we have applied the same for the replication.

Both plugins *Replay a Log on Petri Net for All Optimal Alignments* and *Replay a Log on Petri Net for Conformance Analysis* take as input the Petri Net in Figure 2 and the event log in Figure 1. The plugins are used with the same parameters defined in the original evaluation, as follows:

- **Replay a Log on Petri Net for All Optimal Alignments:** graph-based state space replay to obtain all optimal alignments with maximum explored states equal to 10,001,000

- **Replay a Log on Petri Net for Conformance Analysis:** Parameters used: A cost-based fitness express with ILP with maximum explored states equal to 10,001,000.

3.1.4 Perform Conformance Checking using behavioral alignment in Apromore and ProConformance.

Using Compare plugin for Apromore.

To perform conformance checking with behavioral alignment in Apromore, the original evaluation [1] suggests using *Compare* plugin. This plugin takes as input process model in BPMN format (Figure 3) and the event log in Figure 1. To ensure that the BPMN model that we designed is equivalent with the provided Petri Net, we also applied the ProM plugin *Convert BPMN to Petri Net*, as shown in Figure 5. Comparing Figure 5 with Figure 2, we concluded that the BPMN model we have designed, completely and correctly represents Petri Net in Figure 2. Figure 6 shows how *Compare* plugin can be used in Apromore.

Figure 5: Applying *Convert BPMN to Petri Net* plugin, to verify the BPMN model we designed and the provided normative Petri Net are equivalent.

Figure 6: Using Compare plugin in Apromore

Using ProConformance standalone Java tool.

To evaluate behavioral alignment the authors of [1] have also implemented a standalone Java tool called ProConformance. The source link ¹¹ provided in [1] contains to different version of the the tool; after exploring them we concluded that [1] has made use of *ProConformance 1.0*. According to the description of the tool in the *ReadMe* file, it takes as input a process model in PNML format and an event log in either MXML or XES format and produces the set of differences between the model and the log and vice versa as a set of natural language statements.

¹¹<http://apromore.org/platform/tools>

The tool can be used from CMD in Windows as follows:

```
java -jar ProConformance.jar [folder] [pnmlfile] [logfile] [outputfile] [silentsfile]
```

where:

[folder]: Folder where all input files are located and where the output file will be created.

[pnmlfile]: Process model including extension (.pnml).

[logfile]: Event log including extension (either .mxml or .xes).

[outputfile]: Output file containing control-flow differences.

[silentsfile]: (optional) Text file containing a list of silent transitions in the model that should not be labelled.

Each silent transition should be on a new line in the file.


```
C:\Users\user\Desktop\ProConformance1>java -jar ProConformance.jar Final_road_traffic_final.pnml Road_Traffic_Final.xes output.txt
C:\Users\user\Desktop\ProConformance1>
```

Figure 7: Evidence that ProConformance 1.0 tool, does not create the expected output file

The tool worked well with the provided example files (ensuring in this way that the environment is set up correctly), but when tried with .PNML and .XES file of the Road Traffic Management Process, it did not create the output file that should contain the set of detected differences. As recommended we tested the .PNML file using *WoPeD*, to ensure that it is correctly formatted. Despite this fact, the tool still did not create the expected output file. Furthermore, the authors of [1] were contacted for this problem but we didn't get any suggestion from them on this issue, within an appropriate time for this report. Moreover, they clearly stated that the algorithm in the standalone tool is not the latest one and they have heavily improved it as a plugin of *Apromore* and that version is being maintained. **This is the reason that for replicating this evaluation only the *Compare* plugin from *Apromore* is used.**

3.2 Replication results

3.2.1 Conformance Checking with Trace Alignment in ProM.

Figure 8, illustrates the result obtained by *Replay a Log on Petri Net for All Optimal Alignments* plugin using *Project Alignment to Log (PNet Replayer)* visualization. This plugin find all optimal alignment for each distinct trace in the log. Despite being able to see the exact order in which synchronous (also silent) moves on the model and log occur, we can also interact with each detected alignment/misalignment by hovering on them and see the label of the events and type of move (see Figure 9).

Figure 8: *Replay a Log on Petri Net for All Optimal Alignments* plugin, using *Project Alignment to Log (PNet Replayer)* visualization

Figure 9: *Replay a Log on Petri Net for All Optimal Alignments* plugin, different types of moves (synchronous, log, model, silent, moves) that can be detected for each alignment

Figure 10, illustrates the result obtained by *Replay a Log on Petri Net for Conformance Checking* plugin using *Model Project with Alignment (PNet Alignment Analysis)* visualization. This plugin find one optimal alignment for each distinct trace in the log. Figure 10 shows the projection of the alignments in the Petri Net that is used as input for the plugin (shown in Figure 2). Furthermore, Figure 11 gives some insights in interpreting this visualization:

- Paths with a darker color are more frequent (based on the log). For instance, the path: *Create Fine, Insert Fine, Send Fine, Add Penalty, Payment, end* is one of the most frequent paths.
- Red borders means that these model tasks are often skipped. For instance: *Insert Date Appeal to Prefecture, Send Appeal to Prefecture, Receive Result Appeal from Prefecture, Notify Result Appeal to Offender* tasks.
- There is a color bar for each task, that shows the ratio between the *Synchronous moves* and *Model moves*. For instance, for task *Payment* there are 71919 synchronous moves and 20520 model moves (see Figure 11).

Figure 10: *Replay a Log on Petri Net for Conformance Checking, using Model Project with Alignment (PNet Alignment Analysis) visualization*

Figure 11: *Replay a Log on Petri Net for Conformance Checking, Info, Filter, Display options*

To conclude, both these plugins can be used to perform conformance checking by using trace alignment and as shown above they give us a variety of insights into the differences between the model and the log. However, the analyst needs to analyze each misalignment individually and this requires some extra efforts from his/her side, especially taking into consideration the number of misalignment that result from conformance checking between a real-life event log and the corresponding model. For instance, for the *Road Traffic Management Process*, the number of misalignment is:

- *Replay a Log on Petri Net for All Optimal Alignment*: 406 misalignments out of 412 alignments
- *Replay a Log on Petri Net for Conformance Checking*: 205 misalignments out of 231 alignments.

Therefore, by using these plugins, it is necessary for all these misalignment to be individually examined. Furthermore, as we will show in the next subsection, there are some misalignment that will be only partially detected or impossible to be detected by using trace alignment as it identifies differences at the level of individual traces.

3.2.2 Conformance Checking with Behavioral Alignment

Figure 12, illustrates the result obtained by using the *Compare* plugin in Apromore. In the left panel of this figure we can clearly see the set of statements in natural language showing the differences that are detected between the log and the model and vice-versa.

Figure 12: Behavioral alignment with Compare plugin in Apromore

Using this plugin we will have as an output: **44 statement in natural language** describing the deviations, from which 16 statements are with percentage from 100% to 31% and 28 statements are with percentage 1%. It is important to emphasize that compared with the version used for the original evaluation, the tool has been further improved and it actually offers statistical support for each detected deviation and also it visualizes the deviations and give suggestion for repairing the model.

Table 1 we shows some of the deviations that are detected using behavioral alignment (the ones that can be comparable with the original evaluation), defining their category and a general description:

Nr	Behavioral alignment category	Replicated evaluation	Description
1	Task Relocation	<p>In the log, "<i>Send for credit collection</i>" occurs after "<i>[start event, Create Fine, Send Fine, Insert Fine Notification, Add penalty, Payment]</i>" instead of "<i>[start event, Create Fine, Insert Date Appeal to Prefecture, Send Appeal to Prefecture, Send Fine, Insert Fine Notification, Add penalty]</i>" (in other forms of the deviation <i>Payment</i> task is repeated 2,3,4,10 times).</p> <p>This deviation also appears in other forms, all showing the that "<i>Send for credit collection</i>" occurs after "<i>Payment</i>" in the log instead of after "<i>Add Penalty</i>", but they are defined separately because the path is clearly specified. For instance, some of the other paths are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ...occurs after "<i>[start event, Create Fine, Send Fine, Insert Fine Notification, Payment, Add penalty, Payment]</i>" instead of ... • ...occurs after "<i>[start event, Create Fine, Payment, Send Fine, Insert Fine Notification, Payment, Add penalty, Payment]</i>" instead of ... 	<p>This statement as defined in [1] shows a potential compliance issue: according to the model specifications credit collection should always occur after Add Penalty, but the event log shows that it occurs after payment is done.</p>
2	Causality/ Concurrency mismatch	<p>In the log, after "<i>Insert Fine Notification</i>", "<i>Add Penalty</i>" occurs before "<i>Notify results appeal to offender</i>", while in the model they are concurrent.</p>	<p>As the statement in the original evaluation [1], this statement shows that according to the model penalty should be charged before the appeal , but the log shows that appeal to judge can happen before penalty (the tasks are concurrent).</p>

3	Tasks substitution	<p>In the model, after "Add penalty", "[Send for Credit Collection]" is substituted by "[Insert Date Appeal to Prefecture, Notify Result Appeal to Offender, Receive Result Appeal from Prefecture]" .</p> <p>This deviation also appears in other forms, that consider the lexicographical order of task labels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ... "[Insert Date Appeal to Prefecture, Receive Result Appeal from Prefecture, Send Appeal to Prefecture]" ... • ... "[Insert Date Appeal to Prefecture, Notify Result Appeal to Offender, Receive Result Appeal from Prefecture, Send Appeal to Prefecture]" ... 	<p>This statement shows that "Send by credit Collection" that appears in the event log; in the model is substituted by the set of tasks starting with "Insert Date appeal to prefecture". This means that it happens that after adding the penalty, it is send for credit collection instead of going into the cycle through the prefecture.</p>
4	Unobserved elementary cycle	<p>In the log, the cycle involving [Insert date appeal to prefecture, Receive result appeal from prefecture, Send appeal to prefecture, Notify result appeal to offender] does not occur after "[Create Fine, Send Fine, Insert Fine Notification]" .</p>	<p>As defined in [1], this statement indicates that shows that while in model allows an offender to appeal to the prefecture multiply times, this has never been observed in the event log.</p>

Table 1: A subset of behavioral alignment statements, as the output of Compare plugin in Apromore ⁸

There are also cases of task absence, conflict concurrency mismatch, task skipping, unobserved acyclic interval in the output of behavioral alignment, but they are not included in this report as we can not use them for comparison with the original evaluation (the original evaluation defines clearly only 4 statements).

Based on the original evaluation [1], **we conclude** that there are two statements provided in Table 1 for which trace alignment does not fully provides feedback. *Statement 2*, can not be detected by trace alignment, because it operates in the level of individual traces. Being an example of concurrency causality mismatch, this statement needs an analysis across traces in order to be detected. Also *Statement 4*, that is an example of additional behavior (allowed by the model, but not observed in the log), can only be partially detected by trace alignment, because as showed by the original evaluation these method focus only on fitness. In addition, as original evaluation suggests, to overcome this difficulty we can use "*Check Precision based on Align-ETConformance*" plugin in ProM to identify the escaping edges from which the additional behavior starts. But as defined in [1], this plugin only provides statistics (e.g. precision metrics) and the escaping edges are extracted from the code. But there is no additional information provided on how the extraction from the code is realized; therefore, we were not able to identify escaping edges for the replication.

3.3 Comparison with the original study

Comparing the results of replications with the original qualitative evaluation, we have derived the following conclusions:

- When using *ProM* plugins (*Replay a Log on Petri Net for All Optimal Alignment* and *Replay a Log on Petri Net for Conformance Checking*) we have obtained exactly the same results as the original evaluation. The number of detected misalignments and alignments is exactly the same, as shown in Section 3.2.
- When using *Compare* plugin in *Apromore*, total number of behavioral alignment is 44 statement (from which 16 statements are with percentage from 100%-31% of the traces and 28 statements are with percentage 1% of the traces). Compared with the original evaluation (15 statements), this number is higher (almost three times higher than the result provided by the original evaluation). We think that **one of the reasons for this difference in the result is the fact that the plugin is further developed after [1] and especially implementing the statistical support for each difference may result in having more fine-grained statement** (the replication shows that there are 28 statements with occurrence 1% of the traces). The first statement (Task relocation) in Table 1 can perfectly illustrate this. According to it we have 11 deviations, due to the fact that the path is clearly specified, unlike the original evaluation. The output in the original evaluation does not clearly specifies the path, instead it just mentioned: after "*payment*" (*In the log, "Send for credit collection" occurs after "Payment" and before the end state*). The situation is almost the same for the third example in Table 1, where we have some occurrence of the statement, because the path is clearly defined. In addition, example 2 and 4 in Table 1 are exactly the same with the original evaluation.
- We were unable to use "*Check Precision based on Align-ETConformance*" plugin in *ProM* for identifying escaping edges from which additional model behavior starts. The reason for this is that escaping edges are not shown as the output of the plugin, but they can be extracted from the code. The original evaluation has not clearly described how to achieve this extraction from the code; therefore, we did not performed it. This influenced in verifying that trace alignment can fully identify additional behavior (e.g. *Statement 4* in Table 1).
- We did not succeed in using *ProConformance 1.0* standalone Java tool, despite the fact that the environment was correctly set up (the tool works with the provided example files), the format of PNML file was confirmed using the *WoPeD* (as recommended in the *ReadMe* file of the tool) and the format of XES was verified using *ProM*. This should not be a problem for the evaluation, as long as [1] stated that both tools work in the same way. But taking into consideration the fact that *Compare* plugin of *Apromore* is further improved (statistical support and visual representation of the difference statement), by using *ProConformance*, we could have obtained results closer to the original evaluation and verified our hypothesis that the bigger amount of statements produce by *Apromore* plugin (**44** (from which 28 with occurrence percentage 1% and the remaining 16 from 31% to 100%) vs **15** in the original evaluation), is due to further improving it by adding statistical reporting.

4 Reproducing the Quantitative Evaluation

In this section the replication of the quantitative evaluation will be described, in terms of time performance and number of differences that are produced. We have used only the *IBM BIT* process models collection, as it is publicly available. The original evaluation is performed with a selection of 712 workflow net and sound models. Due to the time limitation for this assignments, we have used 15 process models from BIT collection to perform the replication (models are of different sizes and complexities).

4.1 Steps taken

4.1.1 Obtain IBM BIT process models collection and convert BPMN to Petri Nets

The IBM BIT process models (BPPMN) are obtained from Apromore online repository that is publicly available¹². There is also a folder that contains the PNML format of the models, but when downloaded these files can not be correctly opened in ProM (only a blank screen appears when these files are imported in ProM). For this reason, as shown in figure 13 we have used the BPMN files and converted them into Petri Nets using the ProM plugin: *Convert BPMN diagram to Petri net (control-flow)*(D.Fahland), is Step 2 with parameter for *Soundness checking* and in Step 3 with parameter for *Conformance Checking*.

Figure 13: Converting BPMN to Petri nets for both *Soundness checking* and *Conformance Checking*

¹²<http://apromore.cis.unimelb.edu.au>

4.1.2 Select a subset of the available workflow and sound nets

In this step we have used the Petri Nets obtained from the conversion in Step 1, and applied the plugin *Analyze with Woflan* (H.M.W.Verbeek), to check if the net is workflow net and sound (Figure 14). **This was one of the most time consuming tasks**, as for models above a specific complexity and size, Woflan plugin was taking too much time. Therefore, we were obliged to omit these models from the selection. From this step we selected a subset of **40 workflow and sound nets** to be used for this evaluation. But we have further omitted some of the models due to the out-of-memory exceptions faced with *Generate Event Log from Petri Net* plugin and problem faced with Apromore processing time.

Figure 14: Using *Analyze with Woflan* plugin to select workflow net and sound

4.1.3 Generate event logs from Petri Net.

Generation of the event logs is done by using *Generate event logs from Petri Net* (Seepe vanden Broucke) plugin, as defined in the original evaluation. As mentioned in Section 2 this plugin was not available in *ProM PM 6.8*. We have installed it separately, using the available documentation¹³. To use the plugin we should open *ProM 6.8* from CMD in Windows as shown in Figure 15. It is important to mention that in addition to the command in the corresponding documentation of the tool, **it is important to also add in the path: ProM68_dist/***; otherwise you will not be able to use the plugin, as you will get the error: "*Error: Could not find or load main class org.processmining.contexts.uitopia.UI*"

```
C:\Users\user\ProM68>java -classpath ./plugins/*;./ProM68_lib/*;ProM68_dist/*;.* -Djava.util.Arrays.useLegacyMergeSort=true -Djava.library.p
ath=./ProM68_lib -ea -Xmx2g -XX:MaxPermSize=512m -XX:+UseCompressedOops org.processmining.contexts.uitopia.UI
Java HotSpot(TM) 64-Bit Server VM warning: ignoring option MaxPermSize=512m; support was removed in 8.0
Plug-in level threshold set to Local
Plug-in quality threshold set to VeryPoor
ini file processed
Dec 29, 2018 11:11:58 PM java.util.prefs.WindowsPreferences <init>
WARNING: Could not open/create prefs root node Software\JavaSoft\Prefs at root 0x80000002. Windows RegCreateKeyEx(...) returned error code 5.
>>> Loading packages from C:\Users\user\ProM68\packages\packages.xml
>>> All dependencies have been resolved
>>> Scanning for packages took 0.186 seconds
```

Figure 15: Using *Generate event logs from Petri Net* plugin in ProM 6.8

The plugin is used with the parameters specified in the original evaluation [1], as shown in Figure 16: simulation method: complete generation; min./max. traces to add for each generated sequence: 1; max. times marking seen: 2; only include traces that reach end state; only include traces without remaining tokens. **Also**

¹³<http://processmining.be/loggenerator/>

this step is one of the most time-consuming steps, as the plugin runs into out-of-memory exceptions for models with specific time and complexity. Therefore, we omitted some of the models selected in Section 4.1.2.

Figure 16: Parameters used for *Generate event logs from Petri Net* plugin

4.1.4 Add noise to the event log (5%,10%,15%,20%)

As stated in Section 2, as we were not able to find the plugin implemented by [6], used in the original evaluation [1], we decided to use *Add noise to log filter* plugin for adding noise to the event log. The reason we selected this plugin, was that it works in similar way with the one described at [1]: it enables us to choose the percentage of the events to be removed or added, as shown in figure 17. **This is one of the main deviations from the original evaluation.**

Figure 17: Using *Add noise to log filter* plugin

4.1.5 Conformance checking with trace alignment in ProM

For the subset of process models that we selected we applied conformance checking in ProM, using both: *Replay a Log on Petri Net for All Optimal Alignments* and *Replay a Log on Petri Net for Conformance Checking*, as defined in Section 3.1.3 of Qualitative evaluation.

4.1.6 Conformance checking with behavioral alignment in Apromore

For the subset of process models that we selected we applied conformance checking in Apromore, using *Compare* plugin, as defined in Section 3.1.4 of Qualitative evaluation. For this step, we noticed that for models that generate event logs with more than 1000 events, the Apromore plugin showed problems for noise level 15% and 20% (The plugin keeps processing or runs into "*Exception in the call*" error). Hence, we were obliged to **omit these models from the replication**.

4.1.7 Compare the results of both alignment methods.

Finally we have compared the results achieved by trace alignment and behavioral alignment, in terms of number of deviations produced and execution time.

4.2 Replication Results

As stated in Section 4.12, we started the process of replicating the quantitative evaluation with 40 workflow nets and sound process models. Due to *out of memory exception* faced with "Generate event log from Petri Net plugin" and *Exception in call* faced with Apromore plugin, we ended up with **15 process models for replicating this evaluation**. The subset size was also influenced by the available time for this assignment.

The overall statistics for the model complexity are shown in Table 2. We have also displayed the results of the original evaluation, in order to compare them in Section 4.3. There is a range of model size from 6 to 86 included, with a max of 6 XOR splits and a max of 23 AND splits.

Evaluation	Model statistics	Min	Max	Mean	σ
Replicated Evaluation	Size	6	86	19.44	23.04
	#XOR splits	0	6	2.69	2.05
	Outdegree XOR	2	5	2.5	1
	#AND splits	0	23	4.81	7.3
	Outdegree AND	2	5	2.57	1.16
Original Evaluation	Size	7	177	38.1	30.08
	#XOR splits	0	5	0.61	1
	Outdegree XOR	2	10	2.42	1.18
	#AND splits	0	33	6.49	5.72
	Outdegree AND	2	7	2.08	0.42

Table 2: Statistics on Model complexity for IBM BIT collection

Furthermore, Table 3 shows the overall statistics for the event logs that are generated from the models, for each noise level. The size of event log varies from 8 to 798. As stated in Section 4.1.6, we omitted event logs with more than 1000 events, due to the problems shown by *Apromore* plugin for noise level 15% and 20%. The mean value and the standard error are much higher than the original evaluation, due to the small number of the models that are used.

Evaluation	Noise	Min	Max	Mean	σ
Replicated Evaluation	None	8	789	314.5	257
	5%	8	798	318.25	259
	10%	8	677	365.38	253
	15%	8	795	315.69	259
	20%	8	790	299.4	255
Original Evaluation	None	6	1432	58	120
	5%	6	1427	58	120
	10%	7	1433	58	120
	15%	7	1428	57	120
	20%	7	1428	57	120

Table 3: Statistics on total log size in terms of number of events. As stated in [1]: *With total log size we refer to the total number of events, which corresponds to the sum of the lengths of the traces*

The replication is performed on a machine with a Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-7500U CPU @ 2.7 GHz (4 CPUs), 16 GB RAM, running Windows 8.1 x64 and Java 1.8.0_181. As the original evaluation suggested, each test is executed five times and the average statistics of three executions, removing the fastest and the slowest executions are recorded.

Evaluation	Noise	Min	Max	Mean	σ	Total
Replicated Evaluation	None	0	0	0	0	0
	5%	1	89	22	20	357
	10%	1	129	46	35	858
	15%	2	234	56	77	805
	20%	2	398	128	126	2235
Original Evaluation	None	0	0	0	0	0
	5%	0	42	2	4	480
	10%	0	65	4	7	943
	15%	0	89	5	9	1409
	20%	0	104	7	11	1776

Table 4: Number of difference statements produced by behavioral alignment method (Apromore)

Table 4 shows the number of difference statements that are produced by behavioral alignment method, by using *Compare* plugin in *Apromore*. The number of statement is measured for each noise level. We can see that as expected there is no difference between the model and the event logs without noise. In the extreme case with 20% a set of 398 differences were needed to describe the difference between the log and the model (a log of 790 events and a model of 30 nodes). This is quite a big number, taking into consideration that the main purpose of behavioral alignment method is to be compact and easily interpretable. Furthermore, we can clearly see the difference with the statistics of the original evaluation. We think that the achieved results may be due to the fact that *Compare* plugin in *Apromore* is further improved with statistical support, that can give **more fine-grained results** (*if we do not consider statements that occur 1% of the traces, the max value will be 84 statements, much more compact and interpretable*).

Table 5 shows the number of misalignments detected by trace alignment in *ProM*. The number of misalignment detected by trace alignment is lower than the number of deviations detected by behavioral alignment.

Evaluation	Noise	Min	Max	Mean	σ	Total
Replicated Evaluation	None	0	0	0	0	0
	5%	1	49	21	16	344
	10%	1	53	25	17	456
	15%	3	92	41	29	671
	20%	5	147	64	47	1022
Original Evaluation	None	0	0	0	0	0
	5%	0	36	3	4	795
	10%	1	61	4	6	1194
	15%	1	69	6	8	1567
	20%	1	94	7	10	1864

Table 5: Number of misalignments produced by Replay a log on Petri Net for All Optimal alignment (ProM)

We have not provided statistics for the number of escaping edges, because as stated in Section 3.1.3 we were unable to extract the number of escaping edges from the code of the plugin " *Check Precision based on Align-ETConformance* " in *ProM*. The main reason is that the original evaluation does not clearly shows how this extraction is done (it is not in the output of the plugin).

Furthermore, as *Compare* plugin of *Apromore* is further developed since the original paper [1] was published, its performance time will be highly influence by the fact that the plugin also provides statistical support and visual representation of the differences in the log. Therefore, we decided not to provide statistics for the execution time, as it will be quite higher compared to the original evaluation. In addition, the tool (unlike *ProM*) did not offer an option to show the time for producing the differences. We also tried setting up *Apromore* locally ¹⁴, to interfere with the code and get the performance time from there, but despite the fact that all *Maven* and *Ant* dependencies were set up correctly, we were faced with the problem in Figure 18a, where login screen appears, but "admin" / "password" (or creating a new account) did not work (the recommendation to run "*ant create-h2*" to populate the H2 database did not solve the problem). However, in general, for event logs with a big size (more than 400 events) and with high level of noise (15% and 20%) it was clearly visible that they needed much more time compared with *ProM* conformance checking. Moreover, *Compare* plugin showed to have problems and run into "*Exception in call*" error for logs with more than 1000 events with high noise level, as shown in Figure 18b.

¹⁴<https://github.com/apromore/ApromoreCode/blob/master/README>

(a) Problems in setting up Apromore locally, to get the execution time from the code
 (b) Apromore plugin running into "Exception in call" error for logs with more than 1000 event

Figure 18: Apromore problems for setting it up locally and for event logs beyond a specific size

On the other hand we measured the necessary time for trace alignment in ProM. Despite the small number of tested models, Figure 19 shows, that the time has the same tendency as in the original evaluation: it is positively influenced by the model size and the noise level. Figure 19 is included in this report, just to give a general overview of time performance in ProM, but we have not discussed it further as we are unable to compare it with the time performance of behavioral alignment.

Figure 19: Effect of log size and noise on the time performance of all optimal alignment (IBM BIT)

4.3 Comparison with the original study

Comparing the results of replications with the original quantitative evaluation, we have derived the following conclusions

- The original evaluation uses a collection of **712 models** from both IBM BIT and SAP R/3 collection. Due to the time limitations, we started the replication with 40 models, but we were obliged to eliminate almost half of them to problems faced with *Generate Event Log from Petri Net* plugin, running into "out-of-memory" error and *Compare* plugin in Apromore running into "Exception in the call" error. Therefore for the rest of the evaluation, we used only **15** workflow net and sound process models. This number can not represent the original evaluation, however it gives us a general overview for the performance of both methods.

- Regarding the complexity of the selected models, in terms of size, we selected them to be around half of the size of the original evaluation (see Table 2). In this way we will have acceptable value of the standard deviation, taking into consideration the number of the models that we have used for the replication. This also influence the size of the generated event logs. As shown in table 3, the maximum size of the event logs is almost half of the size of the original evaluation, but the mean and the standard deviation is much more higher due to the low number of process models that we have used.
- We have used exactly the same plugin for generating event logs from Petri Net, *Generate Event Log from Petri Net*, installing it in ProM 6.8 according to the provided documentation (see Section 4.1.3), with the same predefined parameters as the original evaluation. However, it is important to mention that the plugin *Convert BPMN diagram to Petri net(control-flow)* (Section 4.1.1) was not clearly defined in the original paper. We decided to use it, as it offers support for both soundness checking and conformance checking. Choosing this plugin, influences the performance of ProM trace alignment (as the petri net that is generated in this step is further used to evaluate trace alignment) and it can be one of the reasons why we have higher number of misalignment (see Table 5) compared to the original evaluation. It also influences the size of the logs that are generated.
- Another deviation from the original evaluation, as mentioned in Section 4.1.4 was the use of *Add noise to log filter* plugin, as we were not able to find a ProM plugin implemented by [6], used in the original evaluation. We have added the same percentage of noise in the event logs as the original evaluation (5%,10%,15%,20%), but we have no information how the removing or adding of the events through *Add noise to log filter* plugin is done. The original evaluation states that this is done through "adding or removing a random event that already existed in the original log in a random position of a randomly selected trace, until the number of added and removed events equals a percentage of the total number of events in the original log". Furthermore, in every event log of the original evaluation, each distinct trace is duplicated before adding the noise, in order not to increase the total number of traces in the log when the noise is injected. We assumed that this step was performed manually, as there was no information provided; hence, due to time limitations we have not performed this step. We expect this to influence the number of misalignments and differences identified for both trace and behavioral alignment compared to the original evaluation (see Tables 5 and 4).
- Moreover, we were not able to provide the statistics for escaping edges using all optimal alignment in I, because as stated in the original evaluation, these statistics are taken from the code and they are not provided at the output of *Check Precision based on Align-ETConformance* plugin. Therefore, we were not able to analyze how trace alignment deal with additional model behavior.
- Both the number of misalignment from *trace alignment* and the number of deviation detected from *behavioral alignment* is greater than the original evaluation. This result may be due to the reasons mentioned above (using *Convert BPMN diagram to Petri net(control-flow)* plugin, *Add noise to log filter* plugin, not duplicating distinct traces before adding noise). For behavioral alignment method, the bigger number of the deviation may also be related with the statistical support that is added to Apromore, producing in this way more fine-grained results. It is important to mention that from the quantitative evaluation we do not see a clear evidence that behavioral alignment produce a more compact set of statement compared to trace alignment. The reason for this may be the fact that we are considering a small subset of models. However, when analyzing all our 15 models individually, we concluded that only for **7 out of 15 models** the behavioral alignment produces less statement than the trace alignment for all noise levels (these were the smallest models in size, with a maximum of 200

events). When the size of model increases the behavioral alignment produces less statements only for 5% and 10% noise (3 out of 15 models). **Therefore, we can conclude that when the complexity of the models and the noise level increase, there is no clear evidence that behavioral alignment performs better than trace alignment in terms of the number of the statement produced.**

- The last deviation from the original evaluation is that we were not able to perform the comparison between the time performance of the methods. As described above the main reason for this is that Compare plugin in Apromore is further developed by adding statistical support and visual representation, and this improvements will influence the time performance. However, it was clearly visible from the execution that behavioral alignment takes more time than trace alignment, especially for big logs and high level of noise.

5 Conclusions

The main challenge of this replication was setting up all the required plugins and tools to prepare the event logs and process models for the final experiment phase. Furthermore, selecting the right subset of process models for the quantitative evaluation showed to be a time-consuming and demanding task.

The main limitation of the replication was the small number of process models used for the quantitative evaluation (15 vs 348). This leads to a situation when there is no clear evidence that behavioral alignments produce a more compact set of differences compared to the trace alignments. Regarding the tools used, we were unable to perform the experiments with *ProConformance 1.0* and thus used only the *Compare* plugin of *Apromore* to perform them. Using *ProConformance 1.0* might have helped us to avoid the differences in the results that comes from the fact that *Compare* plugin of *Apromore* is further developed by adding statistical reporting and visual representation of the deviations. Regarding the original evaluation, we found the comparison performed with the trace alignment not fully comprehensive in terms of *completeness* of the conformance checking, as there is no clear evidence provided that behavioral alignment covers all the possible deviations detected by trace alignment.

To sum it up, the replication of the qualitative evaluation showed that *ProM* is quite consisted, as exactly the same number of misalignment was detected (we were not able to further verify if they are the same, because the original evaluation did not analyze the individual misalignment in details). Furthermore, despite the fact that we did not obtained exactly the same set of statements by behavioral alignment as the original evaluation (44-from which 28 with occurrence percentage 1% vs 15), the result still supports the conclusion of the original evaluation that behavioral alignment produce a more compact and interpretable set of differences compared with trace alignment. However, the quantitative evaluation pointed out that there is no clear evidence that behavioral alignment has a better performance in terms of the number of statements produced, as the results were not promising when the log size and the noise levels increase. The increase in the number of statement obtained in the replication for both methods, might be related with two plugins used not exactly according to the original evaluation, especially the one for inserting noise in the event logs. In addition, for behavioral alignment, the implementation of statistical support for *Compare* plugin in *Apromore*, may lead in producing more fine-grained deviations. Finally, we were unable to evaluate the time performance of behavioral alignment, as the added statistical support and visual representation highly influence the performance time. Although, it was clearly evident that behavioral alignment needed more time than trace alignment especially when the log size and noise level was high.

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